

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

Advancing knowledge and MCDA tools to assist HTA agencies in evaluating medicines on a common basis

Work Package 7, Task 2, Deliverable 7.2

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WP7, Task 2, Deliverable 7.2 Executive Summary

Motivation and objectives

At its inception, IMPACT HTA WP7 aimed at structuring sound multi-criteria evaluation models within a simple and common, but flexible, framework that would incorporate and reflect the views and value systems of a wide range of decision-makers and stakeholders concerning the evaluation of medicines in the context of HTA. In addition, it would test the use of such methodological framework to build context-specific models for a set of alternative health care interventions through case studies in collaboration with national HTA agencies, through a combination of participatory processes (Delphi panels and decision conferences) involving relevant stakeholders, experts and decision-makers.

Based on these objectives, the specific objective of WP7, Task 2, was twofold: first, to design an MCDA value framework to assess new medicines within the context of HTA on a common basis; this framework would reflect what is important for HTA agency stakeholders and decision-makers; and, second, to define techniques and questioning protocols to enable the implementation of the framework in the assessment of new medicines. The interaction with HTA stakeholders was set to be conducted through collaborative value modelling, i.e. combining non-face-to-face Web-Delphi with face-to-face decision conferencing so as to engage HTA stakeholders in the development and testing of the framework.

WP7 Task 2, resulting in deliverable 7.2 (D7.2), research was led by IST and developed as a collaboration between IST and LSE team members. The output was organized through 4 interlinked research articles (RA), briefly outlined below.

Research Article 1: A systematic review of MCDA in HTA literature

Prior to commencing research on the framework, it was deemed important to analyse existing literature in the area of MCDA in HTA for two reasons: first, to understand the methodological quality of published studies, and, second, to learn about the challenges and limitations identified in previous studies. Accordingly, within Task 2 a comprehensive systematic literature review was undertaken that led to the following article “Multi-criteria decision analysis for health technology assessment: addressing methodological challenges to improve the state of the art” (authors: Mónica Oliveira (IST), Inês Mataloto (IST), Panos Kanavos (LSE); open access article, available from

<https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs10198-019-01052-3>). This article was published in 2019 in the European Journal of Health Economics, with the following abstract:

Multi-criteria decision analysis for health technology assessment: addressing methodological challenges to improve the state of the art

By

Mónica Oliveira, Inês Mataloto, Panos Kanavos

Abstract

Background: Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) concepts, models and tools have been used increasingly in health technology assessment (HTA), with several studies pointing out practical and theoretical issues related to its use. This study provides a critical review of published studies on MCDA in the context of HTA by assessing their methodological quality and summarising methodological challenges.

Methods: A systematic review was conducted to identify studies discussing, developing or reviewing the use of MCDA in HTA using aggregation approaches. Studies were classified according to publication time and type, country of study, technology type and study type. The PROACTIVE-S approach was constructed and used to analyse methodological quality. Challenges and limitations reported in eligible studies were collected and summarised; this was followed by a critical discussion on research requirements to address the identified challenges.

Results: 129 journal articles were eligible for review, 56% of which were published in 2015–2017; 42% focused on pharmaceuticals; 36, 26 and 18% reported model applications, issues regarding MCDA implementation analyses, and proposing frameworks, respectively. Poor compliance with good methodological practice (<25% complying studies) was found regarding behavioural analyses, discussion of model assumptions and uncertainties, modelling of value functions, and dealing with judgment inconsistencies. The five most reported challenges related to evidence and data synthesis; value system differences and participant selection issues; participant difficulties; methodological complexity and resource balance; and criteria and attributes modelling. A critical discussion on ways to address these challenges ensues.

Discussion and implications: Results highlight the need for advancement in robust methodologies, procedures and tools to improve the methodological quality of MCDA in HTA studies. Research pathways include developing new model features, good practice guidelines, technologies to enable participation and behavioural research.

The research work developed in Task 2 highly benefited from the insights and results of this literature review.

Research Article 2: A framework to assist the identification of HTA agency stakeholder groups

An initial attempt at analysing stakeholder involvement in medicines evaluation processes revealed that it was not clear from the literature which stakeholders and experts should be involved in HTA participatory processes and why. In order to address this, research was developed to design and test a new framework to provide a rationale and identify for a given country or context which stakeholders should be involved in HTA agency participatory processes.

This research led to the manuscript entitled “Understanding stakeholders’ roles and involvement in national Health Technology Assessment agency evaluation processes: A new framework based on Critical Systems Heuristics” – authored by Ana Vieira (IST), Mónica Oliveira (IST), Aris Angelis (LSHTM and LSE), Panos Kanavos (LSE) and Carlos Bana e Costa (IST) – which has been submitted for publication. A summary of this study is shown below:

Understanding stakeholders’ roles and involvement in national Health Technology Assessment agency evaluation processes: A new framework based on Critical Systems Heuristics

By

Ana Vieira, Mónica Oliveira, Aris Angelis, Panos Kanavos, Carlos Bana e Costa

Abstract

Objectives: To understand stakeholders' roles and involvement in national Health Technology Assessment (HTA) agency evaluation processes. Emphasis is placed on stakeholders' interests, concerns and values in the assessment of new medicines.

Methods: The original Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) 12 questions were adapted for the HTA context to understand medicines evaluation processes by focusing on four basic aspects, notably, 'boundary issues' (motivation, control, knowledge and legitimacy), each sub-divided into three categories (social roles, specific concerns and key problems). The adapted CSH framework was then applied through an expert consultation with HTA agencies, using a questionnaire. Primary data were collected from eleven study participants having a current or previous affiliation with six HTA agencies (NICE, SMC, HAS, TLV, IQWiG, AOTMiT).

Results: The application of the adapted CSH framework revealed two main types of findings. First, it identified seven stakeholder groups as being relevant in HTA new medicines evaluation processes: (a) patients and carers, (b) general population, (c) industry, (d) payers and policymakers, (e) HTA agencies, (f) healthcare professionals, and (g) scientific experts and methodologists. Second, a conceptual model enabled the understanding of the rationale for involving different stakeholder groups in such processes by analysing the motivation, power, knowledge and legitimacy aspects driving evaluation processes in HTA agencies.

Conclusions: The adapted CSH framework can be used for analysing the rationale of HTA organisations in terms of stakeholder engagement. It enables a reflection of current stakeholder roles within HTA evaluation processes while being aligned with the promotion of legitimacy, representativeness and accountability in medicines evaluation.

Information on HTA agency stakeholder groups generated in this study was used both in the consultation processes to inform the building of the HTA framework, as well as in the analysis of Web-Delphi processes.

Research Article 3: The IMPACT HTA value framework

The core of Task 2 was research undertaken to create a value framework that can be used to evaluate medicines from different disease specificities and with variable evidence and data, that would be of assistance to HTA agencies and healthcare decision-makers. From a literature standpoint, earlier research indicated that there were, indeed, difficulties in having such a framework, which respects context-specific deliberative processes (e.g., in the context of an HTA committee practice), therefore, the added value of this part of Task 2 was the development of a proposal for “The IMPACT-HTA multicriteria value framework to assist HTA agencies in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”. The proposed the IMPACT HTA framework has the following key features:

1. It entails a general and novel multicriteria value frame model structure, which is adjusted for distinct therapeutic indications, and set by the HTA agency; and the HTA agency then sets guidelines for committees making evaluations on a structured but flexible format, accounting for the value aspects and their relevance for each therapeutic indication;
2. Uses collaborative value modelling to build and use the IMPACT HTA value framework: a large number of HTA agency stakeholders and experts are involved in setting the general value frame and adjusting the value frame for the distinct therapeutic indications; and then HTA agency committee members can work within a structured format and prior to the meeting, interact through a Web-Delphi process designed to collect the group judgments on difference of value between specific medicines in the relevant evaluation criteria, so as to build a MACBETH value model.

This work is reported in a manuscript entitled “The IMPACT-HTA multicriteria value framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis” authored by Mónica Oliveira (IST), Ana Vieira (IST), Klara Dimitrovová (IST), Aris Angelis (LSHTM, LSE), Panos Kanavos (LSE), Carlos Bana e Costa (IST)) that is currently being refined for submission to peer review, based on comments and feedback received. The abstract below, outlines the content of this work.

The IMPACT-HTA multicriteria value framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis

by

Monica Oliveira, Ana Vieira, Klara Dimitrovová, Aris Angelis, Panos Kanavos, Carlos Bana e Costa

Abstract

Health Technology Assessment (HTA) agencies make several decisions, which require the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis and the consideration of multiple criteria. These decisions are not always made using structured formats, nor are they supported by analytical tools. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is increasingly explored as an option to address these gaps, as it enables evaluations on a structured basis, involving stakeholders and experts, and considering multiple evaluation dimensions. However, MCDA models to evaluate health technologies available in the literature have mostly been developed for specific contexts, for instance, with specific model structures and sets of weights, and do not equip HTA agencies and the relevant committees with tools to evaluate distinct medicines on a structured basis and based on a common value frame.

In this study we outline the development and testing of the IMPACT HTA socio-technical framework to assist HTA agencies in valuing medicines across multiple dimensions of benefit, across diseases and on a common basis. Technically, the framework combines the (MCDA) MACBETH approach with concepts of the swing weighting matrix such that (a) a common value frame is determined by the HTA agency for groups of therapeutic indications, and (b) committees can evaluate medicines on a structured basis departing from the value set defined by the agency. Socially, the framework is developed through a collaborative modelling approach in which key HTA stakeholders and members of evaluation committees are involved in a sequence of Delphi and decision conferencing processes, to (a) develop both the value frame for different therapeutic indications, and (b) determine the MACBETH value models for the evaluation of specific medicines.

From the perspective of an HTA agency, the framework entails two phases: first, through a consultation with relevant stakeholders and experts, a general (multicriteria) value frame structure is built, which is adjusted for features of distinct therapeutic indications; based on that, guidance is prepared for evaluation committees to enable evaluations on a structured but flexible format; and,

second, evaluation committees make structured assessments with the MACBETH value measurement approach while considering the relevant value aspects set for the therapeutic indication under consideration.

The paper shows how phase 1 has been implemented and tested with the views of a large number of European HTA stakeholders and experts and depicts the views of experts of the INAMI HTA Belgium agency.

The IMPACT HTA framework was successfully tested in a sequence of enriching Delphi and decision conferencing processes, showing its potential for use, as well as contributing to the validation of the framework features. Out of the several Delphi processes carried out to consult HTA agency stakeholders, a significant amount of information was generated on (a) the aspects that should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines in general and for distinct therapeutic indications, and (b) obtaining qualitative insights from participants. Web-Delphi processes, used to generate this information and elicit participant preferences and insights, have shown to be an effective form to capture the views of multiple HTA stakeholders and experts. Statistical analysis carried out in one of the Web-Delphi processes has led to research work 4, outlined below.

Research Article 4: Exploring HTA stakeholder views on value aspects in the evaluation of new medicines

When developing the IMPACT HTA multicriteria value framework, six groups of HTA agency stakeholders and experts were invited to participate in six parallel Web-Delphi processes whose Delphi question was whether the participants considered a list of value aspects relevant for the evaluation of new medicines. In order to develop an understanding on the perspectives of HTA agencies' stakeholders and experts, a manuscript entitled "Exploring HTA stakeholders' views on value aspects in the evaluation of new medicines", authored by Klara Dimitrovová (IST), Ana Vieira (IST), Monica Oliveira (IST), Aris Angelis (LSHTM, LSE), Panos Kanavos (LSE), Carlos Bana e Costa (IST)) was prepared and submitted for publication. The manuscript abstract is provided below:

Exploring HTA stakeholders' views on value aspects in the evaluation of new medicines

By

Klara Dimitrovová, Ana Vieira, Monica Oliveira, Aris Angelis, Panos Kanavos, Carlos Bana e Costa

Abstract

Introduction: Comprehensive stakeholder engagement has been recognised as being key for increasing legitimacy in Health Technology Assessment (HTA) decision processes, with different HTA agencies involving a range of stakeholders in distinct ways. This study collects and analyses the views of *all* relevant stakeholder groups on which value aspects should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines.

Methods: Six parallel two-round web-Delphi panels were conducted to elicit the views of six stakeholder groups and determine their level of agreement on 24 previously identified value aspects potentially relevant for the evaluation of new medicines, using a five-point Likert scale. The most relevant value aspects for each stakeholder group were identified based on the rating agreement percentages. Inter-rater agreement and heterogeneity in the views between the six stakeholder groups were also estimated.

Results: A total of 153 participants (78.5% response rate) completed the web-Delphi process. More than half of the 24 value aspects were considered relevant for the evaluation of new medicines. Inter-rater agreement (Gwet's coefficient) suggests a substantial agreement ($0.60 < K_{\gamma} \leq 0.80$) within participants of two stakeholder groups (i.e., payers & policy-makers and healthcare professionals) and a moderate agreement ($0.40 < K_{\gamma} \leq 0.60$) within participants of four stakeholder groups (i.e., industry, HTA agencies, scientific experts, and patients & carers). Heterogeneity in opinions was found for 9 out of the 24 value aspects between stakeholder groups.

Conclusion: HTA agencies can gain valuable insights from stakeholder involvement; such insights may be relevant in decision-making. Stakeholder involvement requires the adoption of methods to promote consensus in technology assessment. Results suggest that health technology assessments should consider a wide range of value aspects.

Key messages from this study, from the viewpoint of the framework, are as follows: first, there seems to be a consensus across HTA agency stakeholder groups regarding the relevance of a large number of value aspects in the evaluation of medicines (going beyond aspects currently made explicit by HTA agencies); and, second, consensus and divergencies between groups concerning some aspects were found (e.g., divergences between patients and carers on one hand and other stakeholders on the other, regarding some aspects), highlighting both similarities as well as differences in the perception of certain value aspects by individual stakeholders.

Key insights from WP7 Task 2

Task 2 has succeeded in proposing (a) a framework to help identify HTA agency stakeholders and their roles, and (b) the IMPACT HTA framework, which was tested in WP7 Task 3, thus validating the proposal in Task 2.

The process of building the IMPACT-HTA multicriteria value framework was designed to generate a sequence of participatory Delphi processes to collect the views of a large number of HTA-related stakeholders, including health care professionals, patients, regulators, payers, methodology experts, and industry, in collaboration with HTA agencies so as to reflect their value concerns. Web-Delphi processes were found to be successful in engaging a significant number of HTA stakeholders and experts from different geographies while promoting consensus (N=153).

The IMPACT HTA multicriteria value framework includes a set of protocols, techniques and methods enabling its implementation at the HTA agency level in Task 3, through a series of realistic and product-specific case studies.

The research developed as part of Task 2 was conscious of the costs and feasibility issues to HTA agencies of implementing the IMPACT HTA value framework. First, the framework is suitable for health care systems and HTA agencies who (a) recognise that several criteria and objectives (beyond the traditional health gains and costs) need to be considered in the evaluation of new medicines, and (b) perceive the need to align evaluation committees with the views of the HTA agency in considering these objectives, so as to avoid inconsistencies in assessments across committees that have been identified in HTA literature.

Second, in a first stage, implementing the IMPACT HTA value framework requires that HTA agencies engage their stakeholders and experts in a process of identifying which value aspects are relevant for distinct therapeutic indications (classifying value aspects by relevance). Although this requires time and cost (e.g. to design and implement Web-Delphis and workshops), this is needed so that both the agency and the respective evaluation committee(s) have better guidance on which evaluation aspects are essential, influential or complementary in the evaluation of medicines in distinct therapeutic contexts. In so doing, the HTA agency will define its value frame and this is a process that occurs once, with periodical adjustments.

Third, the IMPACT HTA value framework requires a change in (a) the way HTA agencies provide guidance to HTA evaluation committees and (b) the way new medicines' dossiers of evidence and data are gathered. Implementing the IMPACT HTA value framework requires that dossiers with information on medicines to be relayed to evaluation committees (prepared by the HTA agency or by the sponsor) will include more comprehensive evidence and data, including expert views. Although this potentially entails a cost related to evidence collection, evaluation committees will access a more comprehensive set of information than they currently do and, as a result, will be better informed.

Fourth, by following the IMPACT HTA value framework, evaluation committees will assess new technology submissions based on more comprehensive information, which include multiple value aspects; unavoidably, submission dossiers following the IMPACT HTA value framework may require more time to study and prior to the HTA evaluation committee meeting, committee members may need to interact and provide their views in a non-face to face process (e.g. a web-Delphi), which is an additional step compared with current practice. Nevertheless, adhering to such a structured and consensus-building format, the work of evaluation can be delivered more effectively and efficiently.

Fifth, given that it is not common for HTA agency members to have knowledge on MCDA, there may be a need for MCDA training. Agencies could either introduce a facilitator to the work of evaluation committees, or assign that role to a member of the evaluation committee.

Sixth, for an expedited implementation of the IMPACT HTA value framework, it would be important to make available a fit-for-purpose Web-Delphi platform and decision conferencing facilities so that any HTA agency and the respective evaluation committee can adapt the platform and involve the relevant stakeholders and experts in the HTA process.

Seventh, provisions of the IMPACT HTA value framework can be applied in the context of an EU approach to technology assessment to inform recommendations that could be of use to national stakeholders and HTA agencies operating at Member State level.

Hence, the IMPACT HTA value framework potentially changes the paradigm of assessing/appraising medical technologies and arriving at coverage recommendations. Although its adoption requires some initial investment in refining evaluation processes and guidance to evaluation committees, undertaking staff training, and installing new, but inexpensive, infrastructure, it offers a way for evaluation committees to work in more structured and efficient format.

Overall, the objectives set in the IMPACT HTA proposal for WP7, task 2, were met in full. Small adjustments took place given the flow and the results of the research.

Structure of the complete WP7 Deliverable 7.2 report

The complete version of WP7 Deliverable 7.2 (D7.2) report includes this executive summary and the following research papers:

- Part I: “Multi-criteria decision analysis for health technology assessment: addressing methodological challenges to improve the state of the art” (published article);
- Part II: “Understanding stakeholders’ roles and involvement in national Health Technology Assessment agency evaluation processes: A new framework based on Critical Systems Heuristics” (article submitted for publication);
- Part III: Draft article “The IMPACT-HTA multicriteria value framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis” (article in preparation for submission);
- Part IV: “Exploring HTA stakeholders' views on value aspects in the evaluation of new medicines” (article submitted for publication); and
- Part V: Key underlying materials produced in Task 2, which support the information reported in draft articles, and which can be used for further research:
 - Appendices:
 - Reports sent to participants of the first web-Delphi process with an international panel of HTA agency stakeholders and experts, composed by six parallel Web-Delphi processes from six HTA agency stakeholder and expert groups:

- Report to payers and policy makers
- Report to industry
- Report to patients and carers
- Report to scientific experts and methodologists
- Report to health care professionals
- Report to HTA agencies
- Report sent to participants of the second web-Delphi with an international panel of HTA agency stakeholders and experts; and
- Report summarising Web-Delphi results for INAMI on the relevance of value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in five disease contexts.

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

Task 2, Part I: Multi-criteria decision analysis
for health technology assessment:
addressing methodological challenges to
improve the state of the art

Mónica Oliveira (IST), Inês Mataloto (IST), Panos Kanavos
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Multi-criteria decision analysis for health technology assessment: addressing methodological challenges to improve the state of the art

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Abstract

Background Multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) concepts, models and tools have been used increasingly in health technology assessment (HTA), with several studies pointing out practical and theoretical issues related to its use. This study provides a critical review of published studies on MCDA in the context of HTA by assessing their methodological quality and summarising methodological challenges.

Methods A systematic review was conducted to identify studies discussing, developing or reviewing the use of MCDA in HTA using aggregation approaches. Studies were classified according to publication time and type, country of study, technology type and study type. The PROACTIVE-S approach was constructed and used to analyse methodological quality. Challenges and limitations reported in eligible studies were collected and summarised; this was followed by a critical discussion on research requirements to address the identified challenges.

Results 129 journal articles were eligible for review, 56% of which were published in 2015–2017; 42% focused on pharmaceuticals; 36, 26 and 18% reported model applications, issues regarding MCDA implementation analyses, and proposing frameworks, respectively. Poor compliance with good methodological practice (<25% complying studies) was found regarding behavioural analyses, discussion of model assumptions and uncertainties, modelling of value functions, and dealing with judgment inconsistencies. The five most reported challenges related to evidence and data synthesis; value system differences and participant selection issues; participant difficulties; methodological complexity and resource balance; and criteria and attributes modelling. A critical discussion on ways to address these challenges ensues.

Discussion Results highlight the need for advancement in robust methodologies, procedures and tools to improve methodological quality of MCDA in HTA studies. Research pathways include developing new model features, good practice guidelines, technologies to enable participation and behavioural research.

Keywords Multi-criteria decision analysis · Health technology assessment · Systematic review · Methodological quality · Methodological challenges · MCDA modelling

JEL Classification I (Health education and welfare) · I10 (General) · I18 (Government policy regulation public health) · C44 (Operations research statistical decision theory) · D80 (General)

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Background

In a context of increased ageing and epidemiological change, technological advances, increasing patient expectations and budget constraints, health systems are facing considerable challenges to improve access to innovation, enhance rationality in decision-making processes, and improve their efficiency and effectiveness. In this context, health technology assessment (HTA) is playing a critical role by bringing together evidence to help healthcare decision-makers

in understanding the relative value of health technologies [1, 2].

As a multidisciplinary field involving theoretical and practice-oriented research to assess the direct and indirect consequences of health technology use [3], HTA is currently challenged in various ways. First, despite the increased use of HTA in many jurisdictions [4], a number of new health technologies—for instance biomedical technologies—are increasingly approved and adopted based on limited evidence on safety and effectiveness, with assessment under real-world conditions being rare, and technologies being used for little or no additional health gain [5]. Second, effective use of HTA requires the involvement of health stakeholders and the implementation of HTA findings, which is far from happening on a routine basis [6]. Third, HTA needs to resolve issues related to the deployment of existing evaluation methods and processes (with some methodological issues, such as the extent to which cost-effectiveness analysis is appropriate to evaluate all types of health technologies, remaining unresolved) [6, 7] and to address the lack of good quality evidence for many evaluation contexts and technologies [8]. Fourth, for HTA to have an impact there is a need to link and align decision processes at distinct health system levels, as decisions at these levels inter-relate [8]. Nevertheless, health technology decision-making by HTA agencies, hospitals and other organisations often remains unconnected. Finally, HTA needs to go beyond the evaluation of pharmaceuticals, with literature acknowledging that other technologies (such as medical devices and health information systems), or, indeed, the broader space of health care interventions, place additional challenges from a methodological and practical perspective [9].

At the core of HTA is the task of measuring additional value, aligned with the spirit that ‘you manage what you value’ [10] and the promotion of value for money in health systems [2]. Most literature in the health field has focused on traditional techniques based on the measurement of value as captured by comparative effectiveness, with effectiveness being centred on health outcomes or on health utilities. Emerging literature, however, has been exploring alternative and more comprehensive ways to measure value. In line with views that other dimensions are relevant for decision-making regarding health technology adoption (for instance equity and innovation), with a sense of inevitability in considering other criteria than clinical-and-cost-effectiveness [11], and with evidence suggesting that HTA agencies consider in practice other aspects in adoption, reimbursement and pricing decisions [12, 13], several studies have been exploring the use of multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) concepts in HTA.

Framed within decision analysis, MCDA operates within a paradigm of rationality, as defined by Simon [14], offering “a philosophy, articulated by a set of logical axioms and a

methodology and collection of systematic procedures, based on those axioms” [15]. As a sound approach with theoretical foundations, MCDA can be seen as “an extension of decision theory that covers any decision with multiple objectives, a methodology for appraising alternatives on individual, often conflicting criteria, and combining them into one overall appraisal” [16]. As a field it operates as a toolbox offering a wide range of concepts, models and tools and a clear framework for thinking about resource allocation decisions and a common language [17].

The potential of MCDA in the health field has been discussed widely; such discussion has led to two taskforce reports from the International Society for Pharmacoeconomics and Health Outcomes (ISPOR) [18, 19] and to several literature reviews [20–23]. The usefulness of MCDA in HTA has been supported in a number of other studies [11, 24]. Clear arguments provided for its use have been its alignment with value-based health care [25]; its encompassing nature and ability to account for health stakeholder preferences and values [26]; its transparent and synthesis reporting format [27]; its contribution in helping decision-makers to understand technology value and data gaps [21] and differences between evidence and value judgments [19]; its easily understandable outputs [24]; and the underlying link with the accountability for reasonableness principle [28]. MCDA has been recalled as a commonly used approach for priority-setting [29], and a number of organisations, including the European Medicines Agency and the Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG) in Germany, have shown interest and explored the use of MCDA methods in drug regulatory science and HTA, respectively [30].

Although MCDA provides theoretically sound methods to balance costs, benefits and risks, and multicriteria models have been seen as intuitive by evaluators, several studies [19, 30–33] have pointed to a number of shortcomings: first, publications under the ‘MCDA in HTA’ umbrella have sometimes used methods without a sound basis or made an inadequate use of existing methods [32, 33]. Second, studies have recognised the need to develop methods, knowledge and guidelines in the area, for instance, to address the use of inappropriate procedures for weighting (not accounting for attribute ranges [33] leads to the most common mistake reported in decision analysis literature [34]), a lack of testing for the adequacy of using additive model structures [32], and the need for developing methodological and practical guidelines to assist MCDA users [19]. Third, most articles in the literature have reported pilot and exploratory studies of MCDA in HTA, with few studies reporting successful implementations of MCDA models and results in the context of HTA, and with some studies reporting cognitive difficulties from participants in the process of model-building [19].

Despite these shortcomings, there is no comprehensive analysis of the extent to which methodological issues related

to the application of MCDA in the context of HTA affect the credibility and policy-usefulness of published literature, and the range of challenges and limitations that need to be addressed by MCDA in this context. In light of this, the aim of the study is fourfold: first, to provide a critical review of published studies in the field; second, by applying a framework, to analyse the quality of MCDA studies in the context of HTA from a methodological perspective, as distinct from a policy-perspective that could have been adopted as an alternative; third, to summarise challenges and limitations reported in relevant studies; and, fourth, to reflect on how MCDA applied in the context of HTA can overcome these challenges and limitations. The study contributes to the literature in four ways: first, it provides a critical appraisal of studies applying MCDA in the context of HTA, their scope and trends; second, it defines and applies an approach to assess the methodological quality of MCDA model applications; third, it informs on which modelling steps improvements are needed; fourth it identifies and reports on a number of methodological challenges and limitations that need to be addressed and discusses how future studies can overcome these challenges.

The study is organized as follows: the “[Methods](#)” section outlines the review protocol and the methods used in the analysis of eligible studies, discusses the methodological quality framework and the process followed to collect and summarise challenges and limitations. The next two sections report the results, and discuss the results and reflect upon how MCDA in HTA can address the identified challenges and limitations. Finally, the last section concludes.

Methods

Review protocol and studies’ analyses

We conducted a systematic search on 18 September 2017 on the databases: PubMed, EBSCO, Web of Science, ScienceDirect and SAGE. A search protocol was developed and applied on the title and abstract fields, with a keyword combination recognising the range of terminological variations regarding MCDA and HTA (for instance related with similar designations such as multi- vs. multiple, criteria vs. attribute, decision analysis vs. decision aiding vs. decision theory, HTA vs. benefit-risk assessment). The search protocol, including all combinations used is shown in Appendix A. The literature search was restricted to journal articles and book chapters written in English, with no time constraints being applied. Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) [35] guidelines were taken into consideration in the development of the study.

Duplicates were removed from the collected studies, and titles and abstracts were screened by two reviewers

(MO and IM) by applying the following predefined inclusion criteria: studies would have to discuss, develop or review the use of multi-criteria analysis (focusing on aggregation approaches only, notably following the strategy of first modelling components of value explicitly and then aggregating these components) for the evaluation of health technologies administered by the health sector. The review took a broad perspective on MCDA as a strict view would require considering only MCDA studies respecting decision theory principles. Studies explicitly structuring the criteria were included if they indicated to be a step towards MCDA model development. Similarly, studies using non-aggregation approaches (e.g. discrete choice experiments) were included only if they provided data to be used as an input to multicriteria aggregation models. Finally, other systematic literature reviews identified as part of the search strategy were included in the eligible studies.

The following exclusion criteria were applied: studies focusing on technologies not strictly classified as health technologies or not administered by the health sector, such as water cleaning technologies, medical waste, solid waste, environmental health, pure or general risk assessment; studies in which multiple criteria were not directly applied to a HTA context, including safety and efficacy assessment used in studies other than marketing authorisation; retrospective evaluation studies (strictly inferring criteria from previous decisions); decision quality and behavioural decision analysis studies; clinical reasoning and descriptive clinical decision-making studies; studies that presented a minor MCDA component, namely those having MCDA combined with other modelling approaches and those discussing several evaluation approaches, but with minor MCDA explanation or discussion, or with little more than mentioning MCDA as a technique among other evaluation techniques; studies recommending the use of MCDA without a detailed discussion about its rationale; MCDA patient preference assessment studies if they were not designed to directly compare health technologies (e.g. those to build quality of life utility scores); studies in languages other than English; and studies corresponding to conference proceedings were excluded if not adhering to the implemented protocol.

The full-text of the articles considered eligible was obtained from public sources or requested from the authors if not available otherwise. Articles for which the full-text was not made available, were removed. Supplementary articles and book chapters that were not found through the protocol but were identified along the initial review of studies and deemed to be within the protocol scope and published before the end of 2017 were added.

Analysis of eligible studies

The studies included for systematic review were classified with regards to the time of publication, type of journal, country of study, health technology focus and type of study. Since the number of studies covering the scope of this review has been increasing considerably since 2008 and one aimed at capturing recent trends (while avoiding periods with small numbers of studies, year fluctuations and uncomparable periods), periods of 3 years from 2009 onwards were considered, resulting in four time windows: up to 2008, 2009–2011, 2012–2014, 2015–2017.

Regarding the health technology focus, the following categories were considered: pharmaceuticals, vaccines, medical devices, nanotechnologies, general health technologies (e.g. medical devices or medical equipment), and health interventions (e.g. assessing tobacco control vs. promoting physical activity in the workplace vs. prescribing to control blood pressure). Studies not focusing on a specific type of health technology were classified as general health technologies; and studies centred on health interventions, strategies or programmes to promote individual or community health benefits, health equity or healthy behaviours were classified as health interventions.

Publications were also classified according to their methodological/conceptual/theoretical or practical/empirical focus: clinical, non-clinical (but health related), Operational Research/Management Science or interdisciplinary.

Regarding the country of study, studies were classified according to the institutional location of the first author.

Regarding the type of study, studies were categorized according to their main focus in the following categories: methodological or conceptual frameworks, analysis of issues, systematic literature reviews, structuring criteria studies, modelling approach studies, or model applications. Frameworks were defined as studies suggesting the use of MCDA methods and tools for HTA and defining guidelines or procedures for its use; analysis of issues were studies calling attention and discussing issues related to the development and use of MCDA in HTA; structuring criteria studies were those analysing the evaluation dimensions to be used within the scope of MCDA modelling; modelling approach studies were those developing MCDA approaches to address HTA issues; finally, model applications were studies reporting MCDA evaluation models to compare health technologies in practice. Within each type of study, the focus of the reported research was analysed.

Framework for analysing methodological quality

As no established approach for assessing the methodological quality of MCDA studies has been reported [36], this study developed the PROACTIVE-S approach for this purpose, as

an enhancement to the PROACTIVE (Problem, Reframe, Objective, Alternatives, Consequences and Chances, Trade-Offs, Integrate, Value, and Explore and Evaluate) approach [37] that in itself was inspired in the PrOACT-URL approach (PROblem, Objectives, Alternatives, Consequences, Trade-offs, Uncertainty, Risk attitudes, and Linked decisions) [38]. PROACTIVE specifies each of these components as a modelling step in which some tools may be used, while it builds upon the eight elements for sound decision processes defined in the Smart Choices PrOACT-URL approach [38]. Both PROACTIVE and PrOACT-URL are explicit processes that require a clear and deep understanding by decision-makers before they commit to a decision [38] and are aligned with a value-focused thinking perspective, which is specifically useful to: (a) guide strategic thinking, (b) facilitate collective decision-making, (c) uncover hidden objectives, (d) direct the collection of information and (e) improve communication [34]. In comparison to PrOACT-URL, PROACTIVE makes more explicit the role of evidence, values, uncertainty and integration of these components [37], which are deemed particularly relevant in the context of HTA.

To produce an approach that can be used for the assessment of methodological quality of MCDA studies according to good practice considerations, PROACTIVE-S was developed (see Table 1) by adapting, adjusting, enhancing and improving PROACTIVE by:

- (a) adjusting some steps and specifying each step into a set of sub-steps that detail good practice considerations based on multi-criteria decision theory, value measurement and value focused thinking literature [16, 34, 39–41] and studies reflecting good practice aspects regarding the use of MCDA in health [18, 19, 42–44];
- (b) adding a “social step” (S) to ensure rigor, reliability and potential replicability of MCDA in HTA studies and understand participants’ attitudes and consensus regarding the constructed models. Adding this step is aligned with the view that MCDA modelling inherently follows a socio-technical approach that “combines technical elements of MCDA with social aspects of decision conferencing, resulting in a tested approach to working with key players that creates shared understanding of the issues, a sense of common purpose and commitment to the way forward” [45] and builds upon the socio-technical design principles proposed by Cherns [46]. Accordingly, social processes—that can encompass face-to-face, non-face-to-face processes or a combination of both—need to be properly designed and tested within MCDA for HTA.

The following steps from PROACTIVE are adjusted and divided into several sub-steps, and the “S” extra step is added:

Table 1 Defining the PROACTIVE-S approach to analyse the methodological quality of evaluation models reported in the “MCDA in HTA” literature. Source: the authors

PROACTIVE-S step	Step scope	Sub-step good practice considerations—the extent to which the study...	Sub-step abbreviation
Problem	Define the problem	...describes the evaluation context, the decision goal and reflects upon the type of evaluation problem (decision problematique) [40]	P1
Reframe	Reframe relevant multiple perspectives	...considers/discusses the perspectives of relevant stakeholders and key players, clarifies the perspective of the problem owner [203] and discusses whose views should be considered in model building [43]	R1
Objective	Focus on the objectives	...focuses on the objectives to be achieved [34] (rather than on focusing upon indicators and criteria)	O1
Alternatives	Consider all relevant alternatives	...defines and discusses the relevant health technologies to be evaluated and linked decisions [38]	A1
Consequences and chances	Model consequences, uncertainty and lack data	...assesses relevant consequences in adequate attributes that comply with required properties (measurable, operational, understandable) [34, 47] and organises options consequences into a performance matrix [18]	C1
		...discusses data sources and issues [42], as well as consequences' uncertainty [41]	C2
Trade-offs	Understand value trade-offs	...discusses trade-offs among competing objectives or criteria [34]	T1
Integrate	Integrate the evidence and values	...distinguishes between evidence, options' performance and value information in model building [18]	I1
Value	Build a value model and maximize value	...discusses model respect for exhaustiveness, non-redundancy and non-overlap properties in additive models or other relevant properties for other models [34]	V1
		...discusses preference independence conditions and presents the underlying model structure (p.e. additive model formula) [39, 41]	V2
		...uses methods for model building that comply with multiattribute decision theory [16, 39]	V3
		...defines mechanisms to detect and correct inconsistencies [19, 48]	V4
		...uses procedures to model value functions [34, 41]	V5
		...uses weighting procedures that utilize weighting references [34], explaining the rationale for choosing those references [40, 48]	V6
Explore and Evaluate	Explore assumptions and evaluate uncertainty	...explicitly model assumptions and the relevant uncertainties for the evaluation context (p.e. imprecise consequences, variable consequences, quality of evidence, structural uncertainty and judgmental uncertainty) [19]	E1
		...tests the consequences of model assumptions and uncertainty (e.g. sensitivity, robustness and/or scenario analyses) [45]	E2
		...discusses model validation and requisiteness [45, 49] and questions model results [41]	E3
		...uses computer technology to display results and motivate discussion [50, 51]	E4

Table 1 (continued)

PROACTIVE-S step	Step scope	Sub-step good practice considerations—the extent to which the study...	Sub-step abbreviation
Social	Build and implement a socio-technical design	...the study is replicable by making explicit: model building participants, participatory scope and format, participatory timeline, and protocols of questioning [48, 52]	S1
		...takes into consideration behavioural aspects, such as cognitive burden and potential biases [53–55]	S2
		...promotes participants reflection and iterativeness in model development while promoting consensus [45] and/or reflects in ways to combine participants' assessments [52]	S3

- Consequences and chances need to consider not only aspects related to the proper construction of attributes [34, 47] that serve to characterise technology performance [18], but also to discuss data sources, issues [42] and uncertainty [41].
- Value measurement requires considering that the properties needed for using an additive model properties and model structures are sustained and reflected upon [34, 39, 41], that methods complying with multi-attribute decision theory are adopted [16, 39], that mechanisms to detect and correct inconsistencies are utilized [19, 48], that procedures to model value functions are used [34, 41], and that weighting procedures making use of weighting references are used [34] and the rationale for choosing those references is explained [40, 48].
- Explore and evaluate requires reflecting upon model assumptions and uncertainties [19] and testing the consequences of assumptions and uncertainties [45], discussing model validation and requisiteness issues [45, 49] and questioning model results [41], and using decision support technology (e.g. IT) to display results and motivate discussion [50, 51].
- The added social component (S) requires that the social process is described in detail [48, 52] (for instance for replicability and to enable result interpretation), takes into consideration behavioural aspects [53–55], promotes participants' reflection and consensus [45] and/or reflects how to combine participant assessments [52].

Protocol for identifying limitations and challenges

To collect information on limitations and challenges concerning the use of MCDA models in the context of HTA, articles were searched for the words “limitat*”, “challenge*”, “barrier*”, “difficult*”, “pitfall*”, “disadvantage*”, “accept*”, “implement*”, and “concern*”. Reported issues related to the use of MCDA in HTA were collected, for instance, general HTA concerns not specifically related to

MCDA were not considered, and subsequently were clustered with similar or related limitations and challenges. The 12 most frequently cited clusters of limitations and challenges were summarised and studies expressing these concerns were identified.

Results

Protocol results

The search protocol yielded a total of 763 studies, of which 403 remained following the removal of duplicates. Screening at title and abstract level resulted in the elimination of 283 studies, leaving 120 studies to assess in full-text level. Among these, three full-texts could not be obtained (from Thai and Polish journals), three studies were considered out of scope because of content, two studies were conference proceedings and one article had been retracted. A further 18 studies that were deemed relevant (identified along the initial review of studies and deemed to be within the protocol scope) were added, resulting in a final sample of 129 studies included in the systematic review. The results from the literature selection process are presented as a PRISMA flowchart in Fig. 1.

Study characteristics

Period of publication: The 129 studies meeting the inclusion criteria were published between 1990 and 2017, with an upward publication trend being observed (Fig. 2a). Only 5% of the studies (seven studies) were published up to 2008, whereas the period between 2015 and 2017 accounted for 56% of the study sample (72). In the interim, 15 and 35 studies were published in the 2009–2011 and 2012–2014 periods, respectively.

Type of publication: The studies were published in 59 different journals that cover a wide range of perspectives.

Fig. 1 PRISMA flowchart describing study selection

Value in Health published the largest number of studies (17), followed by the *International Journal of Technology Assessment in Health Care* (9) and *Pharmacoeconomics* (8). Sixty-eight percent of all studies were published in health (non-clinical), 26% in clinical, 5% in operational research/management science and 1% in interdisciplinary journals.

Study country: First author institutions spanned across 27 countries, with the most frequent first author institutions being located in the UK (30 studies), followed by Netherlands (17), Canada (17), US (16), Germany (8), Italy (7) and Hungary (4). Twenty other countries accounted for three or less studies each.

Health technology focus: Based on Fig. 2b, 44 studies (42%) focused on pharmaceuticals (the majority analysing pharmaceuticals in general, rather than pharmaceuticals for a specific therapeutic indication), with 29 studies investigating general health technologies, 25 studying health interventions, 16 studying medical devices (most of them comparing different devices), 3 researching vaccines (all of them exploring relevant criteria to assess vaccines), with one considering a nanotechnology.

Type of study: According to their main focus, 46 studies (36%) developed models to evaluate health technologies in practice; 33 (26%) analysed MCDA implementation issues; 23 (18%) proposed frameworks to support MCDA in HTA implementation; 7 (5%) explored modelling approaches; and 3 (2%) provided a systematic literature review (Fig. 2c). The content in each of these study groups is discussed below.

(a) Model application studies

The 46 model application studies evaluated pharmaceuticals (24 studies), medical devices (12), health interventions (9) and general health technologies (1). Pharmaceuticals constituted the subject matter of investigations in the following disease areas: rare diseases (none of which contained orphan

cancer indications) [56–60], cancer [61–63], depression [64, 65], cerebrovascular diseases [66, 67], pain-relief [68, 69], age-related macular degeneration [70], overactive bladder [71], idiopathic short stature [72], Turner syndrome [73], psoriasis [74], hypercholesterolemia [75], chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) [76] and relapsing–remitting multiple sclerosis (RRMS) [77]. Two studies developed models to compare pharmaceuticals targeting several diseases [27, 78].

Medical device studies included imaging, surgical and screening approaches, notably, CT, MRI and ultrasound devices [79], MRI equipment [80], imaging techniques, software platforms for cerebrovascular diseases [81], photoacoustic mammoscope technique for breast cancer diagnosis [82], surgical approaches for cam femoroacetabular impingement [83], non-fusion surgery approach for adolescent idiopathic scoliosis [84], surgical robotic innovations [85, 86], reusable pedicle screw instrument kit for lumbar arthrodesis [87], a pulmonary heart sensor [88], drug eluting beads for transcatheter arterial chemoembolization [89] and a screening test for cervical cancer [90].

Evaluated health interventions included public health programmes [91], primary care programmes [92, 93], community care programmes [94], screening strategies [95], mental health services [96], smoking cessation interventions [97] and types of medical care to be covered [98, 99]. One study evaluated both pharmaceuticals and surgical technologies for priority setting purposes [100].

Most applications in this group (34 studies, 74%) aimed to select the most valuable technology, although other purposes have been reported: ranking technologies (6), allocating available resources to technologies (5), and assigning to reimbursement categories (1). With regards to social processes, 39 studies (85%) reported the use of participative methods, 32 (70%) adopted face-to-face approaches for model-building, including decision conferences and workshops, whilst 7 (15%) used web-based formats; 10 (22%) used questionnaires/surveys, 2 (4%) each used interviews and Delphi processes; 7 (15%) studies developed models based upon authors' opinion or did not detail if and how participatory processes took place; 18 (39%) studies dealt with aggregation of individual answers within modelling.

The most frequently used procedures for weighting criteria were the analytical hierarchy process (AHP) (12), quantitative swing weighting (9), point-scaling (8), 100-point allocation (4), and qualitative swing weighting with the measuring attractiveness by a categorical-based evaluation technique (MACBETH) (3); other procedures included the simple multi-attribute rating technique (SMART), SMART/SMARTS (SMART with Swings)/SMARTER (SMART Extended to Ranking), Borda points, equal weighting and weighting calibration according to fatal events. Studies reported building value

Fig. 2 **a** Number of article publications over time; **b** number of publications by type; **c** number of publications according to health technology focus. Source: the authors from the literature

scales with point systems (11 studies), direct rating (7), MACBETH (3), AHP (2), and selecting functions (3), including one selecting linear value functions; 18 studies either did not provide information about value scoring issues or implicitly opted for not modelling value scales. Only one study reported a non-additive model, having

used a multiplicative model [96]. Five studies reported that results from MCDA modelling had practical consequences for decision-making.

(b) Analysis studies

The 33 studies in this category discussed a range of MCDA issues related to HTA adoption, notably (a) raising methodological issues, (b) analysing the relevance of MCDA in HTA, (c) providing a critique on the use of MCDA in HTA and (d) discussing aspects related to its practical use in the HTA context.

With regards to methodological issues on the use of MCDA in HTA, studies addressed a range of issues: first, they provided an overview of MCDA methods and their potential for supporting transparent and consistent health care decision-making [18]; second, they analysed the most common types of MCDA models applied in HTA and identified practical issues in its use [24]; third, they discussed requirements and defined steps for a Universal Methodology for Benefit-Risk Assessment (UMBRA) [101]; fourth, they compared MCDA with other methods for considering equity–efficiency trade-offs in assessing breast cancer control options [102], for evaluating medical devices and imaging technologies [103] and for comparing patient preferences [104]; fifth, they discussed MCDA as a method to integrate economic evidence into clinical practice guidelines [33]; sixth, they described (structured) Evidence to decision frameworks as an alternative or as complementary to MCDA models [105]; and, finally, reported 16 best practice principles for MCDA practice in HTA, with emphasis to facilitated group modelling [44].

Regarding the relevance of using MCDA in HTA, studies, first, discussed the use of MCDA methods to overcome barriers in priority setting, particularly by accounting for the views of healthcare stakeholders [106]; second, they recommended MCDA for dealing with stroke interventions requirements [107]; third, they discussed MCDA usefulness in the context of personalized healthcare by dealing with nuanced and context-specific information that decision-makers would typically require [108]; fourth, they suggested MCDA as a comprehensive tool for dealing with distinct criteria in priority setting or for designing healthcare coverage packages [109]; fifth, they suggested MCDA to value pharmaceuticals [110], arguing for its specific suitability in the rare diseases context [111, 112]; sixth, they discussed the potential role of MCDA to implement a hedonic-pricing approach by bringing together multiple perspectives on the benefits (and potential harms) of medical technologies [113]; seventh, they suggested MCDA to operationalise value-based pricing and aggregate elements of value that are not well represented by weighted quality adjusted life years in a pragmatic way [25]; eighth, they discussed the relevance of including evidence on patient preferences in MCDA [114]; ninth, they suggested MCDA as a tool to include all the relevant criteria that impact on decision-making within transparent processes in Canada [115] and analysed the benefits and

challenges regarding its use in that context [116]; tenth, they suggested MCDA to explicitly model non-economic criteria in pricing and reimbursement decisions in Central and Eastern Europe [117]; and, finally, they suggested MCDA as a methodological approach to increase efficiency, rationality and legitimacy in resource allocation decisions [118].

A sizable group of studies provided a critical appraisal on the use of MCDA in HTA. Studies in this group, first, argued that MCDA can make decision-making too complex or too mechanistic, removing the element of deliberation [119]; second, they showed that MCDA, similarly to other economic evaluation methods, failed to incorporate opportunity costs [120]; third, they alerted for methodological flaws in current applications [121]; fourth, they alerted on the risk of MCDA adding complication since its influence on decision-makers and stakeholders was described as not clear in pharmaceutical pricing and reimbursement contexts [122]; fifth, they suggested the treacle test (can a winning intervention be incompletely ineffective?) and the smallpox test (can a winning intervention be for a disease that no one suffers from?) to raise questions about the adequacy of evaluation model structures reported in the field [32]; and, sixth, they raised issues about the validity and reliability of MCDA for evaluating pharmaceuticals and providing suggestions for improving methodological quality [31].

Finally, with regards to the practical use of MCDA in HTA, studies concluded positively upon first experiences of applying MCDA to prioritize health interventions [123]; discussed the implementation of HTA in Latin American countries, concluding that although MCDA has been applied in few cases, most health stakeholders declared preferring its use [124]; discussed its limited use in Hungary, but the relevance for its development [125]; and discussed that stakeholders in a case study favoured structured approaches to integrate patient views [126].

(c) Framework studies

Twenty-three studies explored the use of MCDA methods and tools for HTA and defined related guidelines or procedures in multiple decision-making and evaluation contexts. A first group of framework studies focused on the use of MCDA in HTA for specific health technologies: to assess new medical technologies [26, 127]; to evaluate pharmaceuticals while focusing on new pharmaceuticals [30, 128], social values [129], (older) well-established pharmaceuticals whose benefit–risk balance may have changed [130] and drug or dose comparisons [131].

A second group of framework studies was developed for specific purposes, exploring one of the following areas: to apply MCDA in clinical decision-making when clinical consensus regarding clinical criteria and weights is required [132]; to inform radiology guideline development [133]

and disease management programs [134]; to select an optimal nanomaterial for a given medical application [135]; to inform drug ranking for formulary listing in low-income countries [136]; to propose MCDA in HTA for middle-income countries [137] and to critically reflect upon that proposal [138]; to inform a wide range of decisions, e.g. approval, guidelines and pricing/reimbursement [43]; to evaluate statins for primary prevention of cardiovascular disease [42]; and to select criteria to be used in HTA [139, 140].

A third group of framework studies focused on principles, methods and processes, aiming to (a) integrate MCDA and accountability for reasonableness principles to support HTA agencies and promote legitimacy in reimbursement recommendations [28]; (b) account for good practice considerations to implement MCDA in healthcare (not specific to HTA) [19]; (c) support deliberative processes behind decision-making by dealing with data analysis, synthesis and validation by experts in general [141], and for rare diseases [142] in particular; and (d) prioritize health technologies based on value for money concepts and under a limited budget [143].

(d) Structuring criteria studies

Studies structuring criteria aimed at informing selection in the following health technology contexts: diagnostic imaging evaluation [144]; vaccines evaluation [145–147]; evaluation of off-patent pharmaceuticals in emerging markets [148]; evaluation of pharmaceuticals in a development stage [149]; pharmaceutical pricing and reimbursement [150]; orphan drug reimbursement [151]; disinvestment and resource allocation processes [152]; hospital investment [153]; hospital decision-making [154]; value definitions [155]; priority setting [156, 157]; criteria beyond cost-effectiveness analysis [158]; defining equity [159]; and physiotherapy implementation [160].

Most structuring criteria studies (12) conducted literature reviews to inform criteria selection, while some of them combined reviews with surveys, interviews or workshops. Six studies used specific tools to structure or rank the criteria, namely direct scoring [148], the AHP [154], a discrete choice experiment [156], a design comparing technologies in clinical scenarios [144], predefined scales [158] and ELECTRE III [with ELECTRE standing for *ELimination Et Choix Traduisant la REalité* (ELimination and Choice Expressing REality)] [150].

Other reviewed studies with a main focus other than structuring criteria also devoted substantial work to structuring criteria in the following contexts: assessment of medical innovation [139], drugs [129] and new medicines [30], for setting up local HTA evaluation processes [140], for

evaluating disease management programs [134], and rare disease interventions across disease areas [142].

(e) Modelling approach studies

Chen [161] developed an approach to deal with imprecise judgments. Broekhuizen and colleagues [162, 163] and Wen et al. [164] researched how to model uncertainty in patient preferences and/or clinical outcomes using MCDA combined with Monte-Carlo simulation. Three studies made use of the stochastic multi-criteria acceptability analysis approach (SMAA) to explore what can be concluded when limited or no preference information exists and a data-driven approach is used: one explored Mixed Treatment Comparison for evidence synthesis within SMAA [165]; a second proposed a stochastic multi-criteria discriminatory method based on SMAA to describe the likelihood of one treatment performing better than alternatives [166]; and, a third, presented the net monetary benefit framework as a special case of SMAA [167].

(f) Literature review studies

There are three studies in this category; the first, reviewed approaches adopted in 40 MCDA studies, analysing the objective of the study and lessons learned [21]. The second assessed 22 MCDA studies to analyse costs and benefits at different stages of medical innovation, reviewing the type of policy applications, methodology, and criteria used and respective definitions [22]. And, the third reviewed ten MCDA studies which involved patients in model building [36].

Methodological quality of model applications

The application of the PROACTIVE-S approach to assess the extent to which the 46 model application studies followed good methodological practice is shown in Table 2, where studies are classified as fully, partially or not complying with the PROACTIVE-S sub-steps (as defined in Table 1); Fig. 3 summarises results from the analyses.

There are three broad areas of interest based on the data reported in Table 2 and the summary data in Fig. 3. First, the lowest levels of adherence to PROACTIVE-S's good methodological practice considerations ($\leq 50\%$ of studies are fully or partly complying with good practice considerations) are found in the value measurement sub-steps and concern behavioural issues, such as: fully using methods for model building comply with multi-attribute decision theory (V3) (26% of studies); defining mechanisms to detect and correct inconsistencies (V4) (25% of studies); using procedures to model value functions (V5) (24% of studies); using weighting procedures that utilize weighting references and explain

their rationale (V6) (35% of studies); and taking into consideration behavioural aspects (S2) (13% of studies).

Second, low levels of adherence (fully compliant at $\leq 50\%$ and fully or partly compliant $> 50\%$) are found in the following sub-steps: (fully) focusing on the objectives to be achieved (O1) (41% of studies); assessing relevant consequences in adequate attributes that comply with required properties and organising consequences of options into a performance matrix (C1) (39% of studies); discussing data sources and issues and consequences uncertainty (C2) (41% of studies); discussing model respect for exhaustiveness, non-redundancy and non-overlap properties in additive models or relevant properties for other models (V1) (28% of studies); discussing preference independence conditions and presenting the underlying model structure (V2) (30% of studies); explicitly modelling assumptions and the relevant uncertainties for the evaluation context (E1) (22% of studies); testing the consequences of model assumptions and uncertainty (E2) (46% of studies); and enabling replicability by making explicit model building participants, participatory scope and format, participatory timeline, and protocols of questioning (S1) (50% of studies).

Third, intermediate levels of adherence—translating into studies fully compliant with good methodological practice at $> 50\%$ but at a large distance from 100%—were found for the following sub-steps: studies fully defining and discussing the relevant health technologies to be evaluated and linked decisions (A1) (57% of studies); discussing model validation and requisiteness and questioning model results (E3) (54% of studies); and promoting participants' reflection and iterativeness in model development while also promoting consensus and/or reflecting on ways to combine participants' assessments (S3) (57% of studies).

Finally, higher but not full levels of adherence to good methodological practice were found in the following areas: studies fully discussing the perspectives of relevant stakeholders and key players, clarifying the perspective of the problem owner and discussing whose views should be considered in model building (R1) (70% of studies); distinguishing between evidence, options' performance and value information (I1) (76% of studies); using computer technology to display results and motivate discussion (E4) (74% of studies).

Reported limitations and challenges

The most common limitations and challenges that have been reported in the 129 reviewed studies are presented on Table 3. These were clustered by relatedness, leading to 12 concerns that were claimed by at least 4 studies each. These concerns relate to: (a) evidence and data processing within model building and use (47 studies, 36%); (b) differences in value systems and the influence of participants'

composition and numbers on evaluation (46 studies, 36%); (c) participants' difficulties in understanding model building tasks and results (33 studies, 26%); (d) model developers having to trade-off methodological complexity with time and cost resources for model development (21 studies, 16%); (e) the selection of criteria and the construction of attributes in model structuring (20 studies, 15.5%); (f) modelling of uncertainty (19 studies, 15%); (g) addressing model additivity issues (17 studies, 13%); (h) the selection of methods (17 studies, 13%); (i) promoting consensus and dealing with the aggregation of participants' answers (12 studies, 9%); (j) attempting to create universal/general evaluation models (9 studies, 7%); (k) fostering MCDA training and expertise (7 studies, 5%); and (l) generating model scores which have a meaningful interpretation (4 studies, 3%).

Discussion

The objective of this paper was to review existing literature of MCDA applications in HTA using aggregation approaches, to identify the scope of research published to date, to develop an understanding of the challenges and limitations reported in published research and to assess the methodological quality of studies whose main focus was to develop multidimensional models to evaluate health technologies. Several messages can be taken from this review, including an understanding of how the application of MCDA in HTA literature needs to evolve to address the limitations and challenges identified in the 129 studies.

Key messages

The systematic analysis of MCDA studies in the context of HTA has yielded seven key messages related to trends, the direction of published research to date and a range of methodological issues that need to be addressed in future research. These messages are discussed below.

Regarding trends in the application of MCDA in HTA studies, one observes a high growth in published research, with most studies developed in a small number of countries (UK, Netherlands, Canada, US, Germany and Italy) and disseminated through health (mainly non-clinical) journals. Model application studies are far from being able to cover all types of health technologies, decisions and decision contexts: evaluation models have been built mostly for pharmaceuticals and for general health technologies and interventions (although general technologies or interventions are restricted to one area, notably public health); most studies aimed to inform the selection of the best technology (with some looking into priority setting and resource allocation).

The majority of studies have developed experimental models in applied settings; the focus has been to discuss

Table 3 Identification of challenges and limitations in published MCDA studies (aggregated into clusters; the descending order reflects the number of studies raising a particular challenge or limitation). Source: The authors from the literature

Cluster #	Summary (number of studies)	Clustered reported limitations and challenges	Articles expressing limitations and challenges
#1	Evidence and Data related Difficulties (TECHNICAL) (47 studies)	Multiple difficulties exist regarding the use of evidence and data in evaluation processes: information from multiple studies may be complex, not fully comparable (e.g. data often derived from separate trials differing in populations, treatment durations and calculated in different units), hard to capture by checklists or scales, have questionable quality, and participants may be overwhelmed by data (for instance numerous aggregations of data from non-standardised and often non-computerized databases). There may be lack of evidence and lack of good quality data for criteria deemed as relevant by evaluators, and there are challenges to synthesize relevant information. Participants may have a sense of information loss along evaluation processes. There is a lack of consensus about quantities such as 'quality of life' or 'economic value' of a healthy individual, which translate into evaluation difficulties. It is difficult to acquire and interpret data across heterogeneous health technologies	[18, 19, 21, 24–28, 31, 42, 60, 63, 69, 74, 80, 82–84, 87–89, 91, 94, 97, 98, 102, 103, 112, 113, 126, 130–132, 135, 137, 140, 142, 143, 151–153, 155, 158–160, 164, 165]
#2	Value System Differences and Participant Selection issues (SOCIAL) (46 studies)	There are variations in experts and stakeholders' views and in the value systems of countries/regions/health systems. Value systems can vary over time and in response to new evidence. In multiple contexts evaluations rely on the views of members of a small panel/committee, with resulting evaluations being influenced possibly by participants' characteristics and not being representative. In contexts where representativeness is important, it is not clear whose views should be considered. There are limits to involve a large number of participants in a face-to-face setting. MCDA studies have been involving much smaller numbers of participants than large patient preference studies	[19, 21, 24, 26, 27, 31, 33, 36, 57, 59, 60, 62, 63, 65, 66, 72, 73, 75, 78, 80, 82, 84, 97–99, 101–103, 106, 109, 111, 113, 116, 121, 123, 126, 129, 131, 132, 139, 142, 144, 147, 148, 153, 162]

Table 3 (continued)

Cluster #	Summary (number of studies)	Clustered reported limitations and challenges	Articles expressing limitations and challenges
#3	Participant Difficulties in Evaluation Processes (SOCIAL) (33 studies)	Participants face difficulties in interpreting data or in understanding evaluation processes; they also face cognitive difficulties in providing judgments (for instance using swing weighting, comparing mild and serious events, understanding orders of magnitude, interpreting weighting coefficients). Evaluation judgments may be frame-dependent (e.g. being influenced by the method in use), with multiple heuristics and biases. Applying, for instance, judgments may be prone to strategic behaviour, to vested interests and may be critically influenced by some participants; languages and translations may influence evaluations; participants typically have distinct levels of understanding; and weighting is influenced by ranges, with participants shying away from extremes	[18, 19, 21, 24, 26, 28, 30, 31, 33, 36, 43, 57–60, 68, 72, 73, 75–78, 96, 98, 99, 104, 106, 116, 144, 149–151, 155]
#4	Balancing Methodological Complexity and Resources (TECHNICAL) (21 studies)	There is methodological complexity in using MCDA in HTA and a trade-off between methodological complexity and MCDA resources (including costs and time for model development). Standards and requirements for MCDA modelling may limit flexibility, adaptability, and timeliness. Many MCDA models are simplistic, with the choice of simple, intuitive, easy to use techniques, even if there is a compromise on rigor; often only partial information is requested from experts because of cost and time. Analysts are faced with the trade-off between ensuring an exhaustive set of criteria and the time and cognitive effort associated with using more criteria. Time is needed for evaluators to get acquainted with MCDA processes, and there may be participant fatigue. A significant amount of work is involved in reporting a MCDA model to evaluate health technologies	[19, 24, 27, 28, 30, 33, 57, 59, 60, 69, 74, 97, 99, 116, 119, 127, 129, 140, 149, 151, 162]
#5	Criteria Selection and Attribute building Difficulties (TECHNICAL) (20 studies)	The definition of evaluation criteria and attributes is a long, difficult and subjective process, further complicated because of variability of HTA terminology adopted in the hospital context. Some criteria, such as equity, are difficult to operationalize and the use of attributes is open to subjective interpretations. There is a lack of guidelines on the number of criteria and the structure of the evaluation model can become too extensive if all criteria need to be taken into account, as well as it can lead to cognitive burden and time-consuming procedures. Several attributes can be chosen for a criterion and there are difficulties in defining references for those attributes. Work is needed to advise how to estimate baseline effects. Not all aspects to be accounted for are quantifiable and it may not be possible to incorporate them into an MCDA model (e.g. context issues related to system capacity and appropriate use of an intervention)	[21, 26, 30, 59, 61, 63, 73, 78, 82, 89, 123, 129, 130, 132, 134, 140, 149, 151, 157, 165]

Table 3 (continued)

Cluster #	Summary (number of studies)	Clustered reported limitations and challenges	Articles expressing limitations and challenges
#6	Uncertainty Modelling Needs (TECHNICAL) (19 studies)	Health technology assessment entails uncertainty from multiple sources, related to scoring and weighting methods, criteria choice and with attributes in use (such as some based on point systems), as well as with evaluation judgments. Evaluators may not be able to give exact preference information on weights. Several modelling options, such as the choice of time horizon for costs and benefits, can influence evaluation	[18, 19, 21, 24, 25, 33, 68, 75, 80, 93, 98, 113, 121, 122, 126, 143, 163, 164, 166]
#7	Model Additivity Issues (TECHNICAL) (17 studies)	There are multiple issues related to the use of an additive model—for instance, it cannot be used to deal with thresholds (e.g. a threshold of incidence of adverse events above which the drug is considered unacceptable), as one cannot use trade-offs with it. There is potential for criteria to be neither exhaustive nor mutually exclusive, there may be overlaps and double counting (e.g. some degree of overlap is inherent in many of the endpoints), and one needs to deal with interdependencies. More complex methods are known, but their adoption may imply that the elicitation questions become too hard for evaluators	[19, 21, 30, 32, 43, 61, 64, 77, 82, 93, 116, 121, 123, 133, 145, 151, 162]
#8	Methods' Selection Issues (TECHNICAL) (17 studies)	There is no consensus about the best framework and about the best weighting method, and methods are not standardised which raises validity issues. The selection of method may introduce bias, and inadequate weighting practices are recognised in the literature. There is generally no gold standard against which to compare results and results have not been replicated by independent third parties. There is a sense of arbitrariness in the implementation of an MCDA approach. Acknowledging the existence of different schools of thought, the appropriate weighting technique is essential, as are the circumstances under which a specific technique should be used	[18, 26, 33, 43, 58, 68, 69, 98, 121, 122, 126, 128, 134, 146, 148]
#9	Consensus Promotion and Aggregation of Participant Answers (SOCIAL) (12 studies)	Despite the importance of promoting consensus, consensus agreement varies across studies and needs to be both accommodated and reported. There are also issues on how to properly combine individual judgments and to assess consensus	[18, 24, 26, 30, 99, 113, 116, 121, 131, 132, 142, 153]
#10	Introduce Flexibility Features for Universal/General Evaluation Models (TECHNICAL) (9 studies)	Despite the ambition of building universal (or general) models to compare distinct technologies across diseases and therapeutic areas, there are conceptual and methodological difficulties in developing such models. Different models tend to be built for different contexts	[24, 36, 59, 101, 103, 106, 121, 144, 155]

Table 3 (continued)

Cluster #	Summary (number of studies)	Clustered reported limitations and challenges	Articles expressing limitations and challenges
#11	MCDA Training and Expertise Needs (TECHNICAL) (7 studies)	There is a lack of familiarity with MCDA techniques and, consequently, there is a need for training staff for MCDA implementation, as well as a need for participant training (e.g. patient training). Training requires time and resources	[36, 43, 56, 84, 97, 101, 111, 116, 123, 136, 137]
#12	Model Scores Meaningfulness Issues (TECHNICAL) (4 studies)	There are difficulties in interpreting model outputs and in understanding the meaning of these outputs, which need to be tested and validated. Scores are relative and produced in an interval scale, and thus limit the usefulness of a cost-value ratio; they also do not provide information about the absolute effectiveness, utilities, or absolute costs in monetary units	[21, 36, 75, 93]

adoption, development and implementation issues and to develop frameworks for a wide range of contexts, thus showing the emerging and exploratory nature of research in the area. Studies discussing MCDA aspects have raised methodological issues and alerts for the methodological robustness of MCDA in the context of HTA, but also underlined the high potential and positive experience regarding MCDA exploration and adoption. Framework studies outlined MCDA processes for multiple technologies and evaluation purposes, and set principles, methods and processes for MCDA that address specific aspects and contexts.

The majority of studies made use of participatory approaches that relied on workshop sessions but other non-face-to-face and web-based processes have been explored, demonstrating the interest in overcoming the limitations of making decisions relying on a small number of individuals that meet face-to-face and the cost and time constraints.

Concerning methods in use, in light of the multicriteria value measurement literature, the fact that most studies did not model value functions and that AHP and point scaling were the two most commonly selected weighting procedures raises methodological issues (discussed below in the relevant section). Although issues concerning methodological quality have been raised in other HTA areas [168], our study findings provide evidence that more research, methodological quality improvements and more models developed in realistic settings are required. This is compatible with what others have argued in the literature [19, 32, 43, 121].

Regarding the analysis of the modelling application studies' methodological quality in light of the PROACTIVE-S approach, results suggest action is needed to improve the methodological quality of MCDA in HTA studies. More than 50% of the studies had a number of shortcomings: they did not follow good practice regarding value measurement sub-steps, did not focus on objectives (not adopting a value-focused thinking perspective [34]), did not adopt best practice tools in building attributes to analyse health technology impact, did not address uncertainty in technology impact, did not model assumptions explicitly, did not detail social processes, and did not reflect upon behavioural issues. In general, the lowest methodological quality was found in value measurement sub-steps, as most studies expressed few concerns with model properties, dealt with preference independence and the underlying evaluation model structure, used methods that do not respect the theoretical foundations of multi-attribute value theory (mostly due to the use of the AHP technique that is prone to rank reversal [169, 170] and can violate a condition of order preservation [171] and due to the use of point systems that do not consider weighting references across criteria), did not address judgmental inconsistencies in model building, did not use proper procedures to measure partial value, and did not use adequate weighting procedures.

While authors may have conducted some methodological analyses but not expressed them in writing, overall results suggest that many model applications may not have been properly built and validated and, as a result, models may not have led to appropriate recommendations for decision-making. Detailed guidelines should be developed so that sound procedures and tools are adopted in model building. To ensure adequate methodological quality, published studies should include detailed methodological information so that they can be thoroughly analysed—for instance, studies should detail social processes in use for accuracy and for replicability, which may not be compatible with article size limitations defined in health journals. Some evidence points towards methodological issues not being identified during the article reviewing process: for instance, all studies presenting the formulation of an additive model should have made explicit the weighting references in use. These references are relevant to understand model results in light of the use of interval scales, and weighting coefficients can only be interpreted together with the references in use, as changes in references require weights to be recalculated. One study has described repeatedly the use of a ‘linear additive equation’ [127]. Several studies have made use of similar modelling approaches, advocating the use of methods that do not necessarily follow good practice guidance.

Taking stock of the challenges and limitations identified in the reviewed studies, several challenges are identified by a very large number of studies. More than a quarter of the studies (a) raised questions regarding the use of health technology evidence and data in the evaluation process, (b) made explicit concerns regarding differences and variations in value systems across health stakeholders and contexts (expressing concerns about models reflecting the views of a small number of individuals and being influenced by the choice of individuals, such as committee members), and (c) discussed participants’ difficulties in model development and/or use. Given the scale of such concerns, it is imperative these aspects are addressed in future research. A discussion of how the “MCDA for HTA” literature can be developed to address each cluster of challenges and limitations follows, while the key issues are reported in Table 3.

Addressing the challenges in and advancing the “MCDA for HTA” debate

Challenge 1: evidence and data-related difficulties

Forty-seven studies reported difficulties regarding the use of evidence and data in evaluation processes, particularly in synthesising information, in dealing with data non-comparability issues and with large volumes of data (complete description of cluster 1 in Table 3). While these issues also apply to HTA in general, for the “MCDA in HTA” context

research can help to provide guidelines to address these issues; synthesis formats can be developed to capture what is regarded as key data (in line with evaluation objectives to be achieved with health technologies), by explaining how to address variability in technology impact assessment (e.g. through considering impact intervals and performing sensitivity analysis), and by designing model features that consider cases of data incomparability and lack of data among others. Regarding this last point, flexible and non-closed models can be explored in which attributes consider not only quantitative aspects but also qualitative assessments from evaluators (for instance, committee members). Such models have been explored in other contexts, e.g. in the case of faculty evaluation [172]: in this context it was deemed a critical feature for model adoption that evaluators should not only consider quantitative metrics but also other complementary aspects within a qualitative and non-closed but formal assessment (e.g. to consider the number of high quality publications and the number of citations from faculty members, evaluators could consider qualitative aspects such as prizes and adjust evaluation scores). This study context led to the combination of quantitative with qualitative assessments in a multiplicative model structure. Furthermore, there is scope for developing guidelines that clarify and characterise different types of uncertainties in data, and that explain clearly which procedures to undertake for each type of uncertainty, for instance departing from the work by Stewart and Durbach [173].

Challenge 2: value systems’ differences and participants’ selection issues

Forty-six studies were concerned with the variation of value systems across experts, stakeholders and health systems and over time, as well as with MCDA models in HTA relying on the views of a small number of participants that may not represent all relevant views. While it needs to be acknowledged that value systems change over time (being also influenced by new evidence), which implies that evaluation models need to be reassessed and updated occasionally, a wide range of concepts and tools can be developed to ensure that models have the potential to reflect the perspectives of a diverse and larger number of health stakeholders. To address this challenge, “socio-technical processes” can be effectively designed and tested to involve a larger and more representative number of HTA stakeholders in the evaluation of health technologies; this, for instance, would avoid having to rely solely on the perspectives of a small number of evaluation committee members. Such a path has already started to be explored in other health contexts. For example, within the scope of building a population health index (based on a multi-criteria model structure) to evaluate population health across European regions, a socio-technical

approach was adopted combining non-face-to-face web-Delphi processes to collect the views of a large number of European experts and stakeholders with face-to-face decision conferencing processes with a strategic group for building the multi-criteria model (as informed by evidence and by the views collected in the web-Delphis) [174, 175]. These processes can be developed and adapted further to collect health stakeholder views to inform the building of MCDA in HTA models, having to consider consensus and other issues (explored further under challenge 9). Stakeholder theory and engagement literature (discussed in [176]) can help to clarify which stakeholders to involve, under which type of involvement (which may include informing, consulting and co-deciding involvements) and with which format. Additionally, social research studies have explored statistical concepts to inform which participant numbers by stakeholder group are required for representativeness [177].

If properly designed, developed and enhanced by technology, web-based processes can facilitate the collection of information from a larger number of participants at relatively low cost [178]; there may also be space to develop structured techniques to involve larger groups of people in face-to-face settings [178]. Approaches can be further developed so as to test whether value systems tend to change over time, following the research idea explored by Lienert et al. [179] through the study on the stability of preferences over time in the context of wastewater infrastructure decision-making. A few studies in the review have re-tested the preferences of those participating in MCDA modelling with such aim (e.g. [56]).

Challenge 3: participant difficulties in evaluation processes

Thirty-three studies have mentioned several types of participant difficulties in interpreting data, understanding evaluation processes, and providing judgments; additionally, they raised related behavioural issues and biases affecting the development of MCDA models in the context of HTA. MCDA can assist in providing friendly protocols to be tested in empirical applications. Studies can incorporate behavioural research features so as to test preferred modes of questioning (taking into account behavioural issues reported in MCDA development). Some methods have shown to be cognitively friendly in empirical settings [39]. For instance, several studies in health have been using the MACBETH approach [180–182] that provides an interactive questioning procedure based on qualitative judgements that only asks a decision-maker or a group for qualitative preference judgements between two elements at a time; this addresses cognitive uneasiness experienced by evaluators when trying to express their preference judgements numerically [54]; AHP also asked for qualitative judgments (on a ratio scale) in a large number of reviewed model applications, with studies providing positive feedback regarding its friendliness for

participants. While several articles have reported participant difficulties in providing (quantitative) swing weighting judgments, MACBETH enables the use of qualitative swing weighting and has been used with a positive feedback in several of the reviewed model applications [61, 85, 94]. Other user-friendly and methodologically sound protocols may also be explored.

Behavioural research, informed by behavioural literature in general [53] and, specifically, by behavioural literature for MCDA contexts [55, 183], can be developed in MCDA for HTA, for example to compare participant preferences for modes of questioning, visual displays and methods. Eliminating bias from procedures that have been used in other contexts [184] can be adapted, as it is important for those facilitating the use of several protocols of questioning in the phase of model testing and validation: to illustrate, MACBETH qualitative swing weighting and quantitative swing weighting can be used interchangeably to explain and discuss the meaning of weighting coefficients to participants.

Training and guidelines for facilitation and making use of a wide range of existing resources [185–187] can be developed to assist those developing MCDA for HTA applications—facilitation skills can help managing participants and better communication in workshop settings. Other training issues are discussed in challenge 11, below.

Challenge 4: balancing methodological complexity and resources

Twenty-one studies reported concerns related to the methodological complexity of using MCDA in HTA and the need to balance methodological complexity with cost, time and cognition in model development. A first issue is that the HTA community is not fully acquainted with MCDA concepts, methods and tools, as in most cases HTA education and training programmes do not cover MCDA or cover it superficially. If MCDA is to progress convincingly in HTA, it is expected that these programmes will need to enhance their curricula by including MCDA topics, that more MCDA courses are offered, and that HTA experts wishing to apply MCDA collaborate closely with MCDA experts.

A second issue concerns the extent to which pragmatism is acceptable in model development, as simplification can lead to models that do not respect basic MCDA properties. Some of the reviewed studies accept model simplifications [19, 63, 74], explicitly opting to build simple attributes and use weighting protocols that do not comply with multi-attribute decision theory. Many model simplifications may be inappropriate and are invalid (this has been shown for instance in the case of for river rehabilitation [188]); to that end literature and guidelines should provide guidance on which simplifications are acceptable.

A third issue is that methodological complexity can be addressed with a higher focus on the design of the socio-technical process [45, 46] in line with: balancing evidence and participatory processes; balancing larger non-face-to-face interaction to collect the views of a larger number of individuals with smaller face-to-face participatory processes; and with preparing a wide range of materials to assist participants in helping to build technology evaluation models [189].

Finally, concerning the cost and time costs for model development, there is scope for developing frameworks to produce reusable or easily adaptable models for several decision *problematiques* [40] and generating templates, so that evaluators can follow good practice and balance time and effort. Different HTA *problematiques* require distinct types of modelling approaches to be made available to model developers, e.g. modelling for choosing the best health technology (such as the choice of best pharmaceutical [61]), modelling for ranking health technologies (such as the ambition to ordering intervention strategies [95]), modelling for classifying technologies (as in the case of deciding which pharmaceutical falls within a reimbursement category [57]), modelling for allocating resources (such as the need to allocate a commissioning budget or nursing time to health programmes [92, 190]), and modelling for optimizing health care processes, which are also classified as health technologies [5] (as in the case of simultaneously defining hospital and long-term service locations, size of facilities and referral networks [191–193] in line with the health system objectives).

Challenge 5: criteria selection and attribute construction difficulties

Twenty studies mentioned multiple issues and lack of guidance and support to the definition of evaluation criteria and to the construction of attributes. Guidelines to specifically assist in model structuring need to be developed, so as to avoid issues that should not arise if MCDA is properly used. Indeed, structuring is a key step in MCDA model development and results from applying the PROACTIVE-S approach suggest that researchers have not always adopted best practices or dedicated full attention to model structuring when developing model applications. If all relevant criteria are not considered and if attributes are inadequately designed, the succeeding steps in model development may not be successful [34] and claims of subjective interpretations of attributes may appear. A wide range of tools from the problem structuring methods literature can assist problem structuring for MCDA and generally have been unexplored in “MCDA for HTA” [194]. Clear examples on how to build and/or to model attributes may be developed, following [47, 195], with special attention to qualitative and

multi-dimensional attributes that may be critical for cases with lack of data, of data incomparability and of preference dependence between criteria. New model structures should be researched so as to incorporate qualitative aspects within evaluations, and to explicitly deal with a lack or bad quality data (discussed in challenge 1). Existing literature explaining the pros and cons of choosing distinct reference levels within attributes—either local or global, absolute or relative levels [40, 48]—should be clearly made available to the “MCDA in HTA” research community. If a model becomes too large, hierarchical modelling techniques are also advised [196].

Challenge 6: uncertainty modelling needs

Nineteen studies raised issues related to model choice, methods in use, technology impact imprecision or variability, and participant judgments, which translate into different types of uncertainty. Although multiple studies have developed methods to deal with uncertainty and have clearly described different types of uncertainty [19], within the decision analysis spirit of ‘divide and conquer’ [197], there is scope for developing clear procedures on how to deal with each type of uncertainty so that participants and evaluators are better equipped with what modelling pathways to follow under the presence of each uncertainty source.

Challenge 7: model additivity issues

Seventeen studies raised issues related to the appropriateness of using an additive model, namely the way of dealing with thresholds (related to compensation of performance in the evaluation criteria), exhaustiveness of evaluation criteria, double counting (for instance related to the use of several endpoints), preference independence, and the potential cognitive burden related to the use of more complex methods. Clearer guidelines suggesting tests, protocols and tools may need to be developed in this area. Several modelling options may be explored to deal with non-compensability in the performance of technologies in distinct evaluation criteria, for instance, additive evaluation models can be combined with system rules in which minimal thresholds need to be attained so that the technology is considered for evaluation (use of thresholds such as in Bana e Costa et al. [196]). Concerning preference dependence, there is a need to develop tests with friendly protocols of questioning not only for identifying such issues (as in Oliveira et al.), but also to suggest how to make use of distinct model structures in a user-friendly way. Literature already advises on how to restructure models so as to respect additivity, for instance building constructed attributes that integrate preference dependent dimensions [48]; and some studies in health settings have already developed (and applied) user-friendly protocols of questioning to identify preference dependence cases and show how multilinear

[195] and Choquet Integral-based models [198] can be built. Some studies in real settings have also explained the rationale for using multiplicative models [172]. Several of these studies have used the qualitative MACBETH protocol of questioning that has been shown to provide a user-friendly protocol of questioning [54, 181]. The structuring methods recalled in challenge 5 provide tools to avoid double counting and ensure exhaustiveness.

Challenge 8: method selection issues

Seventeen studies made explicit the desire to have a ‘best method and a best framework’ and raised validity and replicability issues. While it is not expected that there will be a single prevailing weighting method or approach in MCDA, there should be clarity about methods that have sound theoretical foundations and the limits of a pragmatic MCDA (discussed in challenge 4). Those developing MCDA for HTA should consider using several protocols during model development and validation (discussed in challenge 3), so as to ensure that evaluations do not rely on methods and that participants develop a better understanding about the evaluation model and results. Behavioural research (discussed in challenge 2), may be carried out to test whether participants prefer to express judgments in specific formats and under distinct methods, and to gauge the best forms to communicate model outputs. Further procedures for model testing and validation can be developed, for example involving experimental design in comparing model evaluations with real decisions within an ex-post evaluation frame. Replication of studies, analysis of preference stability and model retests (addressed in challenge 2) can also be used.

Challenge 9: consensus promotion and aggregation of participants’ answers issues

Twelve studies have explicitly recognised the importance of promoting consensus. It has been observed that consensus levels vary across studies and that clarity is needed about how to combine individual judgments. Following the view that a health technology evaluation model should be requisite (based on Phillips [49], it should be ‘sufficient in form and content to resolve the issues at hand’), the socio-technical design of the model building process needs to incorporate concepts and tools from group decision-making—for instance on voting systems, group decision support systems, group facilitation, and group thinking modelling (multiple issues covered in Kilgour and Eden [199])—to promote collaboration, convergence and alignment in model building [45]. The combination of individual judgments is relevant either in face-to-face contexts in which participants express their preferences that need to be combined and visualised by the group, and in non-face-to-face contexts, which

require aggregation of individual answers. The choice of either format or their combination within a collaborative value modelling framework (such as proposed in [200]) may depend on time, cost and participant availability. To that end, there is a need for tools and guidance on how to proceed in such contexts and how to summarise and aggregate individual judgments or scores. Again, behavioural research can help answer which settings are more effective to promote consensus.

Challenge 10: introduce flexibility features for universal/general evaluation models

Nine studies have raised questions about whether it is possible to build general models that can be used to compare distinct health technologies across diseases or therapeutic areas. Despite the multitude of issues related to the evaluation of distinct technologies—for instance in comparing endpoints across diseases—it is open to “MCDA in HTA” research to introduce flexibility features in evaluation models and, thereby, promote their use across contexts. Such features include exploring: (a) the use of equivalence attributes (following the concept of strategic equivalence as defined in Keeney and Raiffa [16]), so that an attribute can be defined differently for different diseases but that it can be simultaneously compared across diseases; (b) the use of absolute references within each attribute that can be translated for distinct contexts (as discussed in challenge 5); (c) the use of qualitative assessments to complement quantitative assessments (as discussed in challenges 1 and 5); and (d) the use of weighting intervals that enable adjustment of weights for the context. The studies analysed within the review have most commonly used simple additive models, but some of these suggestions have been explored in other contexts, such as in Bana e Costa and Oliveira [172] in the context of faculty evaluation (notably the following figures were explored: qualitative assessments by evaluators; and interval weighting combined with optimization so that each faculty member has the combination of weighting coefficients that maximizes their value score).

Challenge 11: MCDA training and expertise needs

Seven studies have raised explicit concerns regarding the familiarity with MCDA techniques and the need for training researchers and participants. As discussed above, training and education in HTA rarely considers MCDA topics and user-friendly materials—such as videos—explaining the scope, features and applicability of MCDA in HTA are scarce. Successful and unsuccessful cases of application and of real implementation should be communicated clearly. Additionally, MCDA in the context of HTA should develop specifically designed decision support tools [201] to enable

proper development of health technology evaluation models. Research can also explore the connection between MCDA and other evaluation techniques (for instance, Postmus et al. [202] have explored the extent to which net monetary benefit is a special case of SMAA).

Challenge 12: model scores and meaningfulness issues

Four studies have discussed issues related to the interpretation of model outputs and the meaning of model scores. These aspects relate to the use of interval scales, as multicriteria models based upon simple additive models produce value scores for health technologies that need to be anchored in two reference levels—for instance 100 and 0 corresponding to the best or worst plausible performances, respectively. These references are critical not only for weighting but also for the interpretation of value scores (for instance, what does a zero value mean?). This choice of reference levels relates also to issues discussed in challenge 5 (e.g. use of global or local attribute scales), and several paths may be explored to enable a meaningful interpretation of value scores. First, there are modelling features that can be used in some contexts—such as the use of absolute, intrinsic and meaningful references within attributes—that promote an understanding and interpretation of model scores. Second, when two technologies are compared, following the logic of the incremental cost effectiveness ratio (ICER), it is always possible to take zero (or placebo in economic evaluation) as the comparator. Based on this, analyses can be performed regarding the added cost and the added value on a common scale.

Figure 4 displays a visual representation linking the areas in which model application studies most highly deviating from methodological good practice with the 8 most important methodological challenges expressed in studies; it also displays suggested topics for research, which may address improvements in methodological practice or in reported limitations and challenges more explicitly and directly. There can be a connection between methodological challenges and deviations from methodological quality perspective and that suggested research topics have the potential to simultaneously contribute to good methodological robustness and to help researchers working in the area.

Study limitations

The study is not without limitations and challenges. First, given the multiple designations and the variety of nomenclature adopted in MCDA studies relevant to HTA, the choice of terms may have affected some of the results and potentially relevant studies may not have been included; additionally, restricting analysis to journal articles and book chapters published in English may also have had some impact on results. However, our search strategy has been comprehensive enough

to ensure that the likelihood of omitting an eligible study was small. Despite that, and considering the recent upward trend in the publication of relevant studies over the past 5 years, it is likely that in the very near future an increasing number of new studies will be published, but we cannot control for this.

Second, there seems to be a different understanding on what MCDA actually is among scientists developing studies in this particular field. For instance, there are studies included in the sample collecting information from participants through surveys—without further interacting with participants or testing and validating models—and describing that they have been developing MCDA evaluation models. A strict view on what is MCDA could mean that these studies should be excluded. However, as these studies are insightful in many other respects, such as on how to involve participants in the evaluation of health technologies and on which areas it is relevant to explore MCDA in HTA, we decided to include them. Furthermore, this decision is also coherent with the objective of analysing the methodological quality of studies in the area.

Conclusion

This study shows that the application of MCDA in HTA is a growing field with increasing numbers of studies exploring its use in multiple contexts and under distinct perspectives, embedding its concepts and methods within technology policy- and decision-making processes, and showcasing its usefulness. Results show a number of limitations and challenges to address, a need to develop research and guidelines to promote quality and scientific rigor in the use of MCDA in HTA, as well as scope for advancing robust methodologies, processes and tools to assist modellers in the use of methods.

Several research paths have been identified within the scope of this study as potentially addressing the identified methodological challenges. Such paths include developing specific modelling approaches to account for distinct decision HTA contexts, such as to inform adoption, reimbursement and pricing decisions. In a way similar to HTA, training and education tools need to be developed and made available. To address concerns made explicit by researchers regarding the use of evidence and data within multicriteria modelling, new studies need to explore standardised ways of synthesising quantitative evidence and data as well as capture the quality of evidence in a structured format. Such synthesis formats should also be aligned with the objectives to be attained in the evaluation context. Additionally, studies in the area need to balance social with technical aspects in model development, and those interested in applying MCDA in the HTA context should learn from best practice and the experience from those developing models in practical settings. Collaborative research involving multiple health

Fig. 4 Interconnectedness between the MCDA modelling steps with higher deviations from good methodological practice (on top), and the eight most reported limitations and challenges reported in MCDA in HTA studies (on bottom). Lines in the middle depict interrelations

between those deviations and limitations/challenges, with topics near the lines (in capital letters) synthesising areas relevant for developing the state of the art within MCDA for HTA (topics discussed along the “Discussion” section). Source: the authors from the literature

stakeholders is needed, and new technologies with a potential to involve and collect the views from a larger number of perspectives at a lower cost may be carefully designed and tested.

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Appendix A

Adopted search protocol for the systematic review of MCDA studies in HTA, with the following rules being adopted: [(“A” or “B” or “C” or “D”) and (“E” or “F” or “G” or “H”)]

A: "MCDA" OR "Multicriteria Decision Analysis" OR "Multi-criteria Decision Analysis" OR "Multi Criteria Decision Analysis" OR "Multiple Criteria Decision Analysis" OR "Multiple-Criteria Decision Analysis"

B: "Multicriteria Analysis" OR "Multi-criteria Analysis" OR "Multiple-criteria"

C: "MAVT" OR "MAUT" OR "Multiattribute Decision Theory" OR "Multi-attribute Decision Theory" OR "Multi-attribute Utility Theory" OR "Multi-attribute Utility Theory" OR "Multiattribute Utility" OR "Multi-attribute Utility"

D: "Multicriteria Decision Aiding" OR "Multiple-criteria Decision-Making" OR "Multiple criteria Decision-Making" OR "Multicriteria Decision-making" OR "Multiple-characteristics decision-making" OR "MCDM"

E: "Multicriteria Resource Allocation" OR "Multiple Criteria Resource Allocation" OR "Portfolio Decision Analysis" OR ("Multicriteria Optimization" OR "Multiple Criteria Optimization") AND "Resource Allocation"

F: "HTA" OR "Health Technology Assessment" OR "Health Technology Appraisal" OR ("Health" AND "Technology" AND "Evaluation") OR ("Health" AND "Technologies" AND "Evaluation") OR ("Benefit-risk Assessment" AND "Health") OR ("Value-based Assessment" AND "Health") OR ("Economic evaluation" AND "Health")

G: (("Medical" OR "Clinical" OR "Hospital" OR "Health") AND ("Devices" OR "Equipment" OR "Technology")) OR "Drugs" OR "Pharmaceutical" OR "Medicine" OR "Screening" OR "Surgical" AND ("Benefit-risk" OR "Appraisal" OR "Valuation" OR "Assessment" OR "Value Measurement" OR "Value-based Assessment")

H: ("Treatment" OR "Therapy" OR Interventions" OR "Intervention") AND ("Health" OR "Clinical" OR "Medical") AND ("Benefit-risk" OR "Appraisal" OR "Valuation" OR "Assessment" OR "Value Measurement" OR "Value-based Assessment")

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IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

Task 2, Part II: Understanding stakeholders' roles and involvement in national Health Technology Assessment agency evaluation processes: a new framework based on Critical Systems Heuristics

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Abstract

Objectives: To understand stakeholders' roles and involvement in national Health Technology Assessment (HTA) agency evaluation processes. Emphasis is placed on stakeholders' interests, concerns and values in the assessment of new medicines.

Methods: The original Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) 12 questions were adapted for the HTA context to understand medicines evaluation processes by focusing on four basic aspects, i.e. 'boundary issues' (motivation, control, knowledge and legitimacy), each divided into three categories (social roles, specific concerns and key problems). The adapted CSH framework was then applied through an expert consultation with HTA agencies, using a questionnaire. Primary data were collected from eleven study participants having a current or previous affiliation with six HTA agencies (NICE, SMC, HAS, TLV, IQWiG, AOTMiT).

Results: The application of the adapted CSH framework revealed two main types of findings. First, the identification of seven stakeholder groups were found to be relevant in HTA evaluation processes of new medicines: patients and carers, general population, industry, payers and policymakers, HTA agencies, healthcare professionals, scientific experts and methodologists. Second, a conceptual model helped to understand the rationale for involving different stakeholder groups in such processes by analysing the motivation, power, knowledge and legitimacy aspects driving evaluation processes in HTA agencies.

Conclusions: The adapted CSH framework can be used for analysing the rationale of HTA organisations in terms of stakeholder engagement. It enables a reflection about current

stakeholder roles within HTA evaluation processes while being aligned with the promotion of legitimacy, representativeness and accountability in medicines evaluation.

Highlights

i. What is already known about the topic?

Stakeholder involvement is considered to be vital for increasing the credibility and acceptance of Health Technology Assessment decisions.

ii. What does the paper add to existing knowledge?

The work reported helps reflecting about and guiding the consideration of stakeholders' interests, concerns and values in the evaluation processes of new medicines at HTA agencies.

iii. What insights does the paper provide for informing healthcare-related decision making?

The adapted CSH framework enables a reflection about current stakeholder roles within HTA evaluation processes while being aligned with the promotion of legitimacy, representativeness and accountability in medicines evaluation.

Key-words

Health Technology Assessment (HTA); stakeholder identification; stakeholder consultation; Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH); boundary critique; HTA agencies; new medicines

Introduction

Recently, Health Technology Assessment (HTA) was defined as "a multidisciplinary process that uses explicit methods to determine the value of a health technology at different points in its lifecycle; the purpose is to inform decision-making in order to promote an equitable, efficient, and high-quality health system" ((O'Rourke, Oortwijn et al. 2020), p. 2). This definition is accompanied by four important notes, one of them devoted to the specification of 'what is value' for a health technology. In that note, the authors identify different dimensions of value (e.g. clinical effectiveness, safety, costs and economic implications, ethical, social, cultural and legal issues) and highlight that "the overall value may vary depending on the perspective taken, the stakeholders involved, and the decision context" ((O'Rourke, Oortwijn et al. 2020), p. 2). In alignment with this, stakeholder involvement is considered to be vital for increasing the credibility and acceptance of HTA decisions relating to coverage, reimbursement and pricing (Baltussen, Jansen et al. 2017; Oortwijn, Determann et al. 2017). Therefore, as part of evidence assessment and appraisal, the views of a large and diverse set of stakeholders need to be adequately captured to inform HTA-related policy-making, leading to the ongoing challenge of how to incorporate stakeholders' values and preferences into HTA processes (Bombard, Abelson et al. 2011, Baltussen, Jansen et al. 2017, Oortwijn, Determann et al. 2017). Two questions arise when one tries to tackle this challenge: first, 'who to involve', i.e. how to identify which stakeholders should be involved; and, second, 'how to involve' this (potentially large and diverse) set of stakeholders. Other than consultation processes (Brereton, Ingleton et al. 2017), the recently proposed Collaborative Value Modelling framework (Vieira, Oliveira et al. 2020) provides an answer to the second question; still, the first question remains

unanswered, as despite stakeholder analysis methods and techniques being used in a variety of fields to select who are (or should be) the relevant stakeholders (Reed, Graves et al. 2009), there is no universal framework (or guidance) for stakeholder identification in place. Furthermore, HTA agencies being responsible for assessing and appraising the value of new technologies, have not been systematically reflective about which stakeholders need to be involved in their evaluation. Therefore, agencies might involve different stakeholder groups as part of different participatory processes characterising alternative ways of collaboration (Whitty 2013). Additionally, the recent summary of the ISPOR HTA Council Working Group Report on Good Practices in HTA did not find specific good practices related to the use of participatory processes while defining the organizational aspects of HTA (Kristensen, Husereau et al. 2019). As a result, an evidence gap emerges on which is (and how to provide) the rationale for stakeholder identification, and engagement in HTA participatory processes. Such a gap is in alignment with recent literature calling for a more transparent, meaningful and systematic assessment of the value of new technologies by HTA agencies, to avoid divergent recommendations and to increase the consistency, legitimacy and acceptability of HTA decisions (Nielsen, Lauritsen et al. 2009; Nicod and Kanavos 2012; Nicod and Kanavos 2016; Akehurst, Abadie et al. 2017; Angelis, Lange et al. 2018; Angelis, Kanavos et al. 2020).

This study aims to identify relevant stakeholders and understand their interests, concerns and values in HTA evaluation processes of new medicines. To meet this objective, a framework based on Critical Systems Heuristics (CSH) (Ulrich 1987; Ulrich 2003; Ulrich and Reynolds 2010) was developed and empirically tested within the scope of the EU-funded Horizon 2020 IMPACT-HTA project.

The work reported helps HTA agencies to reflect about the inclusion of stakeholders' interests, concerns and values in the evaluation processes concerning new medicines. Our results have practical applications for increasing the transparency of HTA-related decisions, therefore ensuring that legitimacy, representativeness and accountability for reasonableness are all accounted for in the assessment of new medicines.

Methods

The CSH framework and its adaptation

Critical Systems Heuristics (Ulrich 1987; Ulrich 2003; Ulrich and Reynolds 2010) is a framework for self-reflective practice focused on social improvement by raising critical and social awareness (Venter and Goede 2017) used to support and/or evaluate interventions while enhancing stakeholders' communication. The CSH framework is organised around four basic aspects, known as boundary issues: motivation, power, knowledge, and legitimacy; each issue is further divided into three categories: social roles, specific concerns and key problems (Ulrich and Reynolds 2010). Twelve boundary questions then arise from combining the four basic boundary issues with the three categories, which can then be used to “make explicit the everyday judgments on which we rely (consciously or not) to understand situations and to design systems for improving them” ((Ulrich and Reynolds 2010), p. 244). These situations and systems are referred to as ‘reference systems’ in CSH terminology. Ulrich (Ulrich 1996) acknowledges that, depending on the context, it may be necessary to adapt the questions to the context in which they are applied. Hence, in this study, we adapted the CSH framework for

medicines' evaluation by HTA agencies, using this context as the reference system, to which we endeavoured to capture stakeholders' values and preferences by reflecting on 'who is' and 'who ought to be' involved within medicines' evaluation by HTA agencies. This reference system was shaped considering the following 'boundary issues' definitions:

- *Motivation*: who are/ought to be the beneficiaries of the HTA decision-making process, which beneficiary purposes are/ought to be served, which beneficiaries are/ought to be involved, and what is/ought to be the measure of improvement.
- *Power*: who are/ought to be the decision-makers possessing the resources and power for improving the HTA decision-making process, and who are/ought to be the decision-makers who decide upon the measures of success.
- *Knowledge*: who are/ought to be the experts possessing the HTA knowledge, and who implement relevant processes and guarantee their success.
- *Legitimacy*: who are/ought to be the ones affected by the implementation of HTA decision-making processes.

Following these definitions, we rephrased the original questions presented by Ulrich and Reynolds ((Ulrich and Reynolds 2010), p. 244) and reached the the set of twelve adapted questions presented in Table 1.

Table 1 The adapted CSH framework for the context of medicines' evaluation by HTA agencies

Boundary issue/Categories		Question
Motivation	Social roles (stakeholders)	1. Beneficiary: Who is/ought to be the intended beneficiary of the HTA process (including assessment and appraisal)?

	Specific concerns (stakes)	2. Purpose: What is/ought to be the purpose of the HTA process?
	Key problems (stake holding issues)	3. Measure of improvement: What is/ought to be the HTA process measure of improvement or success?
	Social roles (stakeholders)	4. Decision-maker: Who is/ought to be the ultimate decision-maker in the HTA process?
Power	Specific concerns (stakes)	5. Resources: What resources and conditions for the success of the HTA process does the HTA decision-maker control, or ought to control?
	Key problems (stake holding issues)	6. Decision environment: Which conditions of success lie, or ought to lie, outside the control of the HTA decision-maker?
Knowledge	Social roles (stakeholders)	7. Expert: Who is/ought to be considered relevant to participate in the HTA process?
	Specific concerns (stakes)	8. Expertise: What are/ought to be the relevant knowledge and skills for the HTA process?
	Key problems (stake holding issues)	9. Guarantor: What or who is/ought to be assumed to be the guarantor of success in the implementation of the result of the HTA process?
Legitimacy	Social roles (stakeholders)	10. Witness: Who is/ought to be representing the interests of those affected by but not involved in the HTA process?
	Specific concerns (stakes)	11. Emancipation: What secures, or ought to secure, the "emancipation" of those affected from the premises and promises of those involved? And what are/ought to be the opportunities for the interests of those affected to have expression and freedom about the HTA process?
	Key problems (stake holding issues)	12. Worldview: Which views of improvement of the HTA processes are/ought to be considered, and how they are/ought to be reconciled? What space is/ought to be available for reconciling differing views, amongst those involved and affected?

Framework testing

We applied the adapted CSH framework (see Table 1) via primary data collection through a questionnaire with HTA agency experts, having a current or previous affiliation with a national HTA agency. The full questionnaire can be found in Appendix 1. In the testing of the framework, it was only considered the 'is' (i.e. descriptive) questioning mode, as the objective was to understand who is currently involved in HTA decision-making across different European agencies, and how stakeholders' interests, concerns and values are aligned with current evaluation processes at HTA agencies.

Questionnaires were administered by email in September 2018, and responses were received by the end of October 2018. The research group invited a number of experts from HTA agencies, or that had assumed key and recent functions at HTA agencies, to participate in the study under the auspices of the IMPACT-HTA project. An information sheet outlining the purpose of the study and providing a description of participants' involvement and rights as a participant accompanied the questionnaire, alongside a consent form that had to be signed and returned for participants' responses to be considered. We asked participants to reflect upon and answer the questions in their capacity as national experts, to the best of their knowledge and experience, and in the context of their national HTA agency, by considering previous, or existing, evaluation processes for new medicines. All the questions were accompanied by a brief explanation, and at the end of the questionnaire, there was an 'open answer box' inviting for participant commentary or further suggestions.

After having received all responses from participating experts, three researchers (AV, MO, AA) with experience in HTA terminology followed the "framework method" (Gale, Heath et

al. 2013) for conducting the thematic (qualitative content) analysis needed to manage and map the data collected. The “framework method” was selected for the data analysis as it is a sound approach within the health research field because it is a systematic and flexible approach for analysing qualitative data (Gale, Heath et al. 2013). After making themselves familiar with the questionnaire’s answers, and while considering their organisation into the 12 CSH adapted questions, the three researchers coded and interpreted the data. When needed, results were reviewed collaboratively to ensure consensus. In the analysis, the research team focused on two main types of findings: which stakeholder groups were found to be relevant in the HTA evaluation processes across the different agencies, and what was the rationale behind the involvement of stakeholders within evaluation processes for the group of agencies.

LSE provided ethical approval for the study.

Results

In total, 11 study participants responded to the questionnaire. The 11 study participants were from six different national HTA agencies. Two participants came from, or had a previous affiliation with, the National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) in England, two from the Scottish Medicines Consortium (SMC) in Scotland, three from the Haute Autorité de Santé (HAS) in France, one from the Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency (TLV) in Sweden, two from the Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG) in Germany, and one from the Agency for Health Technology Assessment and Tariff System (AOTMiT) in Poland. From the analysis of the questions asking for social roles/stakeholders (see questions

1, 4, 7 and 10, Table 1), we identified seven stakeholder groups: patients and carers, general population, industry, payers and policymakers, HTA agencies, healthcare professionals, scientific experts and methodologists as critical for the context of medicines' evaluation by HTA agencies. Then, we analysed how many HTA agencies allocated each social role with each stakeholder group (see Table 2).

Table 2 Number of HTA agencies (from the total of six agencies inquired) that allocated the four social roles (Beneficiary, Decision-maker, Expert and Witness) with each of the seven stakeholder groups identified

Groups of stakeholders	Beneficiary	Decision-maker	Expert	Witness
Patients and carers	5	1	5	6
General population	3	1	2	3
Industry	3	1	3	2
Payers and policy-makers	5	6	4	2
HTA agencies	1	4	2	0
Healthcare professionals	4	1	5	2

Scientific experts and methodologists	0	0	6	0
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As illustrated in Table 2, only the scientific experts and methodologists were associated with a single social role, the one of 'experts'. The remaining stakeholder groups were all associated with more than one (social) role; for example, both patients and carers and healthcare professionals were associated with the four roles each, even if differences were found between HTA agencies, hence reflecting different specific concerns (stakes) and key problems (stake holding issues) in the organisation of evaluation processes at the level of the different HTA agencies. To help structure this rationale, Figure 1 captures the different concepts behind the involvement of stakeholders within evaluation processes for the participating HTA agencies. The rationale is called from the remaining questions of the adapted CSH framework (Questions 2, 3, 5, 6, 8, 9, 11 and 12, Table 1), and is organised within the CSH four 'boundary issues': motivation, power, knowledge and legitimacy.

Figure 1 Conceptual model to capture the rationale for stakeholders’ involvement within HTA evaluation processes, organised by the CSH four ‘boundary issues’: motivation, power, knowledge and legitimacy.

The rationale presented in the summary box in Figure 2 presents the results from combining the information already presented in Table 2 and Figure 1, and reflects the most common answers – when four or more agencies provided the same answer. This summary captures which are common roles assumed by stakeholder groups, and within the scope of the IMPACT-HTA project, was later used to guide the participatory processes geared towards the development of the multidimensional IMPACT HTA value framework to evaluate new medicines on a common basis.

Figure 2 Summary box of the most common roles assumed by stakeholder groups

The beneficiaries of an HTA process to evaluate new medicines and inform policy making are patients and carers, payers and policymakers and healthcare professionals (**question 1**). Given this variety of stakeholders, three different purposes were highlighted: to promote fair and transparent evaluation processes, with timely access to technology from patients, to ensure robust evidence and provide informed recommendations and to guarantee safe, clinical, economically sound and cost-effective interventions; promote efficient resource allocation (**question 2**).

The measures of success – for which payers and policymakers and HTA agencies are to be responsible (**question 4**) – are: level of uptake of HTA-recommendations, availability of recommended medicines in each health board or institution, efficient use of the HTA agency resources and the use of sound and evidence-based methods, stakeholder involvement and the improvement of health outcomes among patients and society overall (**question 3**).

To enable the organisation and management of such processes, resources are necessary, for instance, financial, human, cooperation with academic partners and other international HTA agencies and participation from the general population and other groups of stakeholders. These resources can be controlled by the decision-maker (**question 5**). On the other hand, resources deemed as necessary but that fall out of the HTA decision-maker are: population needs and epidemiological parameters, number and calibre of innovative products hitting the market, scientific integrity of HTA committee members and how prescribers act and conform with decisions and comply with recommendations (**question 6**).

Patients and carers, payers and policymakers, healthcare professionals and scientific experts and methodologists were considered to provide relevant knowledge and skills for the HTA process (**question 7**), namely evidence and data (clinical, medical and economic), information about comparators, healthcare professionals' experience from using health technologies, patients' experience of care and of the indication and health systems' knowledge, ethics and legal aspects (**question 8**). Aspects related to the legal enforcement from governments, agencies, regulators, policymakers or other entities and controlling mechanisms for the implementation of HTA results may guarantee that the result of the HTA process will be implemented or have an impact (**question 9**).

Patients and carers were the ones considered deemed of interest but who cannot speak for themselves (**question 10**). Initiatives such as public consultation, involving the patients and carers into committees at the HTA agencies and allowing for advocacy initiatives, interest group's participation and lobbying could bring patients and carers interests and values into the HTA process (**question 11**). Hence, the design of inclusive evaluation processes that allow for multidisciplinary discussion within methodologically more flexible approaches could reconcile all the values involved and hence improve the HTA process itself (**question 12**).

Discussion

HTA can be considered under the realm of participatory technology assessment, a concept that integrates “a wide range of knowledge and values in the assessment and policy making of new technologies that involve complex and uncertain decision contexts. Complexity and uncertainty arise because the assessment and policy making of new technologies often deal with “wicked” social problems associated with the introduction of the technology.”(Tavella 2016), p. 119). In HTA, part of this complexity arises from the multiple (and often divergent) set of stakeholders' interests, concerns and values present in assessing new medicines. Hence, one of the main challenges when pursuing more inclusive and democratic HTA processes is the inclusion of this diversity of interests, concerns and values in health technology assessment and policy making (Sorenson, Lavezzari et al. 2017).

Therefore, the objective of this study was to understand stakeholders' roles and involvement in national HTA agency evaluation processes to effectively guide the inclusion of stakeholders' interests, concerns, and values in the evaluation processes of new medicines. As described, to meet this objective, an adapted CSH framework was developed and empirically tested. The development of the framework was based on CSH for its reflective nature and its ability to provide a more detailed description of the system in analysis (evaluation of medicines in our case), by identifying the relevant stakeholders, which may be an opportunity to break down its complexity. Moreover, CSH has already been applied for similar objectives in various fields, for example, for participatory technology assessment in agriculture, namely for the assessment and policy making of genetically modified plants. (Tavella 2016) and beef farming (Setianto, Cameron et al. 2014, Setianto, Cameron et al. 2014), for participatory decision-making and

participatory planning in rural development (Ulrich and Reynolds 2010), and for guiding design science research (Venable 2009). To our knowledge, this is the first application of CSH in HTA, with recent literature recognizing the merits of its theories and methodologies to support Health Systems Research (Jackson and Sambo 2020).

Despite the fact that the adapted CSH framework was developed for allowing a general reflection on ‘who is’ and ‘who ought to be’ involved within medicines’ evaluation by HTA agencies (by including the two questioning modes), in this study, only the ‘who is’ mode was applied. Thus, it captures the scope of current evaluation processes followed by a group of national-level HTA agencies in Europe. It could be argued that this can hinder the framework’s reflective power, however, the aim was not to understand how these processes should be guided towards a more inclusive format (as was for example the objective of the research presented in (Tavella 2016)), neither to engage agencies in challenging the way they have been conducting their evaluation processes, but rather to understand who is currently involved in HTA evaluation processes across different European agencies. Therefore, using the ‘who is’ questioning mode has been deemed appropriate for this specific objective.

As it was expected (Cavazza and Jommi 2012, Allen, Pichler et al. 2013, Akehurst, Abadie et al. 2017), given their different input to decision-making, different stakeholders were found across HTA agencies. Nevertheless, the opportunity to identify stakeholders and understand their roles by identifying their different interests, concerns, and values can be used in different contexts. For example, within the scope of the IMPACT-HTA project, it was critical to identify relevant stakeholders to be involved in the development of the multidimensional value framework to evaluate new medicines on a common basis. This highlights the relevant role a

thorough stakeholder identification has in distinct problem structuring contexts, as already discussed by (Gregory, Atkins et al. 2020). This finding is also aligned with what Foote et al. (Foote, Gregor et al. 2007) discuss, namely that by making clear what are the interests, concerns and values associated with each group of stakeholders, we can identify important areas of agreement and disagreement between stakeholders. In our opinion, acknowledging these positions may assist in promoting consensus, shared understanding and group commitment in HTA decision-making.

The adapted CSH framework was also applied to a sample of 24 studies looking into model applications aiming at evaluating pharmaceuticals (selected from the review (Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019)). In this exercise (data not shown), we found that it is possible to apply the framework for the majority of the questions retrospectively, with exceptions for questions 10 and 11, which were not discussed in the sample of studies. It is also important to mention that many studies were far from being clear regarding the rationale for selecting stakeholders to be involved in those specific HTA participatory processes.

Assuming an all-inclusive HTA process where multiple groups of stakeholders are considered, study findings may have implications on stakeholder involvement in evaluation and decision-making processes, for instance providing knowledge vs. being a beneficiary, which illustrates the need for the design and application of such concepts and tools.

Finally, we believe the adapted CSH framework has the prospects to be applied at different decision-making levels, being relevant at distinct HTA decision-making contexts (e.g. regional agencies, hospitals, etc.) and for different health technologies (e.g. medical devices,

diagnostics, etc.). Furthermore, the CHS framework can be used in its present form or tailored for other specific health policy-making contexts.

Limitations

While the development and application of the described adapted CSH framework may be valuable for guiding the organisation of HTA evaluation processes where multiple stakeholders groups may be engaged, the results of this application need to be analysed with caution. The questionnaire collected the responses of a small number of participants, representing a few key HTA agencies in Europe, within a diverse range of healthcare systems. Nevertheless, the diversity of responses points out the need to extend questioning to a larger set of HTA agencies, so that conclusive results can be drawn on the conceptual model that summarises the diversity of different HTA agencies; also, it may be useful to engage a larger number of participants within a specific country or HTA context. Finally, given that the questionnaires were emailed to participants, it is possible that some questions may have been (mis)interpreted inconsistently by respondents.

Conclusions

The adapted CSH framework could be used for guiding the identification and selection of relevant stakeholders in the evaluation processes of HTA agencies, but also for understanding their roles based on their interests, concerns and values. This work further supports the recent literature calling for a more transparent, meaningful and systematic evaluation of new

technologies by HTA agencies. For this purpose, a better understanding of the decision-making processes is required, including stakeholders engagement and the rationale behind it.

Appendix 1

Who's in and who's out in HTA:

An analytical framework to critically identify stakeholders engaged in the evaluation of new medicines

Context: In Health Technology Assessment (HTA), as part of assessment and appraisal of the evidence, the views of a large and diverse number of key-stakeholders and decision-makers need to be adequately captured to promote representativeness and legitimacy. Literature in the area provides little information on which stakeholders are or should be involved in such participatory processes. Within the scope of the EU funded Horizon2020 IMPACT HTA project we are interested in understanding which stakeholder groups are being currently involved in decision processes at HTA agencies.

Aim: This study aims at developing and testing an analytical framework to systematically analyse and better understand which stakeholder groups are involved in evaluation processes at HTA agencies through primary data collection.

Method: We propose adapting the Critical Systems Heuristics conceptual framework [from Ulrich 1983, 1986, 1987, 2003, 2005], which is organized around four basic boundary issues (motivation, control, knowledge and legitimacy), each divided into three categories (social roles, specific concerns and key problems). Twelve boundary questions arise in this combination to potentially inform who “is” involved within HTA evaluation processes. By applying these questions to the relevant literature, in combination with this expert consultation with national HTA experts, our aim is to better understand who are the stakeholders currently involved in HTA decision-making for new medicines.

Process: Under the auspices of the EU funded project IMPACT HTA, we kindly invite you to answer the 12 questions presented below. We ask you to answer the questions in the capacity of a national expert and in the context of your own country’s HTA agency, by considering the evaluation processes currently in place for new medicines at the best of your own knowledge and experience. If you have any questions regarding the questionnaire, please contact Ana Vieira

(ana.lopes.vieira@tecnico.ulisboa.pt) and Aris Angelis (a.n.angelis@lse.ac.uk). We would appreciate if you could complete and return the questionnaire by the end of October 2018.

EXPERT CONSULTATION QUESTIONNAIRE

SOURCES OF MOTIVATION

- 1. Beneficiary:** Who is the intended beneficiary of the HTA process (including assessment and appraisal)?

(I.e., whose interests does the HTA process actually serve)

- 2. Purpose:** What is the purpose of the HTA process?

(I.e., what are the actual or potential consequences of the HTA process, including unintended or unforeseen side-effects)

- 3. Measure of improvement:** What is the HTA process measure of improvement or success?

(I.e., how can one gauge whether the HTA process is well performed and achieves its objectives)

SOURCES OF POWER

- 4. Decision-maker:** Who is the ultimate decision-maker in the HTA process?
*(I.e., who is interested **in the use** of the results of the HTA process)*

- 5. Resources:** What resources and conditions for the success of the HTA process does the HTA decision-maker control?
(I.e., on what resources and conditions does the implementation of the result of the HTA process rely, e.g. financial, human resources, etc.)

- 6. Decision environment:** Which conditions of success lie outside the control of the HTA decision-maker?
(I.e., what resources and conditions relevant for the HTA process does the HTA decision-maker not control, e.g. budget, national population need, etc.)

SOURCES OF KNOWLEDGE

7. Expert: Who is considered relevant to participate in the HTA process?
(I.e., who provides relevant knowledge and skills in the HTA process)

8. Expertise: What are the relevant knowledge and skills for the HTA process?
(I.e., what kind of knowledge or skills do experts actually contribute and what counts as relevant 'knowledge')

9. Guarantor: What or who is assumed to be the guarantor of success in the implementation of the result of the HTA process?
(I.e., what guarantee exists, if any, that the result of the HTA process will be implemented or have an impact? What or who assumes the role of guarantor and can be seen as a perfect or imperfect guarantor)

SOURCES OF LEGITIMACY

10. Witness: Who is representing the interests of those affected by but not involved in the HTA process?

(I.e., taking an inclusive perspective, who is treated as a legitimate stakeholder, and who represents the case of those deemed of interest but who cannot speak for themselves)

11. Emancipation: What secures the “emancipation” of those affected from the premises and promises of those involved? And what are the opportunities for the interests of those affected to have expression and freedom about the HTA process?

(I.e., where does legitimacy lie? How does the HTA process treat those who may be affected or concerned but who cannot defend their interests)

12. Worldview: Which views of improvement of the HTA processes are considered, and how are they reconciled? What space is available for reconciling differing views, amongst those involved and affected?

(I.e. on what world views is the HTA process based? That is, what are the different visions of 'improvement' among both those involved and those affected, and how does the process deal with these differences)

Thank you for answering to this questionnaire. In case you wish to make a comment or suggestion regarding the questionnaire, please use the following space.

Thank you for your participation!

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IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

Task 2, Part III: The IMPACT-HTA multicriteria value framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis

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Abstract

Health Technology Assessment (HTA) agencies make several types of decisions which require the evaluation of new medicines on a common bases and the consideration of multiple criteria. These decisions are not always made using structured formats nor supported by analytical tools, with Multicriteria decision analysis (MCDA) having been increasingly explored as they enable evaluations on a structured basis, involving stakeholders and experts, and considering multiple evaluation dimensions. However, MCDA models to evaluate health technologies available in the literature have mostly been developed for specific contexts, for instance with specific model structures and sets of weights, and do not enable HTA agencies providing committees with tools to evaluate distinct medicines on a structured basis and on a common value frame.

In this study we describe the development and testing of the IMPACT HTA socio-technical framework to assist HTA agencies in valuing medicines in multiple dimensions across diseases on a common basis. Technically, the framework combines the (MCDA) MACBETH approach with concepts of the swing weighting matrix so that a common value frame is set by the HTA agency for groups of therapeutic indications, and committees evaluate medicines on a structured basis and departing from the value set defined by the agency. Socially, the framework is developed through a collaborative modelling approach in which key HTA stakeholders and members of evaluation committees are involved in a sequence of Delphi and decision conferencing processes, so as to develop both the value frame for each therapeutic indication, and MACBETH value models for specific medicines' evaluations.

From the viewpoint of use by the HTA agency, the framework entails two phases: 1) consulting relevant stakeholders and experts, the HTA builds a general (multicriteria) value frame model structure, which is adjusted for distinct therapeutic indications, and then sets guidelines for evaluation committees making evaluations on a structured but flexible format; 2) and committees make structured evaluations with the MACBETH value measurement approach while considering the relevant value aspects set for the therapeutic indication.

We show how phase 1 has been implemented and tested with the views of a large number of European HTA stakeholders and experts and to depict the views of experts of the INAMI HTA Belgium agency.

1 Introduction

Health Technology Assessment (HTA) has significantly expanded in the last two decades due to the increasing need for improving efficiency in resource allocation in healthcare, there being a need to avoid the adoption of health technologies with little evidence of value and scope for developing methods and tools to better inform public decision-making (OECD 2017).

Within HTA, HTA agencies are commonly in charge of assessing and appraising the value of new technologies (e.g. new medicines and new medical devices) (Angelis, Lange et al. 2018), and generate recommendations on their coverage, reimbursement and pricing, effectively affecting their adoption and utilisation (Sorenson, Drummond et al. 2008). In several countries the decision-making process regarding the introduction of new health technologies has been informed by health economic concepts, for instance taking as a benchmark and as a reference the incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER), which allows the comparison of alternative technologies in terms of both their costs and health outcomes (Drummond, Sculpher et al. 2015). However, several recent studies have identified limitations in these economic evaluation methods, either in the use of an ICER as a single *guide* for selecting health technologies (Culyer 2016, van Baal, Morton et al. 2018), as well as in the use of quality adjusted life years (QALY) as a single measure for health outcomes (Prieto and Sacristán 2003, Dolan, Shaw et al. 2005, Nord, Daniels et al. 2009, Garau, Shah et al. 2011). Furthermore, several studies have shown that HTA agencies in practice – but not always formally – make use of dimensions that go beyond costs and health outcomes in evaluating and deciding upon health technologies (Sussex, Towse et al. 2013, Nicod and Kanavos 2016, Angelis, Lange et al. 2018).

Recently, Angelis *et al* (2018) performed a systematic review of the additional value concerns that are used in HTA agencies of eight European countries in their coverage recommendations and decision-making, showing that the way these concerns are incorporated in the appraisals varies significantly, and their relative importance remain generally unknown (Angelis, Lange et al. 2018). Furthermore, it is not clear what trade-offs HTA agencies are willing to make when performing the recommendations (Angelis, Lange et al. 2018) and there is evidence of substantial variation on how evaluation committees make decisions (see results from Task 1 of WP7 of IMPACT HTA). Other studies have also found that there are considerable inter-country variations between HTA agencies, as well as significant variations in the recommendations within countries' agencies (Kanavos, Nicod et al. 2010, Nicod and Kanavos 2012, Nicod and Kanavos 2016, Allen, Liberti et al. 2017).

In fact, in several contexts additional criteria – further to ICER – have been dealt with on an *ad-hoc*, non-systematic and often non-transparent way to inform decisions in HTA, bearing the risk of leading to inconsistent appraisals (Schwarzer and Siebert 2009, Kanavos, Nicod et al. 2010, Nicod and Kanavos 2012, Nicod and Kanavos 2016). The underlying issue is the complexity of these multidimensional problems, since decision-makers tend to simplify the process by adopting intuitive or heuristic approaches, when faced with multiple trade-offs, and as a result important information during the decision-making process can be ignored (Baltussen and Niessen 2006).

Even though one expects differences in decision-making by HTA agencies, as such differences might be driven by the divergent philosophy of these agencies, as a result of differential political, social and economic factors of their health systems (Allen, Pichler et al. 2013), by the longevity in the implementation of the HTA process in each country (Beletsi, Koutrafoura et al. 2018, Kristensen, Nielsen et al. 2019), and by the different budget constraints and national priorities (Kanavos, Nicod et al. 2010), several studies have acknowledged the need for more transparent and well-defined decision-making processes by HTA agencies to increase the legitimacy of the decisions (Nicod and Kanavos 2012, Akehurst, Abadie et al. 2017, Angelis, Lange et al. 2018, Kristensen, Nielsen et al. 2019) (Angelis, Kanavos et al. 2017). Furthermore, generally the current decision-making process at HTA level is not tailored to take into account a wide range and diversity of stakeholders' preferences, which is also key for the legitimacy in the sense that it is an important requirement for broad societal support for these recommendations (Angelis, Kanavos et al. 2017, Baltussen, Jansen et al. 2017, Oortwijn and Klein 2019). Therefore, it is argued that a higher level of stakeholder involvement in HTA processes is needed – and which should be encouraged by the HTA agencies – in order to identify and collect all the relevant values that society holds to a particular recommendation, and to improve the understanding and coherence among stakeholders of each other's values and in their argumentation regarding a recommendation (Baltussen, Jansen et al. 2017).

Accordingly, in order to face the challenge of enhancing the legitimacy, transparency and consistency of the recommendations for priority setting at the HTA agencies, some authors have explored the use of new methodologies that go beyond conventional health economic concepts, such as the Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) (Devlin and Sussex 2011, Thokala and Duenas 2012, Marsh, M et al. 2016, Thokala, Devlin et al. 2016, Baltussen, Marsh et al. 2019, Hansen and Devlin 2019). MCDA has its foundations in economics, psychology and mathematics, and is both an approach and a group of techniques that aim to support decision making in a clear and transparent way, in situations in which

multiple criteria are to be explicitly evaluated in order to rank or choose alternatives (Belton and Stewart 2002). MCDA can be defined as “an extension of decision theory that covers any decision with multiple objectives, a methodology for appraising alternatives on individual, often conflicting criteria, and combining them into one overall appraisal” (Keeney and Raiffa 1993). Two key advantages of using MCDA (Belton and Stewart 2002) is the structuring of the decision problem, in order to avoid simplifying heuristics and other biases known that affect complex decision processes, and the explicit modelling and incorporation of value systems and trade-offs.

There are different MCDA methods that make use of different analytic models. Almost all MCDA applications in health have involved value-measurement approaches based on weighted-sum models (also known as additive multi-attribute value models) (Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019) and based on the multi-attribute value theory (von Winterfeldt and Edwards 1986, Keeney and Raiffa 1993). In these models, each alternative’s “total score” is aggregated via a linear (additive) equation, based on the weight of each criterion (which represents the alternative’s degree of achievement on the criterion) multiplied by its relative weight (representing the relative importance of the criterion to the evaluator). These models have the advantage of the simplicity of the calculation of the total score for each alternative, however other non-linear functions (such as the multiplicative models) are also possible, but very rare (Hansen and Devlin 2019) (Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019).

In the context of HTA, MCDA has been shown to address some of the limitations pointed out in the economic evaluation of new technologies (Goetghebeur, Wagner et al. 2008, Devlin and Sussex 2011, Thokala and Duenas 2012). Specifically, by allowing the inclusion of a comprehensive list of value dimensions in an explicit manner, it allows the value assessment to be conducted in an encompassing manner (Angelis and Kanavos 2016). MCDA also provides a higher degree of transparency and consistency in the preference-elicitation process since an explicit incorporation of the relative importance of various value dimensions is made. And finally, heterogeneous viewpoints and preferences of all relevant stakeholders in the decision-making process can be incorporated in an open and transparent way, which increases the legitimacy of the decision processes (Angelis and Kanavos 2016). Ultimately, MCDA allows for a more transparent and consistent decision process among HTA committees and over time (Hansen and Devlin 2019).

The potential of using MCDA in the context of HTA have been reported in several studies (Goetghebeur, Wagner et al. 2008, Devlin and Sussex 2011, Angelis and Kanavos 2016, Thokala, Devlin

et al. 2016) and a number of organisations, including the European Medicines Agency (EMA 2012) and the Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care (IQWiG) in Germany (Danner, Hummel et al. 2011), have explored the use of MCDA methods in drug regulation and HTA, respectively.

Also, in 2014 ISPOR convened the “MCDA Emerging Good Practices Task Force” with the objective of establishing a common definition for MCDA and for developing practice guidelines for conducting MCDA to aid healthcare decision-making (Marsh, M et al. 2016, Thokala, Devlin et al. 2016). However, despite the identification of good practices guidelines, there is still the need for developing practical and methodological guidelines to truly assist MCDA users, since the full methodological details for MCDA implementation have not been sufficiently described and some applications have been lacking methodological quality (Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019). Furthermore, despite the current experimental application of MCDA in the context of HTA, most articles published so far report pilot and exploratory studies, with a few reporting a full successful implementation (Marsh, M et al. 2016, Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019). Several studies, including a systematic review that aimed at providing a critical review of the published studies on MCDA in the context of HTA, also found that some methodological quality improvements of MCDA studies in HTA are needed through the development of more robust methodologies, procedures and tools (Marsh, Lanitis et al. 2014, Baltussen, Marsh et al. 2019, Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019). These research pathways include developing new model features in realistic settings, good practice guidelines, as well as the adoption of technologies to enable participation and behavioural research (Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019).

It is important to note that in our view, and according to many authors, MCDA should be seen as an aid to support decision-making about new technologies (Roy 1996, Bana e Costa and Beinat 2005), and not to set automatic decision processes (Marsh, M et al. 2016). I.e., HTA agencies always have to include a deliberative component in their process of formulation recommendations, in order to account for all possible considerations that matter and to set priorities for the most effective alternatives at a particular time, and in order to serve a country’s specific health needs (Oortwijn, Sampietro-Colom et al. 2017, Baltussen, Marsh et al. 2019). And in order to do that, all the relevant aspects for a comprehensive assessment of value need to be made (Oortwijn, Sampietro-Colom et al. 2017). However, even though a common definition of value in the context of HTA is still absent (Antoñanzas, Terkola et al. 2016), there is a general agreement that more attention should be given to patients’ preferences, by considering all the benefits for the patient such as the ability to return to

work and care giver burden, as well as to the inclusion of other societal values, such as equity (Oortwijn, Sampietro-Colom et al. 2017, Lakdawalla, Doshi et al. 2018, Baltussen, Marsh et al. 2019).

The recognition of the need for incorporating additional benefits in the definition of value of new health technologies, in line with the societal values and the need for understanding the importance of different evaluation criteria, have led to the development of different “value frameworks” (Lakdawalla, Doshi et al. 2018). These value frameworks emerge mainly in the US and have also been motivated and inspired by the increasingly complex health technologies, the rising costs of these new technologies, and the perceived disconnect between price and value and for the need of measuring value, and ultimately aim to inform payers, clinicians and patients on the assessment of new medicines (Neumann and Cohen 2015, Oortwijn, Sampietro-Colom et al. 2017).

However, even though these value frameworks are an important step towards a more inclusive value based assessment process, not all of them are designed for policy or clinical decision-making (Angelis and Kanavos 2017). For example, some value frameworks are mainly intended to inform patient-clinician conversations and to facilitate the decision making process of patients by making fully informed decisions while supporting the development of clinical guidelines and pathways (such as the American College of Cardiology and the American Heart Association (ACC/AHA) (Anderson, Heidenreich et al. 2014), the American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) (Schnipper, Davidson et al. 2015) and the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) (NCCN 2015)), while others aim to support payer coverage determinations or price negotiations between payers and manufacturers (such as the Institute for Clinical Effectiveness and Review (ICER) value assessment framework (ICER 2020) and the Memorial Sloan Kettering Cancer Centre (MSKCC) (Bach 2015)). Furthermore, except for the ICER, these frameworks have been developed only for drugs in a specific disease (i.e. for cardiovascular or for oncologic drugs). A general comparison and summary between these value frameworks can be found elsewhere (Neumann and Cohen 2015, Angelis and Kanavos 2017, Slomiany, Madhavan et al. 2017, Sorenson, Lavezzari et al. 2017).

In Europe, the HTA Core Model[®] has been proposed as a value framework to be used by HTA organizations when assessing any health technology with the purpose of serving as a common methodological framework for international collaborative production and sharing of HTA information in a structured format (Kristensen, Lampe et al. 2017). In addition, as part of a EU-funded project “Integrated health technology assessment for the evaluation of complex technologies”, the

INTEGRATE-HTA model was developed as a step-wise approach that offers methodological guidance on the steps for the assessment of complex technologies (Wahlster, Brereton et al. 2017).

However, to the best of our knowledge, only two value frameworks have been set to support in detail HTA evaluation processes through multicriteria analysis: the Evidence and Value Impact on DEcisionMaking (EVIDEM) (Goetghebeur, Wagner et al. 2008) and the Advance Value Framework (AVF) (Angelis and Kanavos 2017). Both these frameworks aim to facilitate decision making by enhancing the transparency and consistency in the preference-elicitation process, and presuppose the participation of several stakeholders (e.g. researchers, HTA committees, health professionals, policy-makers among others), during the entire assessment process; both have been tested in several case studies (examples of applications (Wagner, Khoury et al. 2017) (Zozaya, Martínez-Galdeano et al. 2018) (Angelis, Linch et al. 2020)); both are set to calculate a linear additive model; but they differ in that ADVANCE HTA respects multi-attribute decision theory and value measurement principles (Belton and Stewart 2002).

Nevertheless, literature has not delivered frameworks that can be used by HTA evaluation committees to evaluate distinct types of medicines on a common but flexible value frame, i.e., ensuring that evaluations of similar medicines are performed consistently and using the same value frame, but still respecting that evaluations of medicines across disease areas entail specificities and that should be aligned within a flexible value frame. Also, existing frameworks have not established ways of systematically involving a large number of HTA stakeholders and experts in setting a value framework. Within the scope of the IMPACT HTA H2020 project, in this study we describe the IMPACT HTA multicriteria value framework to assist HTA agencies on the evaluation of drugs on a common but flexible basis and while addressing identified challenges. Specifically, the framework also uptakes the objective of reflecting the views and values of a wide range of HTA stakeholders and experts, with sound methods and friendly protocols of questioning being established.

The paper is structured as follows: in Section 2 we describe the IMPACT HTA Value Framework, then in Section 3 we describe how we tested phase 1 of the framework, and in Section 4 we show the results of those tests. Sections 5 and 6 discuss the framework and provide concluding remarks, respectively.

2 The IMPACT HTA value framework

2.1 Foundations and rationale

Despite the differences between the existing value frameworks in terms of their core purpose and different definitions of value, several authors have argued that some basic common principles need to be fulfilled by value frameworks (Oortwijn, Sampietro-Colom et al. 2017, Sorenson, Lavezzari et al. 2017, Willke, Neumann et al. 2018), for which we set the grounds for the IMPACT HTA framework:

- a) **Intended purpose:** it intends to help HTA agencies to adopt evaluation processes that promote more consistent decision-making related to medicines;
- b) **Stated users and target audiences:** HTA agency, HTA committees, HTA stakeholders and experts, and those making decisions regarding the adoption, reimbursement and pricing of medicines;
- c) **Rationale behind its application:** the framework is set for HTA agencies that:
 - wish to adopt more structured and transparent decision processes;
 - wish to make use of procedures to evaluate medicines on a common but still flexible basis, considering the specificities and contexts of distinct types of medicines from different disease areas;
 - find it adequate to set guidelines for HTA committees working through more structured processes, aligned with the value systems set by the HTA agency, but still respecting the nature of their deliberative work and the knowledge of their members, as well as variations in the amount and quality of evidence and data that affect their analyses and evaluations;
 - consider it relevant to systematically involve HTA agency stakeholders and experts in setting evaluation processes;
 - and that want to adopt sound techniques and participatory processes for evaluating medicines;
- d) **Well-defined, inclusive and transparent stakeholders' engagement process and promotion of consistency across decisions:** adopting a collaborative value modelling perspective (Vieira, Oliveira et al. 2020), the IMPACT HTA framework is set to make use of a set of Web-Delphi, decision conferencing and interviewing participatory processes to extensively involve HTA agency stakeholders and experts in building the value frame and in helping committees to

evaluate medicines in systematic and organized formats (potentiated by new web-based platforms); and the IMPACT HTA follows a constructive paradigm (Mingers and Brocklesby 1997), in that participatory processes are set to create collective alignment and to promote consensus, and committee members work within a collaborative learning process;

- e) **Be grounded in established and transparent methods:** the IMPACT HTA framework follows the socio-technical school of thought in MCDA (Phillips and Bana e Costa 2007) that embeds sound evaluation techniques with specifically designed participatory processes for model building; evaluation methods used in the framework are informed by multi-attribute value theory (Keeney and Raiffa 1976) (von Winterfeldt and Edwards 1986) and by value measurement concepts (Belton and Stewart 2002), with the MACBETH approach (Bana e Costa and Vansnick 1994) (Bana e Costa, De Corte et al. 2012) for value measurement and its protocols of questioning being adopted; accordingly, the IMPACT HTA value framework defines a set of protocols of questioning (including for trade-offs), replicable Web-Delphi and decision conferencing processes, as well as sets clear inputs and outputs regarding model building and the evaluation of medicines; the it builds upon methods developed within the ADVANCE HTA project (Angelis and Kanavos 2017) (Angelis, Linch et al. 2020), as well as on the development of Web-Delphi and collaborative value modelling approaches to involve health stakeholders and experts in MCDA modelling that were developed in previous European projects (Vieira, Oliveira et al. 2020) (Santana, Freitas et al. 2020) (Freitas, Santana et al. 2018). The adoption of value measurement methods in is line with previous literature pointing out its adequacy and preferred use in health contexts (Marsh, M et al. 2016) (Oliveira, Mataloto et al. 2019). The selected MACBETH approach is founded on the principles of (value-)difference measurement (Krantz, Suppes et al. 1971) and uses a nonnumerical elicitation protocol in which responders are invited to make their judgements by choosing one among seven qualitative categories – no difference, or very weak, or weak, or moderate, or strong, or very strong, or extreme difference – of difference in value (or desirability or attractiveness) (Bana e Costa, De Corte et al. 2012). MACBETH has been extensively applied for the multicriteria value measurement of multidimensional options in a variety of complex evaluation contexts (Bana e Costa, De Corte et al. 2016), including for the prioritization of health programmes (Oliveira, Rodrigues et al. 2012), for health states' evaluation (Oliveira, Agostinho et al. 2018), for building health indices (Rodrigues, Montibeller et al. 2017), for

resource allocation in health (Phillips and Bana e Costa 2007) (Hummel, Oliveira et al. 2017), and for the prioritization of public investments (Sanchez-Lopez, Bana e Costa et al. 2012) (Bana e Costa, Fernandes et al. 2006), as well as has been successfully tested in the ADVANCE HTA project (Angelis, Linch et al. 2020).

- f) **Include full range of available evidence including real-world evidence and broad effects of medicines:** by enabling HTA agencies to define processes to comprehensively evaluate medicines in multiple dimensions, the IMPACT HTA value framework helps agencies to set background information (including evidence, data, and experts opinion) which is useful to help committees evaluating medicines within the HTA agency value frame;
- g) **Ability to adapt to shifts in science, evidence, values, and the health care system more broadly:** the IMPACT HTA framework is flexible so that its use will depend on existing evidence and data, on the therapeutic context, as well as it accounts for the perspectives and values of HTA stakeholders and experts and of the agency, with committees being able to consider health system issues. Also, along time, the value frame can be adapted and improved according to experience from its implementation.

2.2 Overview

Aiming to help HTA agencies to promote the evaluation of medicines in multiple dimensions while making use of a common but flexible value frame, the development and use of the IMPACT HTA value framework is dynamic, with 3 phases being adopted (as illustrated in Figure 1):

- in phase 1, the HTA agency involves its stakeholders and experts in setting a common but flexible multicriteria value frame in which a comprehensive set of value aspects are broadly identified as relevant for evaluations, and those aspects are then given a relevance level for each therapeutic context; the value aspects to be considered in evaluation, as well as their relevance, together with evidence, data, and the MCDA procedures and guidelines for working in a structured format, are then set for work by HTA committees.
- in phase 2, committees start by working under the value frame set for the respective therapeutic indications and follow MCDA procedures and guidelines given by the HTA agency to evaluate medicines using the MACBETH approach and structured formats;

- in phase 3 the HTA agency analyses and reflects upon evaluation results from several HTA committees and upon feedback from committee members, so as to improve the value frame and tools for its use and implementation.

In both phases 1 and 2, HTA agency stakeholders and experts are invited to participate within the value modelling stages through collaborative value modelling, with a combination of Web-Delphi and decision conferencing group processes, as well as interviews, being used.

Figure 1: underlying development and testing cycle of the IMPACT HTA framework by HTA agencies

Figure 2 summarises the content of the phases from a socio-technical perspective, each phase being explained in detail in the following sub-sections. It embeds sound multicriteria evaluation methods with collaborative group processes required to involve and enable an interaction with HTA agency stakeholders and experts and between HTA committee members. Collaborative value modelling is grounded on a balanced combination between Delphi and decision conferencing processes which enables involving a large range of HTA agency stakeholders and experts in model building, while promoting convergence. Delphi has long been recognized in multiple contexts including health as a valuable non-face to face process “for the systematic collection and aggregation of informed judgements” ((Hasson and Keeney 2011), p. 1696) from all stakeholders, as well as a “knowledge acquisition technique” (Liou, Weber et al. 1990) (Liou 1992) for developing different models of

knowledge (Cairo 1998) (Hamilton and Breslawski 1996), being composed of a succession of rounds in which participants' views are collected through their individual answers in the same questionnaire. Enabling anonymity, a summary of the participants answers is returned to the participants and, at the light of the group knowledge, participants may change their opinion in the subsequent rounds. Delphi processes have shown to be effective for a group discussing complex issues (Linstone and Turoff 2002).

Decision conferencing is a face to face meeting defined “as a gathering of key players who wish to resolve important issues facing their organisation, assisted by an impartial facilitator who is a specialist in decision analysis and works as a process consultant (Schein 1999), using a model of relevant data and judgements created on-the-spot to assist the group in thinking more clearly about the issues” (Phillips and Bana e Costa 2007) (p. 54) and has proved to be effective in involving and aligning a small group in face-to-face value model building (Parnell, Bresnick et al. 2013).

Accordingly, the combination of Web-Delphi with decision conferencing enables implementing a collaborative knowledge acquisition strategy from HTA agency stakeholders and experts, in which one moves from individual judgemental knowledge from a (very) large and diverse number of stakeholders towards collaboratively developing a widely informed multicriteria evaluation frame. Additionally, the combination enables that involve HTA committee members, to acquire their knowledge, as well as to promote convergence in their evaluation of medicines for the specific context. Such processes are enabled by recent Web-Delphi platforms (for instance, the WELPHI decision support system (Decision Eyes 2021a)) which enable implementing Delphi processes in Web-formats in an expedite and user-friendly format (Freitas, Santana et al. 2018); and by decision support systems to enable the implementation of the MACBETH approach within a decision conferencing environment, such as M-MACBETH (Bana Consulting 2005) and WISEDON (Decision Eyes 2021b).

Figure 2: socio-technical components for implementing the IMPACT HTA framework

2.3 Phases

2.3.1 Phase 1

Recognising that it is challenging to build multicriteria value models that not only promote transparency and consistency in decision-making, but also take into consideration that the evaluation of medicines can vary across disease and therapeutic areas, and that there are often issues regarding availability of evidence and data for medicines under evaluation, as well as that evaluation committees should adopt deliberative but structured decision formats, the IMPACT HTA value framework is technically inspired by a specific feature of the swing weighting matrix (SWM) proposed by Parnell and colleagues (described in (Parnell, Bresnick et al. 2013) and that has been adopted and tested in several contexts (Ewing Jr, Tarantino et al. 2006, Geis, Parnell et al. 2011)). According to the SWM, prior to the construction of a multicriteria evaluation model, there are steps which include an explicit definition of the direct importance of value aspects deemed as relevant for the decision context. Prior to the building of multicriteria models, this feature of the SWM helps creating an alignment, reducing the value aspects (for instance, for some contexts some evaluation dimension are recognised as having little importance or relevance), as well as easing the communication of swing weights which

are a complex concept to decision-makers and are used later in modelling (Parnell, Bresnick et al. 2013). In fact, previous literature has shown the practical use in many contexts of importance weights (Parnell and Trainor 2009), despite of it being – when used in the phase of building evaluation models – recalled in literature as the most “common critical mistake” in decision analysis (Keeney 1992); and multiple studies failed to explicitly document the rationale for determining weights that are critical to communicate to higher levels of management or senior review groups (Parnell and Trainor 2009). Hence, decision-makers in several contexts have been able to intuitively first set importance weights as a first step before moving forward to determine relative weights when building an evaluation model for a specific evaluation context.

Applying this feature to the HTA context for different therapeutic indication contexts, we propose that the HTA agency adopts a process (involving its stakeholders and experts) to define:

- which value aspects are relevant for the evaluation of medicines, thereby capturing the value system behind the HTA agency operation;
- and then, for each disease or therapeutic indication, the HTA agency defines the relevance of each value aspect.

The use of a distinct categorisation of value aspects per therapeutic area enables adapting evaluations in different therapeutic contexts given the different components of medicines’ value, as well as evidence and data issues. Inspired by the study from Marttunen et al. (Marttunen, Haag et al. 2019), we propose that a relevance scale is used for categorising the value aspects, with each HTA agency defining its own relevance scale. Table 1 shows an example of the relevance scale developed experimentally in the IMPACT HTA project and that was used in empirically testing the framework: through it, a value aspects can be categorised as Essential, Influential, Complementary or Irrelevant according to the therapeutic context.

Table 1: Example of the relevance scale used for categorising value aspects in each therapeutic context in the IMPACT HTA project

Relevance	Description
Essential	<i>This aspect must be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it is not possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); it is not possible to reach an evaluation recommendation without explicitly considering performance on this aspect.</i>
Influential	<i>This aspect is highly desirable to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it could still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); the lack of favourable performance on this aspect could influence the decision in a detrimental way, as a desirable benefit may not be captured.</i>
Complementary	<i>This aspect is advantageous to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it would still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); favourable performance on this aspect could act supportively to complement the designated purpose of the medicine, i.e. "nice-to-have".</i>
Irrelevant	<i>This aspect does not necessarily need to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (evidence of the medicine's performance on it, does not influence if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose).</i>

Technically, phase 1 consists in structuring a value tree for which all the value aspects relevant to the evaluation of medicines for an agency are accounted for, and a tree with value aspects and their respective relevance for each therapeutic context.

From the social viewpoint, adopting the principles of collaborative value modelling, Web-Delphi and decision conferencing participatory processes are designed with the HTA agency to involve stakeholders and experts in that process of selecting (and defining) value aspects and their relevance for distinct therapeutic contexts. This requires that the agency identifies relevant groups of stakeholders and experts; that selects participants from the respective groups to be engaged; and that adapts the stages of collaborative value modelling described in (Vieira, Oliveira et al. 2020).

Web-Delphi processes can be selectively designed for the agency context and used to stimulate the reflection around an extended list of value aspects to be used, to validate the inclusion of aspects, for understanding the relevance of aspects for distinct evaluation contexts, as well as to identify relevant descriptors of performance for the aspects. And key HTA agency players can, departing from the results of the Web-Delphi processes, define the value frame and the value frame for each therapeutic context, within a decision conferencing context.

Once a HTA agency defines the value aspects deemed as relevant for distinct therapeutic contexts, it can then set evaluation guidelines for its committees working in structured formats and within (again)

a collaborative value modelling logic and using sound tools and concepts from MCDA and value measurement.

The IMPACT HTA framework defines that for a given therapeutic and evaluation context in which distinct value aspects have been defined as relevance, it is needed:

- A dossier selecting the medicines to be compared and with available evidence and performance data to analyse medicines on the relevant value aspects (while respecting other guidelines set by the agency concerning evaluation, including comparator information), together with information on the value aspects to be considered and their relevance;
- An adjustment of the collaborative value modelling approach for use by members of the evaluation committees, to follow the iterative steps of building multicriteria models of values, including:
 - A Web-Delphi process for members of the committee participating, prior to the decision conferencing meeting, and expressing their individual judgments regarding differences in attractiveness between medicines on different value aspects with MACBETH protocols of questioning;
 - The committee can then meet within a decision conferencing format, so that it proceeds in structuring and building a MACBETH value model to inform the decision-makers, which should also be subject to sensitivity and robustness analyses, and to final adjustments and validation, as well as to prepare recommendations.

Additive value modelling should be taken as working hypothesis (Bana e Costa and Pirlot 1997) in restructuring value aspects into (a set of concise, exhaustive, non-redundant and preference independent (Belton and Stewart 2002)) evaluation criteria, thereby adopting a constructive attitude in decision aiding (Bana e Costa and Pirlot 1997); there should be an alignment between the MACBETH protocols for partial value modelling and weighting used in the Web-Delphi and in the decision conference; and the common steps of going from model structuring to model building, and to model testing and validation should be followed.

Details of the procedures to be set by the HTA agency and used by committees' work using the MACBETH approach are further described and discussed in the next sub-section.

Following its views, the HTA agency can go further in providing a more structured value frame. Examples of more structured value frames for the agency to communicate to HTA committees are:

organizing value aspects into clinical and non-clinical ones, and additionally cost aspects; if the agency considers that CUA is a good starting point, it can organise value aspects so as to later calculate a multicriteria clinical score to be integrated in an extra cost per added multicriteria value score, with this measure being then used within a multicriteria score that considers non-clinical value aspects.

2.3.2 Phase 2

Within phase 2, HTA committees develop multicriteria value models of judgmental knowledge, informed by medicines' evidence and data, following the guidelines given by the HTA agency and accounting for the value frame; such model development is set through collaborative value modelling, in which social and technical elements are embedded in all stages of model building. We herein exemplify the general work that needs to be performed by committees.

First, medicines to be evaluated should be selected, and a synthesis of available evidence and data to analyse medicines' performance on the value aspects deemed as relevant for the therapeutic context should be defined. This includes filling medicines' performance (using evidence, data and/or expert judgment) in the relevant value aspects; considering further qualitative considerations relevant to complement evaluation (for instance, considering data quality or the quality of the evidence).

Second, it is designed a Web-Delphi process for committee members participating prior to the decision conference, so as to collect their individual value judgments about the treatments on key value aspects, based upon clinical evidence, with each participant providing his/her judgment by choosing the qualitative judgements about the difference in value between medicines, based on MACBETH scale. The Web-Delphi needs to be fed with performance data, makes use of MACBETH protocols of questions, and can generate information to inform partial value modelling and weighting. The implementation of the Web-Delphi can vary depending on the number of medicines to be evaluated, on whether the committee is to compare directly the medicines or wants to build or make use of a reusable model. It is advised that the Delphi entails two rounds, so that committee members provide their views and have an opportunity to interact.

Third, committee members participate and interact through the Web-Delphi process to align and acquire knowledge to motivate later face-to-face discussion in the decision conference. The output of the Web-Delphi is group majority judgements about the difference in value between medicines to

reach value aspects scores and weights for developing a prototype value model that can be used in the decision conference.

Fourth, the outputs of the Web-Delphi process – either group judgments and a prototype model – can be used to trigger the subsequent multicriteria decision conferencing process along the decision conference. Evaluation committee members need to undergo a set of MCDA phases for building a model to evaluate medicines, taking into consideration the value aspects and their relevance consensualised and communicated by the HTA agency, as well as HTA agency guidelines. The committees' work within a structured format can include:

- a) Warm-up discussion about the therapeutic and disease context, and analysis on whether all the value aspects relevant to evaluate medicines on the therapeutic context are considered (i.e. completeness of the set of aspects);
- b) Analyse the matrix of performance of the medicines on the value aspects, with a discussion on data availability and quality issues;
- c) Restructure the model if required, for instance combining value aspects into one criterion, if deemed as appropriate given preference dependence issues, and analysing redundancy and other issues relevant for structuring a value model;
- d) Analyse group judgments from the Web-Delphi and the prototype model, and initiate group elicitation of MACBETH judgments through an iterative and interactive group elicitation format. To guarantee technical coherence, the questioning protocol used in the decision conference should be the same as the one applied during the Web-Delphi stage, even if minor changes can be introduced considering that elicitation is performed at a group level. Additional to the inherent behavioural aggregation that occurs in the decision conference, voting procedures (Liou 1992), such as MACBETH voting may be used (Bana e Costa, Lourenço et al. 2014);
- e) Move from MACBETH qualitative judgments on the difference in value of medicines into numerical value scales and weights;
- f) Perform sensitivity analysis to data and/or judgements, as well as robustness analyses, so that a requisite model is reached (Phillips 1984), i.e. a good enough model that helps the committee to draw conclusions from the evaluation;
- g) And draw conclusions from evaluation and make recommendations to the decision-makers, that can be the agency or another entity (varying across countries).

A specific issue both for the decision conference and Web-Delphi, is that both require the work of an impartial facilitator to manage the process (Phillips 2007) (Vieira, Oliveira et al. 2020). As earlier mentioned, decision support systems can be adopted to enable the Web-Delphi and multicriteria decision conferencing stages with MACBETH.

Along the decision conference the committee is free to consider any qualitative issues and the decision conference provides a more structured deliberative process, to ensure alignment with the HTA agency value system.

As earlier mentioned, the agency can define a type of model structure (for instance, adjusting the incremental cost effectiveness ratio (ICER) to incorporate clinical aspects beyond QALYs, as well as non-clinical aspects further to the ICER) or give freedom to the committee selecting the most suitable model structure.

Figure 3 present examples of strategies for collaborative value modelling of value functions under the IMPACT HTA framework, showing that the implementation of the framework to assist committees may differ if a committee wants to build a model to directly compare and value the medicines' partial value, or if it wants to build value functions that can be used in that committee and in future committees. Together with the technical work, protocols and the tasks to be done in the Web-Delphi and in the decision conference are set.

Figure 3: Examples of strategies for collaborative value modelling of medicines' value functions

2.3.3 Phase 3

Given the complexity of building a common value frame that is to be used by committees in very different therapeutic contexts, the HTA agency needs to devote time to:

- Streamline procedures to build a dossier with evidence and data regarding relevant evaluation aspects;
- Analyse adjustments to the design and use of Web-Delphi processes to be used by different committees, as well as to improve expedite tools to enable an alignment of committee members before the decision conference;
- Analyse the experience of committee members along the structured decision conferences and challenges from using the IMPACT HTA framework;
- Analyse which value aspects have been used in practice for distinct therapeutic indications;
- Adjust the framework given the previous and other issues.

3 Approaches to test phase 1 of the IMPACT HTA Value Framework

The use of the IMPACT HTA value framework is dependent of the HTA agency context. In this study, we aimed at testing phase 1 of the framework in two collaborative value modelling parts:

- a) First by involving a large number of HTA agency stakeholders and experts – an international group of participants – so as to test on how to reach a common set of value aspects relevant for the evaluation of medicines;
- b) And second, specifically testing how a specific agency, departing from the results from a), can involve its HTA agency' stakeholder and experts to find the set of value elements and the relevance of those elements for distinct therapeutic contexts. This test took place within a case study developed at the INAMI Belgian HTA agency.

A first question that appeared in a) was which HTA agency stakeholders and experts to involve. Analysis of the literature has shown that these distinct stakeholders and experts assume different roles in different countries, and that there was no scientific approach to justify why specific stakeholders and experts should be involved. Accordingly, in another study developed within the scope of the IMPACT HTA project, Vieira et al. (Vieira, M. et al. 2021) developed an approach to identify stakeholders and experts, and found the following groups of stakeholders of relevant for 6 European HTA agencies: patients and careers, general population, industry, payers and policy-makers, HTA agencies, healthcare professionals, and scientific experts and methodologists. All these groups, except the general population, were considered in the designed methods.

3.1 Value aspects relevant for the evaluation of medicines by an international panel

3.1.1 Overview

Following Figure 4, it was designed a process in which, departing from a list of aspects identified from literature and from analysing implicit and explicit criteria used by HTA agency committees (step 1 in Figure 4, developed in another work of WP7 of IMPACT HTA), a large number of HTA agency stakeholders and experts were invited to provide their views separately within 6 parallel Web-Delphi panels (patients and careers, industry, payers and policy-makers, HTA agencies, healthcare professionals, and scientific experts and methodologists) about which of the selected aspects were

relevant for the evaluation of medicines (step 2 in Figure 4). These results concerning the views of each HTA stakeholder and expert group and by combining the views of all participants were then digested (step 3 in Figure 4) and then presented and discussed by key representatives from those groups, within a decision conferencing environment. These key representatives of the groups analysed whether the aspects should be included in the evaluation of medicines, as well as recommended adding other value aspects (step 4 in Figure 4). Results from the decision conference were digested into DC recommendations, as there was differences in opinion across key representatives (step 5 in Figure 4). By combining results from the Web-Delphi panels and from the decision conference panel, some conclusions were taken about value aspects which should be unquestionably included and excluded in the evaluation of medicines, and which aspects were not consensual for the two panels (step 6 in Figure 4). Aspects for which no consensus was found were the input for a final Web-Delphi panel in which all those that had participated in the previous parallel Delphi processes were invited to participate and provided their views on whether these aspects should be included (step 7 in Figure 4). The results of this second Web-Delphi were then analysed and led to a final list of value aspects deemed as relevant by an international sampe of HTA agency stakeholder and experts (step 8 in Figure 4).

Figure 4: Process adopted to consult an international panel of HTA agency' stakeholders and experts about which aspects are relevant for the evaluation of medicines by HTA agencies

All these participatory processes were prepared in detail, with Figure 5 providing an overview of the steps used to test the involvement of HTA stakeholders and to inform the construction of a common value frame by the HTA agency, under the perspective of collaborative value modelling. Accordingly, details of the planning, of the invited participants, of the knowledge elicitation tasks performed in each participatory process, of the knowledge extracted, and of the knowledge verification procedures, are made explicit. In the next subsections, we detail the three participatory processes, as well as make explicit the decision rules required to implement Figure 4.

Figure 5: Consultation of HTA agency stakeholders by following collaborative value modelling principles

3.1.2 Initial Web-Delphi

Six Web-Delphi processes were performed between February and March 2019 to engage different stakeholder groups with a wide range of expertise profile, in the evaluation of new medicines by ascertain their views on 24 previously selected aspects used for decision-making regarding critical determinants of HTA recommendation.

The total number of invited participants was 195, distributed within six panels, with each panel gathering participants from one specific stakeholder group, as follows: industry (n=40), payers and policy-makers (n=20), HTA bodies (n=33), healthcare professionals (n=30), scientific experts (n=46), and patients and carers (n=26).

In this two round web-Delphi process, participants were asked to specify their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5-level Likert scale ('Strongly disagree' (SD), 'Disagree' (D), 'Neither agree nor disagree' (NAD), 'Agree' (A), 'Strongly agree'(SA) plus an option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' (DN/DWA), about the relevance of each of the 24 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. In the second round, participants were also presented with an anonymous summary of the overall responses from the first round of their own panel, and had the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in the light of their panels' opinion. Furthermore, a final survey was sent to all participants that completed the second round, in which they had the possibility of suggesting other aspects to be considered in the evaluation of new medicines, different from those 24 aspects presented.

Results show that from the 195 invited stakeholders, 167 (85.6%) agreed to participate and completed the first round. From these, a total of 153 (91.6%) completed the second round, resulting in an overall participation rate of 78.5%.

A Delphi net agreement score (Dna) was calculated for each aspect using the following formula: $Dna = \%(SA+A) - f * \%(SD+D)$, in which $\%(SA+A)$ is the Delphi concordance measured by summing the percentages of "strong agreement" and "agreement"; $\%(SD+D)$ is the Delphi discordance measured by summing the percentages of "strong disagreement" and "disagreement"; and f is the Discordance factor (≥ 1). Adopting a discordance factor of 2 (giving to disagreement double the importance of agreement), a classification of "include", "doubt" or "exclude" was assigned to each aspect, by applying the following rules: $Dna > 80\%$ = include recommendation of the value aspect out of the Web-Delphi process; $Dna [50-80]$ = doubt; $Dna < 50\%$ = exclude.

3.1.3 Decision conference

Subsequently, two participants from each stakeholder group were invited to a one-day decision conference (April 2019), with 11 participating reviewing and discussing the results of the initial Web-Delphi process. For all aspects, the participants voted for their inclusion or exclusion, which led to the result classification as follows (Table 2):

Table 2: Decision conference result classification

Decision conferencing voting	Decision conference result classification of aspects
Consensual inclusion	Include
No consensus	Doubt
Consensual exclusion	Exclude

The new aspects proposed in the initial Web-Delphi were also subject to voting in the decision conference, and those that were not consensually excluded received the classification of “doubt”. Additionally, any new aspects proposed in the decision conference received the classification of “doubt”.

The results from the initial Web-Delphi and decision conferencing processes were analysed and combined into an overall outcome.

Table 3. Procedure used to combine the results from the initial Web-Delphi and from the decision conference

Initial Web-Delphi result	Decision conference result	Combined result
Include	Include	Include
Include	Doubt	Doubt
Include	Exclude	Doubt
Doubt	Include	Include
Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
Doubt	Exclude	Exclude
Exclude	Include	Doubt
Exclude	Doubt	Doubt
Exclude	Exclude	Exclude

3.1.4 Second Web-Delphi process

After combining the results of the initial Web-Delphi and decision conferencing processes, a novel Delphi process was implemented: this second Web-Delphi process intended to complete the collaborative process of identifying which value dimensions should be considered in this new value framework for HTA. It was focused only on 16 aspects for which doubts still subsisted at the light of the combined results of the initial Web-Delphi and the decision conference (cases of Doubt in the last column of Table 3).

Similarly to the initial Web-Delphi, in this second Web-Delphi the aim was also to get the views of a large and diverse number of HTA stakeholders, except that now they were gathered into one single panel. As this was the final stage of the collaborative process, only the 153 participants that successfully completed the two rounds of the initial Web-Delphi were invited to be part of the second Web-Delphi.

The Delphi tool place in September and October 2019, with participants being asked to specify a choice between 'Yes' or 'No' (plus an option for 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer') about the

relevance of each of the 16 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. In the second round, participants were also presented with an anonymous summary of the overall responses from the first round, and had the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in the light of the overall groups' opinion.

From the 153 invited stakeholders to take part in the second Web-Delphi, 118 (77.1%) agreed to participate and completed the first round. From these, a total of 102 (86.4%) completed the second round, resulting in an overall participation rate of 66.7%. The final decision rule for inclusion of an aspect was based on the voting of 'Yes' higher or equal to 50%.

3.2 Value aspects and their relevance for an HTA agency

At the level of the HTA agency, so as to move from a set of value aspects obtained from an international panel of aspects, it was designed a process to reach a common value set of aspects relevant for INAMI, and then to move towards the classification of value aspects by using the relevance scale for different therapeutic aspects.

3.2.1 Overview

Details about the planning, the involved participants, of the knowledge elicitation tasks performed in sequential participatory processes, of the knowledge extracted, and of the knowledge verification procedures, are made explicit in Figure 6, again following the steps of collaborative value modelling. In the next subsections, the three participatory processes are detailed.

Figure 6: Setting the value frame for distinct therapeutic indications with the HTA agency

3.2.2 Consultation with INAMI representatives to discuss value aspects

Consultation through email with two INAMI members aimed at obtaining feedback about the list of value aspects, with an emphasis on its completeness. The following question was used in the interviews: “From the perspective of INAMI-RIZIV in Belgium (HTA body), is any relevant value aspect deemed to be missing? At this stage we are not interested to the relevance of each of these aspects, only to whether something is missing”. INAMI members had the opportunity to suggest new value aspects. Additionally, the consultation included questions about the choice of therapeutic indications with interest to test the IMPACT HTA value framework for the agencies, as well as to discuss the INAMI stakeholders and experts to be involved in the Web-Delphi process. Five therapeutic contexts were defined, and 36 INAMI stakeholders and experts were identified to participate in the subsequent Web-Delphi. This interaction took place in April 2020.

3.2.3 Web-Delphi with INAMI stakeholders and experts about aspects relevance for distinct therapeutic indications

Departing from the list of aspects generated from the international panel of stakeholders and experts, and from the added value aspects suggested through the consultation, a 3-round Web-Delphi process was designed to understand the views of a panel of INAMI stakeholders and experts concerning “The relevance of the following value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in this disease context” using the relevance scale presented in Table 1 (classifying experts as Essential, Influential, Complementary or Irrelevant). The following therapeutic contexts were selected:

1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.
2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.
3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.
4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for non alcoholic steatohepatitis.
5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

In this Web-Delphi process 36 INAMI stakeholder and experts participated in three rounds between May 2020 and September 2020 with the following scope:

- Round 1:
 - input: list of aspects obtained in the consultation with INAMI representatives;
 - participants’ task: each participant anonymously makes comments to the list of value aspects and can suggest new aspects;
- Round 2:

- input: synthesis of results from Round 1;
- participants' task: each participant classifies the value aspect for relevance (essential, influential, complementary, irrelevant) for each of the 5 selected disease contexts;
- Round 3:
 - input: results from Round 2;
 - participants' task: each participant classifies each aspect in light of the results of Round 2.

13 INAMI stakeholders and experts answered to this Web-Delphi process. A feedback survey was implemented to collect participants views on the Web-Delphi process and results.

3.2.4 Interviews with INAMI representatives

Results from the Web-Delphi process were presented to two INAMI members, with a suggestion of the majority relevance category for each aspect being analysed for each disease context; or in case a relevance category did not gather more than 50% of the group judgments, consecutive categories gathering more than 50% were selected. The participants also could adjust results and select the relevant category for each value aspect (with this being replicated for all disease contexts) in the group interview that took place in November and December 2020.

4 Results from testing phase 1 of the IMPACT HTA Value Framework

In this section we present key results from testing the IMPACT HTA Value Framework either with international HTA stakeholders and experts, either with INAMI stakeholders and experts, using the approaches described in the previous section.

4.1 Results from consulting HTA agency stakeholders

4.1.1 Results from the first Web-Delphi process

The digested results from 153 (international) HTA agency stakeholders and experts that expressed their views in the first 6 parallel Web-Delphi processes concerning the relevance of considering 24 value aspects in the evaluation of medicines are presented in Table 4. Detailed results about differences in opinion from the 6 groups are analysed elsewhere (Dimitrovová, Vieira et al. 2021). By applying the concordance and Dna rules earlier described, 10 value aspects are to be included, 10 exclude, and 4 cast doubts. Out of the participants comments, 9 extra value aspects were identified.

Table 4: Results of the first Web-Delphi process (all stakeholder groups; n= 153) [Legend: Strongly Agree (SA); Agree (A); Disagree (D); Strongly Disagree (SD)]

Aspect name	Concordance (%SA+A)	Discordance (%SD+D)	Dna	Initial Delphi classification
1 - Severity of the disease	93%	3%	86%	Include
2 - Unmet need of the disease	92%	3%	86%	Include
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	71%	12%	46%	Exclude
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	100%	0%	100%	Include
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	99%	0%	99%	Include
6 - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	99%	0%	99%	Include
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	95%	1%	93%	Include
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	92%	2%	88%	Include
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	68%	12%	43%	Exclude
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	63%	10%	42%	Exclude
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	36%	25%	-14%	Exclude
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	54%	16%	21%	Exclude

13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	75%	5%	65%	Doubt
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	92%	1%	91%	Include
15 - Medicine's economic impact	86%	5%	77%	Doubt
16 - Medicine's affordability	80%	8%	65%	Doubt
17 - Medicine's efficiency	93%	5%	84%	Include
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	88%	2%	84%	Include
19 - Disease duration	59%	10%	38%	Exclude
20 - Disease age of onset	54%	16%	21%	Exclude
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	80%	5%	71%	Doubt
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	77%	4%	69%	Doubt
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	26%	33%	-39%	Exclude
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	58%	18%	23%	Exclude

4.1.2 Results after the Decision Conference

The discussions among 11 decision conference participants – departing from the analysis of quantitative and qualitative results of the Web-Delphi – led to the recommendation for inclusion presented in the third column of Table 5. Out of the 24 value aspects included in the Web-Delphi, 7 are to be included, 9 excluded and 8 cast doubts. Concerning the 9 aspects suggested by Web-Delphi participants, 6 were to be excluded, and 3 casted doubts. Decision conference participants further suggested 4 new value aspects. Divergences were observed among the Web-Delphi results and the decision conference results, with the combined results, obtained by applying the rules presented in Table 3, being presented in the last column of Table 5.

Table 5: Synthesis of the results of the initial Web-Delphi and of the decision conference and combined result

Aspect	Initial Web-Delphi result	Decision conference result	Combined result
1 - Severity of the disease	Include	Include	Include
2 - Unmet need of the disease	Include	Include	Include
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	Include	Include	Include
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	Include	Include	Include
6 - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	Include	Include	Include
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	Include	Doubt	Doubt
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	Include	Exclude	Doubt
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	Exclude	Doubt	Doubt
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Include	Include	Include
15 - Medicine's economic impact	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
16 - Medicine's affordability	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
17 - Medicine's efficiency	Include	Include	Include
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Include	Doubt	Doubt
19 - Disease duration	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
20 - Disease age of onset	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude

<u>New aspects suggested in the initial Web-Delphi</u>			
Quality of evidence	–	Exclude	Exclude
Surrogate outcomes	–	Exclude	Exclude
Patient feedback/User experience	–	Exclude	Exclude
Specialist prescribing for the first years	–	Exclude	Exclude
Type of National Health System	–	Exclude	Exclude
Adherence to treatment	–	Exclude	Exclude
Medicine's environmental impact	–	Doubt	Doubt
Medicine's "value of hope"	–	Doubt	Doubt
Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	–	Doubt	Doubt
<u>New aspects suggested in the decision conference</u>			
Medicines' impact on patient functionality	–	Include	Doubt
Medicine's time for treatment effect	–	Include	Doubt
Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	–	Include	Doubt
Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	–	Include	Doubt

4.1.3 Results of the second Web-Delphi process

Value aspects for which there were doubts after the decision conference were subject to a second Web-Delphi in which the 153 participants that completed the previous Web-Delphi were invited. 102 participants finished this Web-Delphi, for which the application of majority rules led to the classification presented in the last column of Table 6.

Table 6: Final results of the second Web-Delphi process carried out with an international panel of HTA agency stakeholders and experts

Aspect name	Yes	No	DN/DWA	Classification
Medicine's adverse events profile (aspect 7 in the initial Web-Delphi)	92%	8%	0%	Include

Medicine's tolerability to patients (aspect 8 in the initial Web-Delphi)	89%	10%	1%	Include
Medicine's mechanism of action (aspect 11 in the initial Web-Delphi)	30%	67%	3%	Exclude
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients (aspect 13 in the initial Web-Delphi)	78%	18%	4%	Include
Medicine's economic impact (aspect 15 in the initial Web-Delphi)	90%	9%	1%	Include
Medicine's affordability (aspect 16 in the initial Web-Delphi)	78%	20%	2%	Include
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (aspect 18 in the initial Web-Delphi)	91%	8%	1%	Include
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (aspect 21 in the initial Web-Delphi)	75%	24%	2%	Include
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (aspect 22 in the initial Web-Delphi)	81%	16%	3%	Include
Medicine's environmental impact	40%	55%	5%	Exclude
Medicine's "value of hope"	29%	67%	4%	Exclude
Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	57%	37%	6%	Include
Medicines' impact on patient functionality	86%	11%	3%	Include
Medicine's time for treatment effect	50%	46%	4%	Include
Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	78%	21%	1%	Include
Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	76%	22%	2%	Include

4.1.4 Final results from the process of involving HTA stakeholders

As a result of the collaborative process, the final list of 20 aspects presented in Table 7 was obtained. This list was taken as the starting point for discussion in the INAMI HTA agency.

Table 7: Final list of aspects from the collaborative process

Aspect name
A - Severity of the disease
B - Unmet need of the disease
C - Medicine's impact on mortality
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life
F - Medicine's adverse events profile
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community
J - Medicine's economic impact
K - Medicine's affordability
L - Medicine's efficiency
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

4.2 Results from setting the value frame for distinct therapeutic indications at INAMI

Collaborative processes performed with INAMI stakeholders and experts are herein presented.

4.2.1 Complete list of aspects

Along the consultation of INAMI representatives, no new value aspect was added.

4.2.2 Results of the Web-Delphi process to set aspects relevance across therapeutic indications

3 new aspects were proposed by INAMI participants in round 1. The votes of 13 participants after round 3 of the Web-Delphi process, for two out of the five therapeutic indications, are presented in Table 8 and Table 9 (for an indication regarding metastatic prostate cancer, and an indication regarding spinal muscular atrophy, respectively). In grey are the votes of the relevance category or consecutive relevance categories that gathered more than 50% of the opinions.

Table 8: Results of the Delphi process with INAMI participants to classify aspects by relevance for Disease Context 1 - Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer. [Legend: majority relevance from Web-Delphi results in grey; selection of final classification by INAMI representatives in dark grey]

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	0	0	10	3
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	9	4	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	9	4	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	8	4	1	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	8	4	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	4	8	1
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1	2	8	2
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	7	6	0	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	7	4	1	1
K - Medicine's affordability	7	5	0	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	7	5	1	0
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	2	3	7	1
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	0	4	7	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	6	4	1	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	4	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	2	3	6	2
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	2	1	6	3
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	4	6	3
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	5	4	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	5	5	3	0

Table 9: Results of the Delphi process with INAMI participants to classify aspects by relevance for Disease Context 2 - Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy. [Legend: majority relevance from Web-Delphi results in grey; selection of final classification by INAMI representatives in dark grey]

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	9	4	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	8	2	2	1
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	8	5	0	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	5	8	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	3	8	2
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	7	6	0	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	7	4	2	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	6	7	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	7	5
J - Medicine's economic impact	6	5	1	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	1	6	5	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	4	6	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	3	6	3
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	2	6	4
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	2	5	2
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	5	3	4	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	6	6	1	0
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	5	3	5	0

4.2.3 Results from the group interview

In the group interview, the two INAMI members analysed the Web-Delphi results and selected a relevance category considering the answers of the Delphi participants and their own view (categories in dark grey in Table 8 and in Table 9). For these two indications, the interviewees punctually changed aspects relevance (with justification) for a few value aspects. Many qualitative comments arose along this process.

Table 10 presents the value aspects to be considered by INAMI committees and their relevance for the described therapeutic contexts. One can clearly observe that aspects' relevance differs across

therapeutical indications. In other therapeutical contexts not reported in here, some aspects were deemed as irrelevant for evaluation.

Table 10: Overview of value aspects by relevance to be considered by INAMI committees when evaluation medicines from the selected therapeutic contexts

	Disease context 1: Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer	Disease context 2: Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy
Essential	A - Severity of the disease B - Unmet need of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality D - Medicine's impact on morbidity E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life F - Medicine's adverse events profile G - Medicine's tolerability to patients J - Medicine's economic impact K - Medicine's affordability L - Medicine's efficiency M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	A - Severity of the disease B - Unmet need of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality D - Medicine's impact on morbidity E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life F - Medicine's adverse events profile J - Medicine's economic impact K - Medicine's affordability L - Medicine's efficiency S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s) U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)
Influential	H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	G - Medicine's tolerability to patients M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality R - Medicine's time for treatment effect

		T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
Complementary	<p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>	<p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	-	-

5 Discussion

Results show that it is possible to implement Phase 1 of the IMPACT HTA framework, with promising results being obtained.

Results from the testing of the collaborative modelling processes to test the IMPACT HTA framework suggest that:

- Many value aspects that are not formally recognised within formal evaluation models by many HTA agencies seem to be of relevance for the evaluation of medicines. This result is aligned with the findings from other studies in that several value dimensions should be considered in the evaluation of medicines (for instance, aligned with (Lakdawalla, Doshi et al. 2018));
- There are clear differences in opinion among HTA stakeholders and experts, with the adopted methods contributing to convergence in opinions; the adopted methods were successful in enabling the participation of a large number of HTA agency stakeholder and experts in

building a common value frame; additionally, the framework enables understanding the opinions of each HTA agency stakeholder and expert, which may be quite relevant – see the case of the patients and carers opinions;

- Despite of a common value frame, the evaluation of medicines for distinct therapeutical contexts needs to consider specificities, and distinct aspects assume distinct relevance; accordingly, the structuring of value aspects by a large panel of stakeholders and experts and by agency members by relevance and per therapeutic context has shown that it is possible to go further in the testing of the framework; additionally, this is a key feature of the framework;
- Out of the testing of the framework, a large amount of information was generated (for instance, results from several Web-Delphi processes, including qualitative comments and feedback surveys concerning the process and the results); despite these comments are not presented in this document, participants from the different processes gave very positive feedback concerning the adopted collaborative value modelling processes.

Several challenges were perceived in the testing of the framework:

- There is a need to develop tools to enable an expedite implementation of the IMPACT HTA framework;
- Implementation of the framework requires facilitation by individuals knowing Delphi and decision conferencing processes, as well as knowledge concerning MCDA modelling.

There is still a need to go further and fully test the IMPACT HTA framework in case studies with evaluation committees from HTA agencies, which has also been performed in other studies (see Task 3 from IMPACT HTA WP7). Building a requisite model is another reason for the use of MACBETH questioning protocol, as a major concern in decision conferencing is to balance theoretically sound and sophisticated modelling with the development of a transparent, comprehensive and understandable model which has a substantive meaning to participants.

Please not that, within the IMPACT HTA value framework we do not expect that the multicriteria models set in phase 2 mechanistically replace the committee, but they guide the committee in reaching a conclusion.

6 Conclusion

In this article we proposed the IMPACT HTA value framework to help HTA agencies to evaluate medicines while comprehensively considering a multidimensional set of value dimensions.

The proposed framework makes a four-fold contribute to literature: to enable HTA agencies evaluating medicines in multiple value dimensions, aligned with the agency value system; to involve extensively HTA agency stakeholders and experts in setting the value framework; in helping committees to make structured decision aligned with the agency value system; and having a system that has a common value frame, but that also considers the specificities of evaluations within distinct therapeutic indications.

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IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

Task 2, Part IV: Exploring HTA stakeholders' views on value aspects in the evaluation of new medicines

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Abstract

Introduction:

Comprehensive stakeholder engagement has been recognised as being key for increasing legitimacy in Health Technology Assessment (HTA) decision processes, with different HTA agencies involving a range of stakeholders in distinct ways. This study collects and analyses the views of *all* relevant stakeholder groups on which value aspects should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines.

Methods:

Six parallel two-round web-Delphi panels were conducted to obtain the views of six stakeholder groups regarding their agreement on 24 previously identified value aspects potentially relevant for the evaluation of new medicines, using a five-point Likert scale. The most relevant value aspects for each stakeholder group were identified based on the rating agreement percentages. Inter-rater agreement and heterogeneity in the views between the six stakeholder groups were also estimated.

Results:

A total of 153 participants (78.5% response rate) completed the web-Delphi process. More than half of the 24 value aspects were considered relevant for the evaluation of new medicines. Inter-rater agreement suggests a substantial agreement within participants of two stakeholder groups (i.e., Payers & Policy-makers and Healthcare Professionals) and a moderate agreement within participants of four stakeholder groups (i.e., Industry, HTA bodies, Scientific Experts, and Patients & Carers). Heterogeneity in opinions was found for nine out of the 24 value aspects between stakeholder groups.

Conclusion:

HTA agencies can gain valuable insights from the involvement of stakeholders, which may be relevant in decision-making. Such involvement requires the adoption of methods to promote agreement in technology assessment. Results suggest that HTA evaluations should consider a wide range of value aspects.

1. Introduction

Health Technology Assessment (HTA) has evolved substantially since its origins in the US in 1976 [1] and its uptake and use have expanded considerably in the last three decades. This is due to the increasing need for improving efficiency in healthcare resource allocation whilst also ensuring affordability [2].

The primary role of HTA agencies is to assess and appraise the value of new technologies and generate recommendations on their coverage, reimbursement and pricing, ultimately affecting their adoption and utilisation [3] [4]. However, the HTA scientific and decision-making community has recognised several methodological challenges in the use of traditional economic evaluation approaches. For example, they are limited in the range of value aspects that can be incorporated in a structured way; they judge the value of new technologies through non-empirically validated rules, for instance through somewhat arbitrary and debatable thresholds; and they have limited potential to collectively incorporate stakeholders' views [5].

Studies show that HTA agencies consider, explicitly or implicitly, additional value aspects in their decision-making (often referred to as "other considerations" or "social value judgements"), going beyond the clinical benefits and costs of treatments captured in conventional economic evaluation and clinical benefit assessment [6] [7] [8] [3]. However, the extent to which such value aspects are incorporated in the appraisals often varies significantly, and their relative importance remains generally unknown [3]. These differences may be potentially explained by specific risk or value preferences, contextual factors, the subjectivity in the interpretation of the results, uncertainty [9, 10], and the perspective taken, the decision context and the stakeholders involved [1].

As a consequence, several studies have acknowledged the need for more transparent and well-defined evaluation and decision-making processes by HTA agencies, in order to better understand the plausible reasons for diverging recommendations and to increase the consistency and legitimacy of the decisions [3, 11-14] [5, 15] [10].

It has been argued that the decision-making process and coverage recommendations should not be based solely on the preferences of the individual representatives involved in the appraisal and negotiation process, usually acting on behalf of the HTA agencies or payers; instead, the preferences and the views of all stakeholders who have an interest in, or who can be affected by a coverage decision – such as patients, caregivers and healthcare professionals – should be

captured and incorporated into the decision-making process [5]. Such an encompassing engagement should be encouraged by HTA agencies, by involving an iterative process of actively soliciting the judgments and values of all relevant stakeholders [16]. It is also a key factor for the legitimacy of the decisions, as representativeness is an important driver to ensure broad societal support [14, 17, 18]. This encompassing stakeholder involvement poses an enormous challenge given the various interests and perspectives that must be balanced throughout [15]. Although some studies have focused on the role that some stakeholder groups might exert in the HTA process [15, 19-21], these concerns have not been systematically addressed [4] [15] [20]. The type of stakeholders involved, the nature of their involvement, and the way this involvement is ultimately taken into consideration vary across settings [22], as different HTA agencies have adopted their own approaches [15] [22].

Stakeholders should be involved early in the process of choosing the value aspects, since this choice itself involves value judgments [5]. This process must involve multiple stakeholders and a fair process that can ensure that a consensus on the selected aspects is reached, or at least that all stakeholders accept the validity and fairness of the process that was used to choose them [5]. Then, a shared understanding of their relative importance to inform the appraisal process would increase transparency and, therefore, the reasonableness and credibility of the decisions [3] [23].

Some studies have explored the differences in the relative importance of the value aspects for different stakeholders, for example the general public, patients, HTA committees or decision-makers [24] [25] [12] [26] [27] [28] [26]. However, to the best of our knowledge, no study has systematically explored through a consensus-building process, the involvement of a large and diverse range of participants, the views of distinct stakeholders regarding which value aspects should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines. In order to address this gap in the literature, the aim of this study, undertaken in the context of the EU funded Horizon 2020 IMPACT-HTA project (work-package 7) [29], is to collect and analyse the views of different stakeholder groups regarding the value aspects that should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines. Our study addresses three research questions: 1) Which value aspects do distinct stakeholder groups agree that should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines? 2) Is there an agreement within each stakeholder group? 3) Are there differences in agreement between stakeholder groups? This study could be a starting point for HTA agencies to gain insights on the views of different stakeholder groups.

2. Methods

2.1 Expert sample

The selection of stakeholder groups was based on a previous study that analysed which stakeholder groups are, and should, be involved in the evaluation processes of HTA agencies [30]. A total of 195 HTA experts from existing professional networks of the authors and of members of the IMPACT HTA project were invited for participation, belonging to six stakeholder groups: Industry (n=40), Payers & Policy-makers (n=20), HTA Bodies (n=33), Healthcare Professionals (n=30), Scientific Experts (n=46), and Patients & Carers (n=26).

Ethics approval for the study was granted by the ethical committee from the London School of Economics. All participants received an email invitation for participation, relevant information concerning their involvement and expected contribution, as well as an informed consent form, and had to express their interest to participate in the study via email confirmation.

2.2 The Delphi process

The Delphi method is widely used to collect and aggregate the opinion of survey participants' around topics where agreement (or consensus) can have an important role [31, 32]. The criteria for including experts should be defined in the Delphi process's preparation phase to prevent selection bias [33], as was the case in our study.

We deployed the Delphi method to explore stakeholder perspectives systematically and iteratively and identify differences in the views between and within stakeholder groups. Specifically, six Delphi panels consisting of two rounds each were conducted in parallel for all stakeholder groups using the web-based *Welphi* platform [34]. Usually the Delphi method consists of at least two and not more than four rounds of inquiry [31], and the number of rounds is set with the target of attaining stability in the responses, and not necessarily with the target of achieving consensus [35].

We used the value aspects identified in a previous task carried out within the scope of work-package 7 of the IMPACT-HTA project [29], and in the first round, participants were asked to specify their level of agreement (using a 5-point Likert scale "strongly agree", "agree", "neither agree nor disagree", "disagree", "strongly disagree", or by selection the option "Don't

Know/Don't want to answer”) on each of the 24 listed value aspects (available in Appendix 1) potentially relevant for the evaluation of new medicines, by reflecting on the following statement: “This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”. A definition of each aspect was provided in the platform to assist participants in their reflection.

In the second round, participants were presented with the same list of 24 aspects and with an anonymous summary of the overall responses of their panel from the first round. Accordingly, participants had the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous responses in light of the opinion in their respective panel. A final survey was sent to all participants that completed the second round, giving them the opportunity to suggest additional value aspects that they considered relevant.

The unique features of the Delphi made it the preferred method for our study. Firstly, it facilitated an efficient group dynamic processes and allowed us to gather opinion and knowledge of a large and heterogeneous sample of participants with different backgrounds and in various geographic locations [36-38]. Secondly, it allowed participants to express their opinions without giving in to group pressure, by allowing for anonymity. And thirdly, each participant had the opportunity to revise their answers considering the group opinion, thus promoting agreement, by allowing for iteration and controlled feedback [31, 35, 38].

Before initiating the Web-Delphi process, participants had to give their informed consent. Examples of screenshots from the *Welphi* platform are available in Appendix 2.

2.3 Data analysis

Data collected in each round were analysed in order to answer the three research questions. All analyses were performed using Stata version 16.1® [39] and Microsoft Excel®.

First, group agreement was calculated for each value aspect, of each stakeholder panel, in each round, to identify which value aspects participants agreed that should be considered for the evaluation of new medicines. This group agreement was established by applying the following decision rule: a value aspect receiving more than 75% of responses of strongly agree and agree (i.e. > 75% “SA” + “A”) was approved by *qualified majority*. This type of majority rule, based on the aggregated percentage of responses given in a Likert scale has proved useful in other contexts, such as in political voting systems [35] and in healthcare [36].

Second, the inter-rater agreement (IRA) was calculated for each panel in each round, in order to estimate the agreement within each stakeholder group, on the overall views regarding the 24 value aspects that should be considered for the evaluation of new medicines. The IRA measures the propensity for two or more raters to independently classify a given aspect into the same predefined category, while taking into account the agreement between participants that would occur simply by chance, preventing the overestimation of the level of agreement [35, 40]. Specifically, we used the recently developed Gwet's agreement coefficient (K_g) [40] which intends to overcome some of the weaknesses [41-43] of the well-known Kappa statistics [44] [45]. Gwet's agreement coefficient can be applied to multiple raters, multiple rating categories, any level of measurement and a varying number of ratings per subject (i.e. missing values) [46]. The Gwet's agreement coefficient was weighed for partial agreement in the sense that a "less serious disagreement" is given to two participants that rate the same value aspect in adjacent categories (e.g. "strongly agree" and "agree"), than in nonadjacent categories (e.g. "strongly agree" and "disagree") [46].

Third, to estimate whether there are statistically significant differences between stakeholder panels regarding their agreement on each of the value aspects that should be considered for the evaluation of new medicines, the Kruskal-Wallis H test was computed. In addition, since the Kruskal-Wallis H test only identifies if there is a statistically significant difference between at least one of the six stakeholder panels regarding one specific value aspect, the Dunn's test for binary pairwise multiple comparisons (binary) was performed, in order to explore exactly between which panels those differences occurred for each aspect [47].

In addition, the Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed-ranks test was used to measure the stability in answers over Delphi rounds (i.e. the consistency of responses between rounds) [35]. Specifically, it tests for the null hypothesis that the median of the differences of the paired data of the same group of individuals is zero [48]. For all analysis, a 95% confidence interval was used.

Finally, suggestions for additional value aspects inclusion mentioned in the final survey were listed by stakeholder panel.

3. Results

3.1 Panel participation

From the 195 participants invited for the web-Delphi, 167 (85.6%) agreed to participate and completed the first round. From these, a total of 153 (91.6%) completed the second round, resulting in an overall participation rate of 78.5%. The total number of participants in each round, as well as the response rate by panel are detailed in Table 1. The overall dropout rate was highest among healthcare professionals (30%), and lowest among Payers & Policy-makers (10%) (Table 1). The final survey was completed by 90 (58.8%) participants.

<Table 1>

3.2 Participants' agreement on value aspects

The results on the percentage of ratings of “strongly agree” and “agree” for all 24 value aspects and stakeholder groups (from round 2) are presented in Table 2. The value aspects approved by the *qualified majority* decision rule (i.e. > 75% “SA” + “A”) are highlighted in grey. For the value aspects below this threshold, it was considered that no agreement was found.

Nine value aspects were approved by *qualified majority* across all stakeholder groups (numbers indicate their listing in Table 2): “1 - Severity of the disease”, “2 - Unmet need of the disease”, “4 - Medicine's impact on mortality”, “5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity”, “6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life”, “7 - Medicine's adverse events profile”, “8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients”, “14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community” and “17 - Medicine's efficiency”. On the contrary, no agreement was found in five value aspects in all stakeholder groups: “11 - Medicine's mechanism of action”, “12 - Medicine's spill-over effects”, “19 - Disease duration”, “20 - Disease age of onset” and “23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support”.

Additionally, ten value aspects were approved by *qualified majority* in at least one stakeholder group. For example, “15 - Medicine's economic impact” was approved by *qualified majority* in all stakeholder groups except in Patients & Carers, whereas “24 - Medicine's therapeutic

positioning” was only approved by *qualified majority* in Payers & Policy-makers. This information is also summarised in Table 3.

In almost all value aspects, the difference between the percentage of ratings of “strongly agree” + “agree” between round 1 and round 2, suggests a convergence in the responses between participants in light of their panels' opinion. In seven value aspects, the differences in responses resulted in their approval by *qualified majority* in round 2, that was not achieved in round 1. For simplicity, only the results from round 2 are shown in Table 2, however a full table with the results from both rounds is available in Appendix 3. Additionally, a table with descriptive statistics i.e. percentage of responses in each category, median, and interquartile range is available in Appendix 4.

<Table 2>

<Table 3>

3.3 Inter-rater agreement

Results from the Gwet’s agreement coefficient are presented in Table 4. By using the benchmark scale suggested by Landis and Koch (1977) [49], in the first round, a “moderate agreement” was found in all stakeholder groups, except for the Healthcare professionals, where a “substantial agreement” was found ($K_g = 0.63$, $p < 0.01$). In other words, there was a higher propensity for the 25 participants of this group to independently classify the value aspects into the same predefined Likert-scale. In round 2, the Gwet’s agreement coefficients in each panel were slightly higher but still within the same agreement level, thus indicating a higher IRA, with the exception of the Payers & Policy-makers where there was a shift from “moderate agreement” ($K_g = 0.60$, $p < 0.01$) to “substantial agreement” ($K_g = 0.64$, $p < 0.01$), as defined by the respective benchmark interval.

<Table 4>

3.5 Differences between panels

Statistically significant differences were found between the six stakeholder groups regarding the agreement of nine out of the 24 value aspects (Table 5). Specifically, the Kruskal-Wallis H test suggests that there are statistically significant differences in the mean ranks in the responses of at least one panel in the following value aspects: “2 - Unmet need of the disease”, “6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life”, “9 - Medicine's contraindications of use”, “11 - Medicine's mechanism of action”, “15 - Medicine's economic impact”, “16 - Medicine's affordability”, “17 - Medicine's efficiency”, “18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials” and “24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning”. This means that for these value aspects, there is at least one stakeholder group whose overall responses are statistically different from at least one other stakeholder group (at 95% confidence interval). Pairwise comparisons (Dunn’s test) between panels showcase which stakeholder groups differ from each other. For example, for value aspect 2 “Unmet need of the disease” ($H(5)=15.26, p<0.01$), pairwise comparisons showed a statistically significant difference in the agreement between Industry vs. Scientific Experts ($p<0.05$), and between Scientific Experts vs. Patients & Carers ($p<0.05$). Specifically, scientific Experts had a lower level of agreement (55% “strongly agree”) versus Industry (90% “strongly agree”) and versus Patients & Carers (95% “strongly agree”). In another example, for value aspect 6 “Medicine's impact on health related quality of life” ($H(5)=33.49, p<0.01$), pairwise comparisons showed that Payers & Policy-makers had an agreement which was statistically significantly different from all remaining panels.

The results of the two-sided Wilcoxon matched-pairs signed-ranks were not statistically significant for any of the six stakeholder groups. This means that with a 95% CI we cannot reject the hypothesis that the median of the differences between the responses of the second and first rounds in each panel are different from zero, suggesting stability of the responses between the two Delphi rounds.

<Table 5>

3.6 Results from the final survey

Regarding the final survey, nine additional value aspects were suggested to be considered in the evaluation of new medicines: “value of hope” and “option value” were suggested by the Industry; “quality of evidence”, “surrogate outcomes” and “environment’s sustainability” were suggested by HTA bodies; “environment’s sustainability” was also suggested by Healthcare Professionals in addition to “patient feedback/user experience”, “adherence to treatment”, “specialist prescribing for the first years”, and “type of National Health System”.

4. Discussion

The outcomes of HTA processes predominantly relate to coverage and reimbursement decisions which influence health care services provision and have direct implications on health care expenditures and health outcomes. As a result, a vast range of parties (i.e. stakeholders), have an interest in these HTA outcomes such as manufacturers (industry), patients and carers, health professionals, payers and policymakers, scientific experts and HTA bodies [50]. Therefore, the involvement of all these stakeholders has been advocated as crucial in order to guarantee that all relevant viewpoints and values are taken into account in the evaluation process, thus contributing to the credibility of the HTA process [51].

Even though the HTA process is still not tailored to take into full account the values of all stakeholders [51], recognising the complexity of considering different values simultaneously has led to more structured and transparent approaches, such as deliberative processes. This could encourage dialogue between different stakeholder groups, and consequently to better incorporate what is considered important by these stakeholders [52].

This study aimed to collect and analyse the views of different stakeholder groups regarding the value aspects that should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines. Six parallel web-Delphi panels consisting of two rounds were conducted in order to assess their agreement on 24 different value aspects, with each panel corresponding to one stakeholder group (Industry, Payers & Policy-makers, HTA Bodies, Healthcare Professionals, Scientific Experts, and Patients & Carers). This allowed us to explore commonalities and differences between and within these stakeholder groups, about which value aspects should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines.

Regarding our first research question, “Which value aspects do distinct stakeholder groups agree that should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines?”, and based on the applied rule (i.e. approved by *qualified majority*), our results showed that from the list of 24 value aspects, more than half should be considered for the evaluation of medicines. On one hand, results indicate that different stakeholders believe there are many additional value aspects, beyond the traditional health economic and clinical outcome metrics currently used by economic evaluations and clinical benefit assessments, that should be considered in the decision-making process. Probably the best examples would correspond to severity of the disease, unmet need of the disease, medicine's adverse events profile, medicine's tolerability to patients and medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community; all these were accepted by *qualified majority* in all six stakeholder groups. On the other hand, ten other value aspects were approved by *qualified majority* in at least one panel. This confirms our hypothesis that there are potential differences in the perspectives of different stakeholders of what constitutes value. Consequently, the inclusion of these considerations in the evaluation process can provide a broader perspective on the relative value of a technology. For example, medicine's economic impact was approved by *qualified majority* in all panels except in Patients & Carers, while medicine's special warnings and precautions was only approved in this stakeholder group. In the case of patients, other studies have pointed out that they tend to be least represented and that some of their values (e.g. equity, potential usability, acceptability of side-effects and implications for daily life), may not be adequately captured [53] [54]. Value aspects not approved by *qualified majority*, i.e. value aspects for which there was no agreement, would require further discussion on their inclusion in the evaluation of new medicines, that could depend on the disease specificities or on the specific context of each HTA agency.

We also aimed at exploring the differences in the views within and between stakeholder groups, regarding which value aspects should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines. Such comparison was enabled as we performed six independent, but parallel, web-Delphi processes. On one hand, each participant had the opportunity to revise their answers in light of their group's opinion, thus promoting an agreement within each stakeholder group. On the other hand, the same Delphi design was used for all stakeholder groups, allowing for comparisons between groups. Overall, we found that there was a “substantial” or “moderate agreement” within each stakeholder group, regarding the value aspects that should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines. Even though there is no specific guideline in the literature regarding what level of convergence indicates agreement, Cohen's suggested that a level of agreement as low as 0.41

(which corresponds to the lower bound of the “moderate agreement” benchmark defined by Landis and Koch (1977) [49]), might be acceptable in health-related studies [44]. Based on these results, we could argue that there is an agreement in the perspective of what constitutes value considering the list of 24 value aspects, within the same stakeholder groups. However, when analysing the agreement of each value aspect between stakeholder groups, our results indicate that there are statistically significant differences between stakeholder groups regarding nine out of the 24 value aspects. This suggests that different stakeholder groups may have different or even opposing opinions, and that the inclusion of all these diverse views in the HTA process can promote a discussion and help towards a shared understanding of value.

We used the Delphi method to systematically and iteratively explore the stakeholders’ agreement on the topic through a structured format. In addition, its ease of use through an online platform allowed us to involve many participants located in different geographical locations. The objective was not to achieve a consensus between the participants but to achieve an agreement. In fact, it is very difficult to achieve a consensus in a Delphi study, which is a special case of agreement and occurs only if all participants attribute the same rating to an aspect [55].

Participants’ commitment is key for the success of a Delphi process, and as such several reminders were sent to participants who did not complete the questionnaire in the initially specified time allowed, with deadlines extended to enable a higher participation rate. This allowed us to reduce the nonresponse bias, since high drop-out rates could compromise the representativeness of all points of view. Overall, we were able to achieve a high response rate in all stakeholder groups, with the highest in the Payers & Policy Makers panel in round 2 (100%) and the lowest in the Industry panel in round 1 (77.5%). Even though no common guidelines exist for a minimum response rate, generally, authors recommend a 70% rate as necessary for each round to maintain rigor [56].

Limitations

There are some limitations in our study that should be highlighted. Firstly, there are different measures that can be used to determine the level of agreement [35], and consequently, the results may differ based on the selected methodology. We used the following decision rule: a value aspect receiving more than 75% of responses of “strongly agree” and “agree” was approved by *qualified majority* [36]. The use of percentages to measure the level of agreement is common in Delphi

literature [35], and a 75% of agreement was considered as evidence of a majority opinion, although there is no consensus in the literature on what percentage of responses constitutes a minimum level of agreement [57]. Similarly, there are different measures to estimate IRA, which can also affect the results. We used the recently developed Gwet's agreement coefficient [40] which intends to overcome some of the weaknesses [41-43] of the well-known Kappa statistics [44, 45], and has been recently used in other studies [58, 59].

Secondly, it is important to note that our participants' sample is not a representative sample of the six stakeholder groups, since establishing stakeholder representativeness was not the objective of this study, and of Delphi studies in general [60]. Nevertheless, as participants' selection can affect the results, a systematic approach to select which stakeholder groups to involve was followed, together with the establishment of a set of criteria for participants' involvement. Details of this process are reported in [30].

5. Conclusion

Our results demonstrate that different stakeholders believe many additional value aspects should be considered in the decision-making process, going beyond the metrics of economic evaluation and clinical benefit assessment. Our study also shows that there are potential differences in the perspectives of stakeholder groups about what constitutes value, and consequently, the inclusion of these considerations in the evaluation process can provide a broader perspective on the relative value of a technology. These results highlight the need to engage diverse stakeholder groups in the evaluation process of new technologies and to adopt methods that can promote their agreement.

Regarding policy implications, by analysing the heterogeneity between and within stakeholder groups, our results enable an understanding of the extent to which stakeholder views diverge, reinforcing the importance of including different stakeholders in technology appraisal and of using techniques to promote consensus.

Key messages from this study are: a) many value aspects should be considered in the decision-making process for the evaluation of new medicines; b) despite the large agreement between stakeholder groups, there are still differences in the perspectives about what constitutes value; c) disease specificities and the specific context of each HTA agency could explain some of these

differences; and d) HTA agencies should reflect about these findings and the implications for their evaluation processes.

Tables

Table 1. Response rate, by stakeholder group in rounds 1 and 2.

Stakeholder group	No. Invited	No. (%)		Overall % of dropout rate
		Round 1	Round 2	
Industry	40	31 (77.5%)	29 (93.5%)	27.5%
Payers & Policy-makers	20	18 (90.0%)	18 (100.0%)	10.0%
HTA bodies	33	29 (87.9%)	28 (96.6%)	15.2%
Healthcare professionals	30	25 (83.3%)	21 (84.0%)	30.0%
Scientific experts	46	42 (91.3%)	38 (90.5%)	17.4%
Patients & Carers	26	22 (84.6%)	19 (86.4%)	26.9%
Total	195	167 (85.6%)	153 (91.6%)	21.5%

Table 2. Percentage ratings of “strongly agree” (%SA) and "agree" (%A) for the 24 value aspects, per stakeholder group (round 2).

	Industry	Payers & Policy-makers	HTA bodies	Healthcare professionals	Scientific experts	Patients & Carers
Value aspect	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A
1 - Severity of the disease	97%	100%	89%	100%	87%	90%
2 - Unmet need of the disease	100%	89%	93%	100%	79%	100%
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	69%	78%	64%	76%	68%	79%
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	100%	100%	100%	100%	97%	100%
6 - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	100%	94%	97%	100%	100%	100%
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	93%	89%	93%	100%	97%	94%
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	90%	88%	89%	100%	87%	100%
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	48%	78%	57%	86%	63%	95%
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	45%	73%	61%	67%	64%	79%
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	34%	23%	35%	57%	16%	68%
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	55%	39%	36%	71%	60%	58%
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	69%	83%	57%	86%	82%	79%
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	97%	89%	100%	81%	92%	90%
15 - Medicine's economic impact	93%	94%	92%	81%	87%	64%
16 - Medicine's affordability	58%	89%	93%	86%	82%	79%

	Industry	Payers & Policy-makers	HTA bodies	Healthcare professionals	Scientific experts	Patients & Carers
Value aspect	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A	%SA + %A
17 - Medicine's efficiency	89%	100%	92%	90%	94%	90%
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials ¹	79%	89%	n/a	95%	89%	n/a
19 - Disease duration	62%	61%	64%	62%	50%	58%
20 - Disease age of onset	35%	67%	60%	62%	61%	37%
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	83%	89%	86%	76%	79%	69%
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	72%	66%	78%	81%	82%	79%
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	38%	23%	21%	24%	27%	22%
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	72%	83%	60%	53%	37%	58%
Total number of value aspects approved by <i>qualified majority</i>	12	17	13	17	15	15

Notes: ¹ Due to an unexpected error in the Welphi platform, this aspect was not showed in the HTA bodies and Patient and Carers panels and therefore results are not available.

Results are based on the question: "This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis".

Value aspect receiving more than 75% of "SA" and "A", i.e. approved by qualified majority are highlighted in grey. For the value aspects below this threshold, there was no agreement.

Table 3. List of value aspects approved by qualified majority and with no agreement, round 2

Value aspects approved by qualified majority by all panels	
Value aspect	Panels
1 - Severity of the disease 2 - Unmet need of the disease 4 - Medicine's impact on mortality 5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity 6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile 8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients 14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community 17 - Medicine's efficiency	All 6 panels
Value aspects approved by qualified majority by at least one panel	
Value aspect	Panels
15 - Medicine's economic impact	5 panels (In, P&PM, HTA, HPro, ScE)
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	5 panels (In, P&PM, HTA, HPro, ScE)
16 - Medicine's affordability	5 panels (P&PM, HTA, HPro, ScE, P&C)
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	4 panels (P&PM, HPro, ScE, P&C)
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	4 panels (In, P&PM, HPro, ScE)
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	4 panels (HTA, HPro, ScE, P&C)
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	3 panels (P&PM, HPro, P&C)
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	3 panels (P&PM, HPro, P&C)
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	1 panel (P&C)
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	1 panel (P&PM)
Value aspects with no agreement in all panels	
Value aspect	Panels
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects 19 - Disease duration	All 6 panels

20 - Disease age of onset	
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	

Note: In: Industry, P&PM: Payers & Policy-makers, HTA: HTA bodies, HPro: Healthcare professionals, ScE: Scientific experts, P&C: Patients & Carers.

Table 4. Inter-rater agreement (to classify a given value aspect into the same predefined category) by stakeholder group, in rounds 1 and 2.

Stakeholder group	Round 1				Round 2			
	<i>Ky</i>	95% CI		Benchmark Interval	<i>Ky</i>	95% CI		Benchmark Interval
Industry	0.56***	0.47	0.66	Moderate agreement	0.60***	0.50	0.69	Moderate agreement
Payers & Policy-makers	0.60***	0.52	0.68	Moderate agreement	0.64***	0.57	0.71	Substantial agreement
HTA bodies	0.56***	0.46	0.66	Moderate agreement	0.58***	0.47	0.69	Moderate agreement
Healthcare professionals	0.63***	0.56	0.69	Substantial agreement	0.65***	0.58	0.72	Substantial agreement
Scientific experts	0.52***	0.44	0.60	Moderate agreement	0.57***	0.48	0.65	Moderate agreement
Patients & carers	0.45***	0.35	0.54	Moderate agreement	0.60***	0.49	0.72	Moderate agreement

Notes: Inter-rater agreement measured by the Gwet’s agreement coefficient with linear weights.

Benchmark scale of the level of agreement as suggested by Landis and Koch (1977): Coef. < 0.00 Poor agreement; 0.00 > Coef. ≤ 0.20 slight agreement; 0.20 > Coef. ≤ 0.40 Fair agreement; 0.40 > Coef. ≤ 0.60 Moderate agreement; 0.60 > Coef. ≤ 0.80 Substantial agreement; 0.80 > Coef. ≤ 1 Almost perfect agreement [1].

Table 5. Differences between stakeholder groups in responses for each value aspect in round 2.

Value aspect	Kruskal-Wallis H test ¹	Dunn's test for pairwise comparisons ²
2 - Unmet need of the disease	15.26***	In - ScE**, ScE - P&C**
6 - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	33.49***	In - P&PM***; P&PM - HTA***; P&PM - HPro**; P&PM - ScE***; P&PM - P&C***
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	16.21***	In - P&C***; ScE - P&C***
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	19.26***	In - P&C**; HPro - ScE**; ScE - P&C***
15 - Medicine's economic impact	16.70***	P&PM - P&C**; HTA - HPro**; HTA - P&C**
16 - Medicine's affordability	13.83**	In - HTA**
17 - Medicine's efficiency	12.82**	In - P&PM**
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials ³	13.31***	In - HPro***; In - ScE**
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	11.67**	P&PM - ScE**

Notes: ¹Chi-squared adjusted for ties with 5 degrees of freedom, except for Aspect 18 (3 degrees of freedom). For simplicity of the table, only the value aspects for which a statistically significant result was found, are showed.

² Dunn's test (pairwise multiple comparisons using the Bonferroni adjustment)

³ Note that panel 3 (HTA bodies) and 6 (Patients and carers) were not considered.

*p<0.1; **p<0.05; ***p<0.01

In: Industry, P&PM: Payers & Policy-makers, HTA: HTA bodies, HPro: Healthcare professionals, ScE: Scientific experts, P&C: Patients & Carers.

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iMPACT HTA

The logo for iMPACT HTA features the word 'iMPACT' in a bold, black, sans-serif font, with a lowercase 'i'. The letter 'C' is replaced by a circular graphic consisting of several concentric rings in various colors (yellow, green, blue, purple, pink) that create a rainbow-like effect. To the right of this graphic, the letters 'HTA' are written in the same bold, black, sans-serif font.

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

Task 2, Part V: Detailed Delphi reports

IST and LSE teams

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 779312. The results presented reflect the author's views and not those of the European Commission.

Content: List of reports

- Report to participants, first web-Delphi process with an international panel of HTA agency stakeholders and experts, organized – composed by six parallel Web-Delphi processes from 6 HTA agency stakeholder and expert groups
 - A Report to payers and policy-makers stakeholder group
 - B Report to industry stakeholder group
 - C Report to patients and careers stakeholder group
 - D Report to scientific experts and methodologists stakeholder group
 - E Report to healthcare professionals stakeholder group
 - F Report to HTA bodies stakeholder group
- G Report to participants, second web-Delphi with an international panel of HTA agency stakeholders and experts
- H Report Web-Delphi results for INAMI on the relevance of value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in five disease contexts

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2: Report with results from the Web-Delphi process of the Payers and Policy Makers panel to identify which value dimensions should be considered in the “New multicriteria framework to facilitate Health Technology Assessment (HTA)” organisations in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”

Grant Agreement No.:779312

Work Package: WP7, Task 2

Prepared by: IST (Universidade de Lisboa) and London School of Economics

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1 Background information

IMPACT HTA is a research project looking at new and improved methods across 10 thematic research areas aiming at understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, and integrating clinical and economic data from different sources to improve methods in economic evaluation in the context of HTA and health system performance measurement.

Within IMPACT HTA work package 7 (WP7) research is taking place towards the development and testing of a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new medicines. This fits into the second task of WP7, whose aim is twofold: first, to structure a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, with these models reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers; and, second, to define alternative techniques and questioning protocols to build such a model. The starting point of Task 2 in terms of potential aspects of performance feeds from the results of Task 1 of the WP which has econometrically analysed the determinants of HTA recommendations by relying on secondary data. Following the completion of Task 2, the methodological framework will then be tested in practice through a number of case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies that will be carried out within Task 3 of WP7.

In order to build such a framework, two questions are currently being answered within Task 2: First, which aspects should be considered in a novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis? And second, which of those aspects are fundamental for that evaluation?

In order to address the first question, you kindly participated in a Web-Delphi process. The objective of this report is to provide you with an overview of the aggregated Web-Delphi results for all panels, and also more detailed results for your own stakeholder panel (Payers and Policy Makers).

Regarding the general features of the already developed Web-Delphi process, the views of a mix of a large and diverse number of stakeholders were collected in separate panels (Panel 1: Payers and policy-makers; Panel 2: HTA bodies; Panel 3: Health care professionals; Panel 4: Patients and carers; Panel 5: Scientific experts and methodologists; and Panel 6: Industry) regarding which are the most relevant aspects that should be taken as value dimensions to evaluate new medicines on a common value basis. The complete list of aspects (24 in total) and their respective description are listed in Table

1. As described above, these aspects were derived from analysis that took place in the earlier task of this WP.

Participants were asked to specify their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5-level scale ('Strongly Disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', 'Agree', 'Strongly Agree'), about the relevance of each of the 24 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. For each aspect, participants could always select the option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' and leave additional comments. For each aspect there was a brief description of their substantive meaning.

This Web-Delphi panel included a total of two rounds that took place between February 5th – February 15th and February 19th – March 1st, 2019, respectively. The overall Web-Delphi process was divided across six panels that ran in parallel, with each panel gathering participants' views from a specific stakeholder group. The aim of the first round was to collect the initial views of each participant of the panel regarding what is the relevance of the 24 aspects when evaluating new medicines on a common value basis (e.g. on a multidimensional value score basis). The aim of the second round was for the participants of each panel to access an anonymous summary of their panel's overall responses from the first round and have the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in terms of the inclusion or exclusions of the 24 aspects.

Following the two Web-Delphi rounds, a survey to participants collected comments on both the final results of their panel and the Web-Delphi process itself. Additionally, the panels of 'HTA bodies' and 'Patients and carers' were questioned about one of the aspects separately ('Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of a medicine's clinical trials') because it was not included in the Web-Delphi rounds. The survey took place between March 21st and April 1st, 2019. Following the Web-Delphi, a facilitated workshop was organized in April, with 11 participants representing all stakeholder groups for the purpose of reviewing and validating (for instance, interpreting, discussing and adjusting) the results of the Web-Delphi process.

Information regarding the number of participants in each panel for each round is shown in Table 2, and the aggregated voting final results for all Web-Delphi participants are shown in Table 3.

Following further research conducted by the WP7 team, a new stage will start soon as part of Task 2: all Web-Delphi participants (which previously had been divided into 6 separate stakeholder panels) will be invited to participate together in an overall web-Delphi to provide their final views about how

fundamental is to include each selected aspect in the novel framework. All participants will view the aspects' results from the first Web-Delphi and of the Decision Conferencing processes, for several of which no consensus was reached regarding their inclusion or exclusion in the novel framework, and will be invited to state their views regarding how fundamental each aspect is for the evaluation of drugs on a common basis. This Web-Delphi will be launched in September.

The next section of this report presents the results of the Payers and Policy Makers panel, summarising the results of the first and second rounds, together with the results of the survey including the comments received to the final results of the panel and to the Web-Delphi process.

Thank you again for your collaboration.

Table 1. List of aspects examined in the Web-Delphi and brief description.

Aspect	Description
Severity of the disease	The condition's/ indication's degree of seriousness in respect to mortality and morbidity-derived disability.
Unmet need of the disease	The availability of medical interventions for the indication of interest, which could relate to methods of diagnosis, prevention or treatment.
Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Number of cases of the disease at present or number of new cases that develop, e.g. prevalence of the disease (i.e. proportion of a population that have the disease at a point in time) or incidence of the disease (i.e. rate at which new disease cases occur in a population during a specified period).
Medicine's impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and complications.
Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.
Medicine's adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse outcomes occurring when a medicine is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.
Medicine's tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.
Medicine's contraindications of use	Any risk and safety factors that act as a reason for a medicine not to be used by a patient.
Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Potential risks associated with the use of the medicine in regards to specific patient sub-populations with particular characteristics.
Medicine's mechanism of action	The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).
Medicine's spill-over effects	R&D positive externalities (i.e. beneficial follow-on external effects) that can lead to the development of subsequent innovation or new indication in review or clinical development, e.g. new medicines or new indication approvals.
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.
Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Any risk reduction in transmitting and developing the disease under consideration or any other disease within the broader population.
Medicine's economic impact	Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.
Medicine's affordability	Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.
Medicine's efficiency	The medicine's value-for-money in terms of resource allocation, e.g. the additional cost needed to gain an extra unit of health outcome, i.e. Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants and personnel, detection bias due to ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.
Disease duration	The average length of time the disease is present, e.g. Chronic vs Incurable.
Disease age of onset	The average age at which an individual acquires, develops, or first experiences a condition or symptoms of a disease or disorder, e.g. children.
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity.
Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with cultural, political and stakeholder acceptability and participation, including any legal barriers.
Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Refers to whether the aim, i.e. targeted action of the medicine is preventive, symptomatic (relief) or curative.

Table 2. Number of participants per panel of stakeholder group, across each round of the Web-Delphi process and in the final survey.

Panel (Stakeholder group)	Invited	# participants (round 1)	# participants (round 2)	# participants (survey)
Healthcare professionals	30	25	21	10
Payers and policy-makers	20	18	18	11
HTA bodies	33	29	28	19
Scientific experts and methodologists	46	42	38	23
Patients and carers	26	22	19	13
Industry	40	31	29	14
Total	195	167	153	90

Table 3. Final voting results for all Web-Delphi participants (aggregated results from the 6 panels).

Aspect/ Level of agreement or disagreement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Total
1 - Severity of the disease	1%	3%	4%	24%	69%	0%	153
2 - Unmet need of the disease	1%	2%	3%	20%	72%	1%	153
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1%	11%	16%	42%	29%	0%	153
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	0%	0%	0%	18%	82%	0%	153
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	0%	0%	1%	22%	78%	0%	153
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	0%	0%	1%	22%	77%	0%	153
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	0%	1%	5%	39%	56%	0%	153
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0%	2%	7%	49%	42%	0%	153
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	1%	11%	20%	44%	24%	0%	153
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	0%	10%	27%	41%	22%	0%	153
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	4%	21%	39%	25%	11%	0%	153
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%	12%	29%	42%	12%	1%	153
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1%	5%	20%	52%	24%	0%	153
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0%	1%	7%	39%	54%	0%	153
15 - Medicine's economic impact	0%	5%	9%	35%	52%	0%	153
16 - Medicine's affordability	2%	6%	11%	39%	41%	1%	153
17 - Medicine's efficiency	1%	3%	3%	32%	61%	0%	153
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	0%	2%	10%	49%	39%	0%	106
19 - Disease duration	1%	10%	30%	45%	14%	1%	153

20 - Disease age of onset	1%	15%	30%	44%	10%	0%	153
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0%	5%	14%	54%	26%	1%	153
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1%	3%	19%	47%	30%	0%	153
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	8%	24%	36%	20%	7%	5%	153
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	2%	16%	24%	42%	16%	0%	153

2 Panel results: Payers and Policy Makers

2.1 Web-Delphi – first round versus second round results

2.1.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 4. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) regarding the relevance of each of the 24 proposed aspects at the end of the first round (n=18 participants) versus the end of the second round (n=18 participants). Note: D = Disagree, A = Agree

Aspect/ Level of agreement per round	Round 1 - Strongly D	Round 2 - Strongly D	Round 1 - D	Round 2 - D	Round 1 - Neither A nor D	Round 2 - Neither A nor D	Round 1 - A	Round 2 - A	Round 1 - Strongly A	Round 2 - Strongly A	Round 1 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Round 2 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer
1 - Severity of the disease							39%	28%	61%	72%		
2 - Unmet need of the disease					11%	11%	33%	28%	56%	61%		
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)			6%	6%	17%	17%	61%	61%	17%	17%		
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality							17%	17%	83%	83%		
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity							44%	33%	56%	67%		
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life					6%	6%	67%	72%	28%	22%		
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile					11%	11%	33%	33%	56%	56%		
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients					11%	11%	44%	44%	44%	44%		
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	6%		6%	6%	11%	17%	61%	67%	17%	11%		
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	6%				22%	28%	56%	56%	17%	17%		
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	6%				67%	78%	22%	17%	6%	6%		
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	11%	11%	11%	11%	39%	39%	28%	28%	11%	11%		
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients			11%	11%	6%	6%	72%	72%	11%	11%		

14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community					17%	11%	33%	28%	50%	61%		
15 - Medicine's economic impact			6%	6%			33%	22%	61%	72%		
16 - Medicine's affordability					11%	11%	33%	33%	56%	56%		
17 - Medicine's efficiency							17%	17%	83%	83%		
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials					11%	11%	56%	61%	33%	28%		
19 - Disease duration	6%		11%	11%	22%	28%	44%	44%	17%	17%		
20 - Disease age of onset	6%		17%	22%	11%	11%	56%	56%	11%	11%		
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care			6%	6%	11%	6%	50%	61%	33%	28%		
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues					33%	33%	33%	33%	33%	33%		
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	11%	11%	17%	17%	39%	39%	17%	17%	6%	6%	11%	11%
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning			17%	17%	6%		50%	61%	28%	22%		

2.1.2 Participants' comments first round

Aspect 6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It depends on the budget allocation for medicines and for diseases, i.e. if we will talk about high level country-usually it is taken into account, but for middle and low income country this endpoint is neglect.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To decide about the added value of a new medicine the impact on mortality, morbidity and quality of life are taken into account. However, in practice, quality of life is almost never a primary endpoint in the clinical studies and hard to measure.

Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It has to be used when its calculate eligible population (patients).
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should be considered by clinicians.

Aspect 10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It should be considered by clinicians.
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Aspect 11 - Medicine's mechanism of action

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This endpoint has to be listed, but not more because than we have a double evaluation at the marketing authorization level and HTA level. • A new mechanism of action on its own is not an argument for a positive evaluation. However, in case of, for example, anti-epileptics a new mechanism of action for a medicine with an efficacy comparable to other anti-epileptics can be an argument for a positive evaluation as the subgroup of patients being helped with the new medicine may differ from the other anti-epileptics. On the other hand two anti-epileptics with the same mechanism of action may be considered as "me-too" drugs.
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Aspect 14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

Strongly agree	• Infectious diseases and pathological behaviors.
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Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Strongly agree	• Some medicines have an unparalleled high budget impact, and the resources available to the country are not always sufficient.
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Aspect 18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

Agree	• Depend on each type of product we have i.e. if we talk about a conditional marketing authorization this endpoint have to be take into consideration.
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Aspect 20 - Disease age of onset

Agree	• Medication for younger should be more valuable.
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Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

Don't know/Don't want to answer	• Please make more clear what this criterion really means (what are the practical consequences)? • I did not understand the question.
---------------------------------	--

2.1.3 Participants' comments second round

Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

Strongly agree	• Rarity is especially relevant for pharmacoeconomic evaluation.
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Aspect 4 - Medicine's impact on mortality

Strongly agree	• Probably the most relevant. In the long-run, this is the less controversial dimension.
----------------	--

Aspect 6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

Strongly agree	• Quality of life should weigh more than life expectancy (cfr Belgian KCE report on MCDA).
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Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Neither agree nor disagree	• This is definitely part of the BR assessment.
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Aspect 8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients

Neither agree nor disagree	• Part of BR balance.
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Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Strongly disagree	• I maintain my point and this shall definitely not be taken into account.
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Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Neither agree nor disagree	• Affordability depends on the price and deciders shall be able to make the product eventually affordable when it is not initially.
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Aspect 17 - Medicine's efficiency

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Only on a comparative basis, when looked in perspective with other similar therapeutics.
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Aspect 20 – Disease age of onset

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• The younger the patient the more QALYs he/she can gain.
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2.2 Survey – comments to the final results of the panel

• There may need to clarify from which perspective we are looking at the questions: an HTA agency preparing an assessment? A payer preparing an appraisal? The political decision maker? The weights of some criteria may change depending on the standpoint.

2.3 Survey – comments about the Web-Delphi process

• Easy to use, but a real in-depth discussion and nuances are not possible.
• It's interesting to see the opinion of other colleagues about the field we're working and notice that our thoughts are very aligned. It was great to take part in this survey, thanks for the opportunity.

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2: Report with results from the Web-Delphi process of the Industry panel to identify which value dimensions should be considered in the “New multicriteria framework to facilitate Health Technology Assessment (HTA) organisations in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”

Grant Agreement No.:779312

Work Package: WP7, Task 2

Prepared by: IST (Universidade de Lisboa) and London School of Economics

Date: 29 August 2019

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1 Background information

IMPACT HTA is a research project looking at new and improved methods across 10 thematic research areas aiming at understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, and integrating clinical and economic data from different sources to improve methods in economic evaluation in the context of HTA and health system performance measurement.

Within IMPACT HTA work package 7 (WP7) research is taking place towards the development and testing of a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new medicines. This fits into the second task of WP7, whose aim is twofold: first, to structure a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, with these models reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers; and, second, to define alternative techniques and questioning protocols to build such a model. The starting point of Task 2 in terms of potential aspects of performance feeds from the results of Task 1 of the WP which has econometrically analysed the determinants of HTA recommendations by relying on secondary data. Following the completion of Task 2, the methodological framework will then be tested in practice through a number of case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies that will be carried out within Task 3 of WP7.

In order to build such a framework, two questions are currently being answered within Task 2: First, which aspects should be considered in a novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis? And second, which of those aspects are fundamental for that evaluation?

In order to address the first question, you kindly participated in a Web-Delphi process. The objective of this report is to provide you with an overview of the aggregated Web-Delphi results for all panels, and also more detailed results for your own stakeholder panel (Industry).

Regarding the general features of the already developed Web-Delphi process, the views of a mix of a large and diverse number of stakeholders were collected in separate panels (Panel 1: Payers and policy-makers; Panel 2: HTA bodies; Panel 3: Health care professionals; Panel 4: Patients and carers; Panel 5: Scientific experts and methodologists; and Panel 6: Industry) regarding which are the most relevant aspects that should be taken as value dimensions to evaluate new medicines on a common value basis. The complete list of aspects (24 in total) and their respective description are listed in Table

1. As described above, these aspects were derived from analysis that took place in the earlier task of this WP.

Participants were asked to specify their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5-level scale ('Strongly Disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', 'Agree', 'Strongly Agree'), about the relevance of each of the 24 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. For each aspect, participants could always select the option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' and leave additional comments. For each aspect there was a brief description of their substantive meaning.

This Web-Delphi panel included a total of two rounds that took place between February 5th – February 15th and February 19th – March 1st, 2019, respectively. The overall Web-Delphi process was divided across six panels that ran in parallel, with each panel gathering participants' views from a specific stakeholder group. The aim of the first round was to collect the initial views of each participant of the panel regarding what is the relevance of the 24 aspects when evaluating new medicines on a common value basis (e.g. on a multidimensional value score basis). The aim of the second round was for the participants of each panel to access an anonymous summary of their panel's overall responses from the first round and have the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in terms of the inclusion or exclusions of the 24 aspects.

Following the two Web-Delphi rounds, a survey to participants collected comments on both the final results of their panel and the Web-Delphi process itself. Additionally, the panels of 'HTA bodies' and 'Patients and carers' were questioned about one of the aspects separately ('Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of a medicine's clinical trials') because it was not included in the Web-Delphi rounds. The survey took place between March 21st and April 1st, 2019. Following the Web-Delphi, a facilitated workshop was organized in April, with 11 participants representing all stakeholder groups for the purpose of reviewing and validating (for instance, interpreting, discussing and adjusting) the results of the Web-Delphi process.

Information regarding the number of participants in each panel for each round is shown in Table 2, and the aggregated voting final results for all Web-Delphi participants are shown in Table 3.

Following further research conducted by the WP7 team, a new stage will start soon as part of Task 2: all Web-Delphi participants (which previously had been divided into 6 separate stakeholder panels) will be invited to participate together in an overall web-Delphi to provide their final views about how

fundamental is to include each selected aspect in the novel framework. All participants will view the aspects' results from the first Web-Delphi and of the Decision Conferencing processes, for several of which no consensus was reached regarding their inclusion or exclusion in the novel framework, and will be invited to state their views regarding how fundamental each aspect is for the evaluation of drugs on a common basis. This Web-Delphi will be launched in September.

The next section of this report presents the results of the Industry panel, summarising the results of the first and second rounds, together with the results of the survey including the comments received to the final results of the panel and to the Web-Delphi process.

Thank you again for your collaboration.

Table 1. List of aspects examined in the Web-Delphi and brief description.

Aspect	Description
Severity of the disease	The condition's/ indication's degree of seriousness in respect to mortality and morbidity-derived disability.
Unmet need of the disease	The availability of medical interventions for the indication of interest, which could relate to methods of diagnosis, prevention or treatment.
Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Number of cases of the disease at present or number of new cases that develop, e.g. prevalence of the disease (i.e. proportion of a population that have the disease at a point in time) or incidence of the disease (i.e. rate at which new disease cases occur in a population during a specified period).
Medicine's impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and complications.
Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.
Medicine's adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse outcomes occurring when a medicine is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.
Medicine's tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.
Medicine's contraindications of use	Any risk and safety factors that act as a reason for a medicine not to be used by a patient.
Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Potential risks associated with the use of the medicine in regards to specific patient sub-populations with particular characteristics.
Medicine's mechanism of action	The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).
Medicine's spill-over effects	R&D positive externalities (i.e. beneficial follow-on external effects) that can lead to the development of subsequent innovation or new indication in review or clinical development, e.g. new medicines or new indication approvals.
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.
Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Any risk reduction in transmitting and developing the disease under consideration or any other disease within the broader population.
Medicine's economic impact	Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.
Medicine's affordability	Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.
Medicine's efficiency	The medicine's value-for-money in terms of resource allocation, e.g. the additional cost needed to gain an extra unit of health outcome, i.e. Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants and personnel, detection bias due to ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.
Disease duration	The average length of time the disease is present, e.g. Chronic vs Incurable.
Disease age of onset	The average age at which an individual acquires, develops, or first experiences a condition or symptoms of a disease or disorder, e.g. children.
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity.
Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with cultural, political and stakeholder acceptability and participation, including any legal barriers.
Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Refers to whether the aim, i.e. targeted action of the medicine is preventive, symptomatic (relief) or curative.

Table 2. Number of participants per panel of stakeholder group, across each round of the Web-Delphi process and in the final survey.

Panel (Stakeholder group)	Invited	# participants (round 1)	# participants (round 2)	# participants (survey)
Healthcare professionals	30	25	21	10
Payers and policy-makers	20	18	18	11
HTA bodies	33	29	28	19
Scientific experts and methodologists	46	42	38	23
Patients and carers	26	22	19	13
Industry	40	31	29	14
Total	195	167	153	90

Table 3. Final voting results for all Web-Delphi participants (aggregated results from the 6 panels).

Aspect/ Level of agreement or disagreement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Total
1 - Severity of the disease	1%	3%	4%	24%	69%	0%	153
2 - Unmet need of the disease	1%	2%	3%	20%	72%	1%	153
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1%	11%	16%	42%	29%	0%	153
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	0%	0%	0%	18%	82%	0%	153
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	0%	0%	1%	22%	78%	0%	153
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	0%	0%	1%	22%	77%	0%	153
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	0%	1%	5%	39%	56%	0%	153
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0%	2%	7%	49%	42%	0%	153
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	1%	11%	20%	44%	24%	0%	153
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	0%	10%	27%	41%	22%	0%	153
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	4%	21%	39%	25%	11%	0%	153
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%	12%	29%	42%	12%	1%	153
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1%	5%	20%	52%	24%	0%	153
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0%	1%	7%	39%	54%	0%	153
15 - Medicine's economic impact	0%	5%	9%	35%	52%	0%	153
16 - Medicine's affordability	2%	6%	11%	39%	41%	1%	153
17 - Medicine's efficiency	1%	3%	3%	32%	61%	0%	153
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	0%	2%	10%	49%	39%	0%	106
19 - Disease duration	1%	10%	30%	45%	14%	1%	153

20 - Disease age of onset	1%	15%	30%	44%	10%	0%	153
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0%	5%	14%	54%	26%	1%	153
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1%	3%	19%	47%	30%	0%	153
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	8%	24%	36%	20%	7%	5%	153
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	2%	16%	24%	42%	16%	0%	153

2 Panel results: Industry

2.1 Web-Delphi – first round versus second round results

2.1.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 4. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) regarding the relevance of each of the 24 proposed aspects at the end of the first round (n=31 participants) versus the end of the second round (n=29 participants). Note: D = Disagree, A = Agree

Aspect/ Level of agreement per round	Round 1 - Strongly D	Round 2 - Strongly D	Round 1 - D	Round 2 - D	Round 1 - Neither A nor D	Round 2 - Neither A nor D	Round 1 - A	Round 2 - A	Round 1 - Strongly A	Round 2 - Strongly A	Round 1 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Round 2 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer
1 - Severity of the disease					6%	3%	23%	28%	71%	69%		
2 - Unmet need of the disease							13%	10%	87%	90%		
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)			10%	10%	19%	21%	39%	41%	32%	28%		
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality							16%	17%	84%	83%		
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity							26%	24%	74%	76%		
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life							23%	7%	77%	93%		
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile					10%	7%	48%	52%	42%	41%		
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients			3%		10%	10%	58%	62%	29%	28%		
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	3%		19%	21%	26%	31%	35%	34%	16%	14%		
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions			19%	21%	32%	34%	32%	31%	16%	14%		
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	6%	7%	26%	28%	35%	31%	29%	31%	3%	3%		
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	3%	3%		3%	39%	38%	39%	41%	13%	14%	6%	
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients					35%	31%	35%	41%	29%	28%		

14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community			3%	3%	3%		29%	31%	65%	66%		
15 - Medicine's economic impact					10%	7%	45%	48%	45%	45%		
16 - Medicine's affordability	3%	3%	13%	14%	26%	24%	32%	34%	26%	24%		
17 - Medicine's efficiency	3%	3%	6%	7%			52%	55%	39%	34%		
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials			3%		26%	21%	52%	62%	19%	17%		
19 - Disease duration			13%	14%	26%	24%	45%	48%	16%	14%		
20 - Disease age of onset	3%	3%	29%	28%	29%	34%	29%	28%	10%	7%		
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care			6%	3%	13%	14%	58%	59%	23%	24%		
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues			10%	7%	19%	21%	52%	55%	19%	17%		
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	6%	7%	19%	17%	26%	31%	26%	28%	16%	10%	6%	7%
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	3%		6%	10%	19%	17%	52%	55%	16%	17%	3%	

2.1.2 Participants' comments first round

Aspect 1 - Severity of the disease

Neither agree or disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To me, what matters most is not the severity of the disease but the residual unmet needs with current treatments.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> While the severity of the disease is very important and would deserve a STRONGLY AGREE, member states should be explicit concerning their disease priorities and their willingness to focus funding for the prioritized diseases (funding across healthcare not just pharmaceuticals).
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Although obviously very subjective.

Aspect 2 - Unmet need of the disease

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unmet need should consider the ability of the healthcare system at large to leverage pharmacological interventions to their full potential: while a disease may be regarded as low unmet need if managed with best expertise in a controlled environment, the challenges of optimizing the patient pathway in real life may actually argue for a higher unmet need.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unmet need should be first described vis a vis mortality and morbidity indicators. patient reported outcomes could qualify but system related factors and some patient lifestyle related factors should not by themselves account for unmet medical need. Unmet need should not be defined solely by presence or absence of medical interventions. Potential shortcomings of available interventions should also be considered in this aspect. Residual unmet need very important. Criteria of unmet needs have to be clearly stated, most of the time no alignment exist between regulators, HTA agencies, clinicians and patients.

Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unmet need will take this into account.
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Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A rare disease with a limited unmet need may benefit from an incentive for innovation but this upside should not have the same order of magnitude than the unmet need/severity of the diseases factors. However, a rare disease with very poor prognosis should benefit from a "rare disease bonus". One could envision a multiplying factor for other factors.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indirectly only. If a disease is very rare, the sales potential might not be high enough to justify R&D
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to adjust to time of expected marketing authorization, taking into consideration new (companion) diagnostic tools. • Rarity should be rewarded and not penalized; concept of fairness, all patients should have access to treatments not just those in high prevalence areas.

Aspect 5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This should be captured in health-related QoL.
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Aspect 6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quality of life measures need to be broader than standard questionnaires. Value of hope or peace of mind is not captured today for cell and gene potentially curative. Also QoL impacts for the family and care givers needs to be captured.
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Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considered less important to benefits, as the regulators have already assessed a positive relationship between efficacy and risk. So understanding AE's is important, but less so than benefits.
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Aspect 8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is critical for adherence to Treatment and Treatment performance in real life: it is difficult to assess the impact on compliance in RCTs (other than through drop outs). Predictive methods of tolerability impact on compliance should be (further) developed and taken into consideration.
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Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assessment should be done in the eligible population.
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Aspect 11 - Medicine's mechanism of action

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While a new mechanism of action should not necessarily imply overrating a new Treatment (impact on mortality, morbidity and QoL will capture the clinical relevance of a new MoA) there should not be a prejudice against an existing MoA: again what matters is the clinical impact.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only if the by mechanism of action we are trying to reward innovation. • This needs to be linked to level of innovation. • Mechanism of action is of interest as far as it can be translated into added therapeutic value, better or similar efficacy, lesser or similar side effect. Alone, it has no interest.

Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Don't know/Don't want to answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I do not understand what Spill over means. • Not sure what 'spill over effects' is intended to mean.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Issue is the practicality of the measure. How can we measure it and will future drugs have to be penalized because previous drugs paved the way in science?
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should be captured under a category "degree of innovation".

Aspect 13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When used within a value framework, ease of use would need to be demonstrated through RWD/RWE. As adequate RWE would be available post-approval, conditional/adaptive valuation schemes should be in place. • Only if linked to better outcomes e.g. in adherence.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The impact on adherence to Treatment will be underestimated in RCTs. This dimension has traditionally been neglected by HTA. Predictive methods on adherence to Treatment should be developed. • It may be translated in a better compliance / adherence leading then to better efficacy / effectiveness

Aspect 14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unless we talk about vaccines and AMR drugs, the majority are non communicable disease drugs so this criterion would not apply.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is particularly important as current approaches fail to capture. Very important for some specific technologies as vaccines and other medicines. Public health priorities at national level could differ from one country/ region to another and it should be taken into account

Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Productivity loss is a double-edged sword depending on how it is defined. If defined in a narrow sense (caused by inability to be in paid employment) it automatically disadvantages young and older people. This would need to be addressed before adding productivity gains or losses into an assessment.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are many ways and tools to measure econ impact. this should not be rigid and include wider societal benefits. Very important but flexibility in the methods is mandatory to take into account specificities as OMPs, vaccines, curative treatment...

Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affordability to whom? over what time course? savings / value can accrue over many years. short term / siloed budgeting is often a barrier because affordability is so acute.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The evaluation should be based on science. Affordability is a value judgement/political decision based on how much someone wants the benefits identified through the evaluation.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In most developed countries the issue is not affordability but willingness to pay. If a medicine has been determined as cost-effective by the relevant assessment process, affordability should not come into the equation even though I recognize that there may need to be a 'willingness to pay' discussion following HTA approval. Budget impact and value for money considerations should be separate.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Budget impact assessment should also include indirect economic benefits. Potential schemes for value transfer towards health system would need to be considered. In case budget impact is strictly limited to direct costs and healthcare budget, evaluation with this aspect may potentially hinder new medicines with indirect economic benefits.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Of course affordability is a key dimension: however, guidance on willingness to invest that are in line with prioritization of diseases from a public health policy perspective should be made explicit. It is the

	<p>prerogative of member states to state their health policy and to set incentives that are aligned with These policies but once These are made explicit then funding decisions need to be consistent with These incentives: this is the best way to incentivize industry to select R&D Projects that are aligned with public policy in the long term.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Account for outcomes based agreements in the evaluation. • HTA agencies are not all involved in pricing / budget decision.
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Aspect 17 - Medicine's efficiency

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends what the metric for 'health' is. if QALY, then I would disagree with this question.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be mindful of not splitting economic impact criteria into many eco related criteria as this gives more weight than a singly one. Economic impact and affordability could be 2 distinct criteria. under economic impact include CE and budget impact. • Efficiency is to be measured in current practice or real life setting which is most of the time not the case at time of launch. Real world evidence combined with RCTs will help on it.

Aspect 18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It depends on the context, i.e. more flexibility in assessing uncertainty and biases is needed for therapeutic areas that face inherent challenges in the clinical trial design but not for others. • A more general aspect such as data/evidence quality may be considered.
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Aspect 19 - Disease duration

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unmet need will take this into account.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duration should only be included if it is linked to severity. In itself duration is not necessarily a good indicator of the impact of a disease on a patient. If you have light asthma and need to take an preventive inhaler for the rest of your life you may prefer not to have to do so but if the symptoms are well controlled and there are no side effects then there may not be a need for a new medicine unless it can cure the condition. I think this element requires some further exploration. • Depends how you factor that in to ensure equity to society.

Aspect 20 - Disease age of onset

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unmet need will take this into account.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This element also requires further discussion. It depends on what the thinking is behind it. Could this lead to a medicine not being made available if the average age of onset is high (e.g. 70+). That would be inappropriate as biological age should be the determinant for treatment decision, not chronological age. Or is age of onset linked to duration and therefore severity? This one requires more parameters. • This is a criterion that need to be decided by society at large. As industry representatives we all have our own values, but we can only make decisions that respond to incentives defined by society. HTA methods should be grounded on a robust debate that reflect societal preferences and make them explicit. In fact, this comment extends to many other criteria but is best suited for age of onset.

Aspect 21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance of a pharmacological intervention is as good as its practical implementation by the healthcare system at large. So the value of a new intervention that minimizes the need for complex interactions between the different actors of the system to deliver clinical performance should be reflected in the Overall evaluation. This is becoming even more important for the assessment of therapies that can potentially cure a disease.
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Aspect 22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is a criterion that need to be decided by society at large. As industry representatives we all have our own values, but we can only make decisions that respond to incentives defined by society. HTA methods should be grounded on a robust debate that reflect societal preferences and make them explicit.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This may depend on the country.

Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

Don't know/Don't want to answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The description is too condensed. More information is required to understand the potential impact of including this parameter.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's difficult to imagine what would fall into this category that wouldn't be captured under the other categories, so difficult to answer this question.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • That's a political implementation question, not a scientific evaluation question.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While it is the prerogative of societies to state those goals, it is their duty to be consequent and value new Treatment options that are delivering on These explicit goals.

Aspect 24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning

Don't know/Don't want to answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While it might make sense to give additional weight to preventative or curative treatments, a patient who does not have any treatment options will value symptomatic relief as well. The current QALY approach would in any case reflect the QALY gains from a curative treatment. This element would also benefit from further exploration.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methodology should try to avoid the current biases against prevention. • We should aim for cures rather than chronic treatments for which patients may not be compliant. For the same potential health gain, a premium should be paid for cures over a lifetime.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development programs are global and need to cater for the Needs of multiple jurisdictions. So the possibility to assess an intervention in line with a particular positioning is very important to customize value to the specific goals of a particular country. • Vaccines and cures should be favored. • Disease modifier, game changer has to be clearly stated.

2.1.3 Participants' comments second round

Aspect 2 - Unmet need of the disease

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unmet need should be considered jointly with severity of diseases. Unmet need per se, is less clear to me as a unique criteria.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Suggest to use rather: "residual unmet medical need"

Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Already assessed by regulator. Patient impact should be captured by PROs
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Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I'm assuming that the medicine should be used as per label which will rule out contraindications (medics should also do the same)
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Aspect 11 - Medicine's mechanism of action

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This criteria should probably be combined with Spill overf effects as it basically argues for a specific incentive for innovative technologies BEYOND what they deliver in the specific indication for which that innovation has been studied. <p>However in the end the incentive for industry intrinsically reside in being first to market with a new MoA that will contribute to product Differentiation. In the end it is probably more important that healthcare Systems provide explicit incentive for innovation that are aligned with benefits to patients according to their societal value framework and that HCS are being consequent in translating that value in line with the stated incentive when an innovation meets the stated goals.</p>
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Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of this criteria would not be practical
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Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On further reflection of this question, I'm not sure that HTA should evaluate affordability. Affordability is a separate issue to HTA and decided by others. It is a political decision.
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Aspect 17 - Medicine's efficiency

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On further reflection of this question, I'm not sure that HTA should evaluate either affordability or even cost-effectiveness. The key purpose of HTA should be to quantify the overall benefit and cost consequence (where a country requires it). Affordability and value for money thresholds are a separate issue to HTA and decided by others. <p>In cost-effectiveness markets, the system becomes biased as manufacturers try to achieve a premium price and academic groups / payers use it to achieve the greatest discount (some ERGs/HTA groups can quite clearly be seen to choose the most pessimistic assumptions when they have no empirical basis nor clinical validity). Using economic modelling to predict overall benefit (be that effectiveness or QALYs) and calculate possible cost impact (excluding new drug price) should be the role of HTA. This would focus manufacturers and academics on what is the right benefit rather than gaming the system. Price negotiation is then based on this benefit plus other relevant factors that may not be captured within HTA (e.g. severity, unmet need etc...).</p> <p>In a sense, if you can use an assessment vs negotiation approach as in Germany, with the advanced techniques of CEA bodies (e.g. taking into account other evidence and methods to address uncertainty, such as extrapolation) you can take affordability / value for money out of the equation for HTA.</p>
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Aspect 20 - Disease age of onset

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age of onset is factored in cost/QALY, life years gained (lost) if there is significant morbidity/mortality consequence. Otherwise it does not matter. Also, question doesn't indicate whether the Delphi panel prefers treatments for older people or children, just that 'age of onset' is a factor.
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Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is a slippery slope. It means that diseases with less political priority or ‘patient power’ and voice will suffer vs others which have more political muscle. See breast cancer vs good examples. Or rare diseases with very few advocates. The assessment process should be decoupled from political interventions. • This has no relevance to value and influence in this domain can result in decisions that are not aligned to social preferences.
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2.2 Survey – comments to the final results of the panel

- What is the importance of the disease as a country health problem? Disease areas with high burden should get priority and expedited processes. The same applies to priority disease areas as part of national health strategy.
- We should check the other aspects of value that are described in the ISPOR taskforce value flower, eg value of hope (i.e. heterogeneity of treatment outcomes with some patients potentially having a large benefit that is not sufficiently represented by the median or mean benefit) and option value (i.e. keeping patients alive for longer so that they have the chance to receive better treatment options (e.g. bone marrow transplant or access to future technologies).
- I am wondering whether the process could allow for a rephrasing of some of the criteria or addition of explanations where participants have found it difficult to understand the criterion. I certainly struggled with some of them.
- Might we worth considering new therapeutic platforms such as CAR T in light of potential to stimulate greater long-term advances in treatment with reduced costs over time.
- Suggestion to cluster criteria and respective sub-criteria, in order to organise the most important dimensions and subitems related. For patients’ perspective, for example patient convenience and QoL, inclusion of simplified and qualitative methods a need.

2.3 Survey – comments about the Web-Delphi process

- Very convenient handy and useful process. Thanks for letting me be part of this.
- It would be very helpful if you could provide slides with the results of each round. It would be helpful to have more time for responding in each round and also visibility of the next consultation process, i.e. what to expect. Thank you.
- I thought it was a good process. Would benefit from being easier to see comments as the rounds progress. Some of the descriptions and comments changed my rating in round 2.
- Very simple and user friendly.
- Looks like an efficient process, I would have appreciated a more detailed definition of the different dimensions of value.
- This was an interesting experience that I would be happy to participate in again in the future.

- The process was clear and transparent. Please let us know about next steps, publication and application. Thank you.

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2: Report with results from the Web-Delphi process of the Patients and Carers panel to identify which value dimensions should be considered in the “New multicriteria framework to facilitate Health Technology Assessment (HTA) organisations in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”

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Work Package: WP7, Task 2

Prepared by: IST (Universidade de Lisboa) and London School of Economics

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1 Background information

IMPACT HTA is a research project looking at new and improved methods across 10 thematic research areas aiming at understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, and integrating clinical and economic data from different sources to improve methods in economic evaluation in the context of HTA and health system performance measurement.

Within IMPACT HTA work package 7 (WP7) research is taking place towards the development and testing of a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new medicines. This fits into the second task of WP7, whose aim is twofold: first, to structure a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, with these models reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers; and, second, to define alternative techniques and questioning protocols to build such a model. The starting point of Task 2 in terms of potential aspects of performance feeds from the results of Task 1 of the WP which has econometrically analysed the determinants of HTA recommendations by relying on secondary data. Following the completion of Task 2, the methodological framework will then be tested in practice through a number of case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies that will be carried out within Task 3 of WP7.

In order to build such a framework, two questions are currently being answered within Task 2: First, which aspects should be considered in a novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis? And second, which of those aspects are fundamental for that evaluation?

In order to address the first question, you kindly participated in a Web-Delphi process. The objective of this report is to provide you with an overview of the aggregated Web-Delphi results for all panels, and also more detailed results for your own stakeholder panel (Patients and Carers).

Regarding the general features of the already developed Web-Delphi process, the views of a mix of a large and diverse number of stakeholders were collected in separate panels (Panel 1: Payers and policy-makers; Panel 2: HTA bodies; Panel 3: Health care professionals; Panel 4: Patients and carers; Panel 5: Scientific experts and methodologists; and Panel 6: Industry) regarding which are the most relevant aspects that should be taken as value dimensions to evaluate new medicines on a common value basis. The complete list of aspects (24 in total) and their respective description are listed in Table

1. As described above, these aspects were derived from analysis that took place in the earlier task of this WP.

Participants were asked to specify their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5-level scale ('Strongly Disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', 'Agree', 'Strongly Agree'), about the relevance of each of the 24 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. For each aspect, participants could always select the option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' and leave additional comments. For each aspect there was a brief description of their substantive meaning.

This Web-Delphi panel included a total of two rounds that took place between February 5th – February 15th and February 19th – March 1st, 2019, respectively. The overall Web-Delphi process was divided across six panels that ran in parallel, with each panel gathering participants' views from a specific stakeholder group. The aim of the first round was to collect the initial views of each participant of the panel regarding what is the relevance of the 24 aspects when evaluating new medicines on a common value basis (e.g. on a multidimensional value score basis). The aim of the second round was for the participants of each panel to access an anonymous summary of their panel's overall responses from the first round and have the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in terms of the inclusion or exclusions of the 24 aspects.

Following the two Web-Delphi rounds, a survey to participants collected comments on both the final results of their panel and the Web-Delphi process itself. Additionally, the panels of 'HTA bodies' and 'Patients and carers' were questioned about one of the aspects separately ('Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of a medicine's clinical trials') because it was not included in the Web-Delphi rounds. The survey took place between March 21st and April 1st, 2019. Following the Web-Delphi, a facilitated workshop was organized in April, with 11 participants representing all stakeholder groups for the purpose of reviewing and validating (for instance, interpreting, discussing and adjusting) the results of the Web-Delphi process.

Information regarding the number of participants in each panel for each round is shown in Table 2, and the aggregated voting final results for all Web-Delphi participants are shown in Table 3.

Following further research conducted by the WP7 team, a new stage will start soon as part of Task 2: all Web-Delphi participants (which previously had been divided into 6 separate stakeholder panels) will be invited to participate together in an overall web-Delphi to provide their final views about how

fundamental is to include each selected aspect in the novel framework. All participants will view the aspects' results from the first Web-Delphi and of the Decision Conferencing processes, for several of which no consensus was reached regarding their inclusion or exclusion in the novel framework, and will be invited to state their views regarding how fundamental each aspect is for the evaluation of drugs on a common basis. This Web-Delphi will be launched in September.

The next section of this report presents the results of the Patients and Carers panel, summarising the results of the first and second rounds, together with the results of the survey including the comments received to the final results of the panel and to the Web-Delphi process.

Thank you again for your collaboration.

Table 1. List of aspects examined in the Web-Delphi and brief description.

Aspect	Description
Severity of the disease	The condition's/ indication's degree of seriousness in respect to mortality and morbidity-derived disability.
Unmet need of the disease	The availability of medical interventions for the indication of interest, which could relate to methods of diagnosis, prevention or treatment.
Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Number of cases of the disease at present or number of new cases that develop, e.g. prevalence of the disease (i.e. proportion of a population that have the disease at a point in time) or incidence of the disease (i.e. rate at which new disease cases occur in a population during a specified period).
Medicine's impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and complications.
Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.
Medicine's adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse outcomes occurring when a medicine is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.
Medicine's tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.
Medicine's contraindications of use	Any risk and safety factors that act as a reason for a medicine not to be used by a patient.
Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Potential risks associated with the use of the medicine in regards to specific patient sub-populations with particular characteristics.
Medicine's mechanism of action	The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).
Medicine's spill-over effects	R&D positive externalities (i.e. beneficial follow-on external effects) that can lead to the development of subsequent innovation or new indication in review or clinical development, e.g. new medicines or new indication approvals.
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.
Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Any risk reduction in transmitting and developing the disease under consideration or any other disease within the broader population.
Medicine's economic impact	Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.
Medicine's affordability	Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.
Medicine's efficiency	The medicine's value-for-money in terms of resource allocation, e.g. the additional cost needed to gain an extra unit of health outcome, i.e. Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants and personnel, detection bias due to ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.
Disease duration	The average length of time the disease is present, e.g. Chronic vs Incurable.
Disease age of onset	The average age at which an individual acquires, develops, or first experiences a condition or symptoms of a disease or disorder, e.g. children.
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity.
Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with cultural, political and stakeholder acceptability and participation, including any legal barriers.
Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Refers to whether the aim, i.e. targeted action of the medicine is preventive, symptomatic (relief) or curative.

Table 2. Number of participants per panel of stakeholder group, across each round of the Web-Delphi process and in the final survey.

Panel (Stakeholder group)	Invited	# participants (round 1)	# participants (round 2)	# participants (survey)
Healthcare professionals	30	25	21	10
Payers and policy-makers	20	18	18	11
HTA bodies	33	29	28	19
Scientific experts and methodologists	46	42	38	23
Patients and carers	26	22	19	13
Industry	40	31	29	14
Total	195	167	153	90

Table 3. Final voting results for all Web-Delphi participants (aggregated results from the 6 panels).

Aspect/ Level of agreement or disagreement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Total
1 - Severity of the disease	1%	3%	4%	24%	69%	0%	153
2 - Unmet need of the disease	1%	2%	3%	20%	72%	1%	153
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1%	11%	16%	42%	29%	0%	153
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	0%	0%	0%	18%	82%	0%	153
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	0%	0%	1%	22%	78%	0%	153
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	0%	0%	1%	22%	77%	0%	153
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	0%	1%	5%	39%	56%	0%	153
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0%	2%	7%	49%	42%	0%	153
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	1%	11%	20%	44%	24%	0%	153
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	0%	10%	27%	41%	22%	0%	153
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	4%	21%	39%	25%	11%	0%	153
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%	12%	29%	42%	12%	1%	153
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1%	5%	20%	52%	24%	0%	153
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0%	1%	7%	39%	54%	0%	153
15 - Medicine's economic impact	0%	5%	9%	35%	52%	0%	153
16 - Medicine's affordability	2%	6%	11%	39%	41%	1%	153
17 - Medicine's efficiency	1%	3%	3%	32%	61%	0%	153
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	0%	2%	10%	49%	39%	0%	106
19 - Disease duration	1%	10%	30%	45%	14%	1%	153

20 - Disease age of onset	1%	15%	30%	44%	10%	0%	153
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0%	5%	14%	54%	26%	1%	153
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1%	3%	19%	47%	30%	0%	153
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	8%	24%	36%	20%	7%	5%	153
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	2%	16%	24%	42%	16%	0%	153

2 Panel results: Patients and Carers

2.1 Web-Delphi – first round versus second round results

2.1.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 4. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) regarding the relevance of each of the 23 proposed aspects at the end of the first round (n=22 participants) versus the end of the second round (n=19 participants). Note: D = Disagree, A = Agree

Aspect/ Level of agreement per round	Round 1 - Strongly D	Round 2 - Strongly D	Round 1 - D	Round 2 - D	Round 1 - Neither A nor D	Round 2 - Neither A nor D	Round 1 - A	Round 2 - A	Round 1 - Strongly A	Round 2 - Strongly A	Round 1 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Round 2 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer
1 - Severity of the disease	5%				9%	11%	23%	16%	64%	74%		
2 - Unmet need of the disease	5%						14%	5%	82%	95%		
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	9%	5%			18%	16%	27%	37%	45%	42%		
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	5%		5%				14%	16%	77%	84%		
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	5%		5%				14%	11%	77%	89%		
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	5%		5%				14%	11%	77%	89%		
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	5%				5%	5%	27%	26%	64%	68%		
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	5%						32%	37%	64%	63%		
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	5%				5%	5%	36%	42%	55%	53%		
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	5%				18%	21%	36%	32%	41%	47%		
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	5%		9%	5%	23%	26%	41%	47%	23%	21%		
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%		14%	11%	23%	26%	32%	42%	18%	16%	9%	5%
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	5%				18%	21%	36%	32%	41%	47%		

14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	5%				14%	11%	36%	37%	45%	53%		
15 - Medicine's economic impact			18%	16%	18%	21%	27%	32%	36%	32%		
16 - Medicine's affordability	9%	5%	5%		9%	11%	55%	63%	18%	16%	5%	5%
17 - Medicine's efficiency	9%	5%	5%	5%			27%	32%	55%	58%	5%	
18 - Disease duration	5%		14%	11%	27%	26%	32%	42%	18%	16%	5%	5%
19 - Disease age of onset	5%		14%	16%	36%	47%	36%	26%	9%	11%		
20 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	5%		14%	16%	14%	16%	36%	37%	32%	32%		
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	5%		9%	5%	14%	16%	36%	42%	36%	37%		
22 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	14%	11%	14%	21%	36%	37%	14%	11%	9%	11%	14%	11%
23 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	5%		27%	37%	9%	5%	32%	32%	27%	26%		

2.1.2 Participants' comments first round

Aspect 1 - Severity of the disease

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I don't think we should throw medicine at very sick people. It should still be medicine that is likely to work. There should be biomarkers available or testing that shows likelihood of it working.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Severity suggests need for intervention, but severity could also be a disincentive if the impact of intervention does not create substantial benefit.

Aspect 2 - Unmet need of the disease

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unmet need can also refer to subsets of the disease group that are not appropriately or adequately treated by therapies that could be available for the majority or other subsets of the disease population.
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Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rarity is a factor only because it also implies that there is limited disease knowledge, previous research, and limited expertise from all stakeholders.
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Aspect 4 - Medicine's impact on mortality

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yes, a chance to address mortality for life-threatening conditions is imperative.
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Aspect 5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Any medicine should avoid making you worse than before.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Many diseases have very severe comorbidities that at times will overwhelm the impact of the disease itself.

Aspect 6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

Disagree	• Any medicine should always attempt to improve your quality of life.
Agree	• Quality of life is very important to all patients and valuable to address in an of itself but perhaps not on the same level of importance as mortality and morbidity.
Strongly agree	• Of immense importance. A patient may have needs or preference, and this is the most important factor to consider before providing any treatment.

Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Agree	• Adverse profile should be addressed in the clinical trials but some adverse effects may be very acceptable to some patients.
Strongly agree	• Especially if a patient is near end of life, there should be compassion in how relatives feel seeing their loved one in a helpless state if there is no chance of recovery. They should not be over treated with toxic drugs.

Aspect 8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients

Agree	• Tolerability is a subjective and relative concept and should always be considered from the "individual" patient perspective and take into consideration the range of possible responses from patients. Tolerability should be referred back to patient, for example, as part of informed consent rather than as a full stop to development and access.
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Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Agree	• Contraindications of usage may sometimes be considered in the context of patient preferences and tolerability, unless safety concerns are overwhelming.
Strongly agree	• This should be done prior in regulation and so provide the scope for the HTA.

Aspect 10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Special warnings and precautions may be dealt with in terms of how the drug is introduced, to whom and with appropriate levels of monitoring. • This should not prevent the general population from being prescribed a potentially successful drug. The doctor is the expert in looking at their patient as an individual.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As above should be covered in regulation to provide scope of HTA.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient should be kept informed

Aspect 11 - Medicine's mechanism of action

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too confusing for patients to understand.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the drug's mechanism of action is known and directly related to the disease pathway, that is an asset but many drugs are still developed and brought to the patient without a full understanding of how and why it works. This should not be a limiting factor.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This has to be the most important factor in choosing a correct treatment. We need diagnostics so each patient is correctly treated.

Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Don't know/Don't want to answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not sure what is meant by "spill over effects". • Don't understand what a spillover effect is.
Neither agree nor disagree	<p>It is important to consider spill-over effects and to be expansive (broad) in consideration to put in monitoring and safety measures but not to intervene with access.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Indeed, we learn from trials but the patient should be completely aware of the risk.

Aspect 13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease and convenience are assets but challenges in use and management should also not be considered barriers.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During treatment, part of success is dependent on how the patient feels. They have needs that help them to feel good. Exercise, nutrition,

	love. Less time in hospital for treatment helps the patient to live a more normal life.
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Aspect 14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Always have to consider the broader public impact but not as the first level of consideration; impact on the condition and affected patients greater priorities.
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Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the medicine can be correctly targeted to only 2% of patients, it has immense value as long as it can be correctly targeted to the 2%. We do need to be able to afford medicine for all. • Drug should be considered for the best interest of the patient.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economics are important but secondary to health, quality of life, and societal impact. • The economic costs should be covered by governments; I think is really important to clarify how this impact affects to patients.

Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All medicine should be placed on an affordable platform.
Don't know/Don't want to answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Affordability" is a relative concept - to whom, under what circumstances and what are the alternatives and how affordable are these?
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affordability can be a barrier in the end but should not be a leading factor in adjudicating access. If it is of value, the funding can be found. Affordability also refers to how much we as payers, societal or private, are willing to pay (divert funding from elsewhere or allocate more).
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medicines need to be affordable, but we do need to value medicines that target rare diseases. As every cancer becomes a rare disease because it is specific to the individual, we must spend the time and money on correct diagnostics.

Aspect 17 - Medicine's efficiency

Don't know/Don't want to answer	• Don't know what you mean by this
Disagree	• Medicine should be evaluated on patient quality of life not just extension of life.
Agree	• Efficiency is secondary to effectiveness and other factors related to alternatives.

Aspect 19 - Disease duration

Don't know/Don't want to answer	• A disease may only have a short duration because it is rapidly lethal or it may cause lifelong suffering.
Agree	• Duration works both for and against priority for access; diseases that have known shortened lifespans should not be treated as less important to treat than those which are possible for a "lifetime".

Aspect 20 - Disease age of onset

Neither agree nor disagree	• We seemingly think that children and youths who have not yet had the chance to experience a full life as compared to seniors who have had years of life. However, there is also a case to be made for those who have contributed a whole lifetime; a case can be made for any age, it seems.
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Aspect 21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

Disagree	• We need to be forward thinking for the system to succeed. Long term goals are needed not short term. We need centers of excellence and a system that is stable, not in change with changing politics. Incorrect treatment is as bad as misdiagnosis. We waste too much money on misdiagnosis and do not spend enough on prevention. We must end the capacity crisis in order to test and treat patients correctly. In the long term, this has been proven to save money in countries like Belgium where survival rates are highest.
Neither agree nor disagree	• Put patients health first.

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is more of a negative factor when it may take considerable organization and re-organization to provide access to a therapy; it's a matter of do the resources exist and what it will take to set up.
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Aspect 22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Again, put patients health first
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, considerations are important but probably as access proceeds rather than as a priority consideration when introducing.

Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

Don't know/Don't want to answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't think this should be relevant. • Not sure I understand this. Medicine should always be for the benefit of the patient and not to benefit governance.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sure these factors influence but should not be drivers (although they often are the drivers and also the final arbiters).

Aspect 24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only if it benefits the patients health.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Drugs that are lower in the treatment order may be less priority, but they may also be the ONLY possibility for some patients who have failed all others. We should not automatically relegate a newer therapy to a lesser priority in access just because it is newer or more expensive, since it may be the best for some. Personalized therapies will change all of this.

2.1.3 Participants' comments second round

Aspect 1 - Severity of the disease

Neither agree nor disagree	• I feel that all medicines have a value for a specific purpose. A minor illness needs medication just as much as a severe disease.
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Aspect 13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

Neither agree nor disagree	• Ease and convenience is important for a patient but if a new medicine is not very convenient it should still be considered. Most rare diseases are very complicated. An easy pill is preferred by patients. Unfortunately, this will not be the case in a lot of cases (gene therapy etc).
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Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Agree	• The economic aspect is important in a later stage when reimbursement is discussed. A new, working medicine should still be considered although the price is very high. It could be a treatment which has to be used once. Maybe the extremely expensive treatment makes it possible for patients to be completely active again (in the economic market).
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Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Neither agree nor disagree	• If the medicine is right for the condition, it doesn't matter if it is more expensive or not from a patient's point of view.
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Aspect 20 – Disease age of onset

Neither agree nor disagree	• Having a disease, whether you are young or older, should be treated equally the same, if a drug improves the quality of life, however long you have left, if that is the case, you can live it to your best.
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2.2 Survey – comments to the final results of the panel

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personalized medicine has to be the best way forward. • I found it very interesting to see the results from members of the panel. I noted that in the first half of the questions, dealing with morbidity and factors that were more direct, there was an
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overwhelming majority to a single response. The latter questions were more varied in responses dealing with age, ethnic background etc. This is to be expected. However, I found difficulty evaluating several answers as I feel the first priority should be given to targeted therapy. If the drug has high positive percentage response even to a small percentage of patients, then high value should be placed on this when evaluated.

- While I am in broad agreement with the weightings given, I think it is also important to consider whether we have the knowledge yet that makes it a realistic possibility to develop an intervention. For example, we have recently begun to see some progress in developing a disease modifying therapy for Huntington's disease, a devastating progressive neurological disorder, but this has only been possible due to progress elsewhere in understanding the blood/brain barrier and how to either circumvent or to cross it. Without this addressing the faulty process that caused the disease at the molecular level was impossible.

- I don't have anything to add, other than that I trust the panel represented both chronic and acute illnesses, rare and common. It is important to try to avoid bias in the result.

- I would love to see the figures I put in in my own input, and compare them to the final results, but it appears to be a consistent outcome. How long you have had a disease and at what age outweighs the cost/political implications from a patient's point of view, at the end of the day, from my personal viewpoint, if I have only a few years left, I would like to have a better quality of life. It would be the pharmaceutical company's responsibility to provide these medications at a cost that would make it possible for everyone to have these drugs.

2.3 Survey – comments about the Web-Delphi process

- A number of the questions in the process were somewhat confusing. Simpler explanations could be better.

- It is a very good process and it would be interesting to see the results from the other panels. For patients and carers, it would be helpful to word the questions more directly.

- This has been an interesting exercise allowing the comparison of my opinions with others and hopefully building towards a consensus.

- Straightforward. Would have liked the items to be grouped, e.g. disease-related, medicine-related, process-related.

- I did not find the comments very useful in changing opinions because they were relatively vague. I think nesting these principles in real world contexts would be more meaningful.

- Excellent process, with the active input provided by end-users (patients), and consultants, looking at every issue relevant in today's drug provision and the main areas of importance.

2.4 Survey – aspect ‘Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine’s clinical trials’

2.4.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 5. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) about the relevance of the aspect ‘Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials’ (13 participants).

Proposed aspect	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Don't know/Don't want to answer
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials			15%	38%	38%	8%

2.4.2 Participants’ comments

Aspect 18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If research ethics committees, data access committees, peer reviewers, regulators etc are doing their job properly and professionally then flawed designs ought to be spotted and the issues addressed prior to initiating the trial. • Really depends on what type of bias, how much the bias would influence the Clinical Trials process and outcomes, and the likely impact on the efficacy and/or safety of the drug as well as the potential impact on cost-effectiveness, for example, estimates of eligible population, size of benefits and adverse effects.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All drug trials should be aimed at providing benefits for the patients and not to benefit the trial processes and outcomes. Use of targeted therapy must be the best way forward. • My concern is that the paucity of data for trials in rare diseases, or for trials of combination treatments in cancer based on genomic data will make HTA processes difficult requiring new paradigms/models to assess sufficiently well to allow medicines that may be effective to get introduced (especially with the England model). Even today, cancer treatments can have widely different ICERs in different settings (adjuvant vs metastatic) and this 'lifetime' use of a medicine is not considered. This is not a flaw in the design of trials, but it is a failure to look forward and to make processes fit for purpose for future medicines - a flaw in HTA design, not trial design or practice.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is obviously a risk of bias in such trials, especially when being carried out by a pharmaceutical company likely to make vast profits, but these risks should be contained and ideally removed by added completely independent checker(s), and sufficient participants involved in clinical trials especially where there are high cost implications, political implications and obviously risk to mortality.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I feel that some trials have been designed, in the past, to benefit the pharmaceutical company, not the patient. Hence, OS has been the end point as this has previously been favored by HTA. It is most important that the patients on the trial are reflective of the average who would receive this medication, otherwise this bias should be noted.

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2: Report with results from the Web-Delphi process of the Scientific Experts and Methodologists panel to identify which value dimensions should be considered in the “New multicriteria framework to facilitate Health Technology Assessment (HTA) organisations in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”

Grant Agreement No.:779312

Work Package: WP7, Task 2

Prepared by: IST (Universidade de Lisboa) and London School of Economics

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1 Background information

IMPACT HTA is a research project looking at new and improved methods across 10 thematic research areas aiming at understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, and integrating clinical and economic data from different sources to improve methods in economic evaluation in the context of HTA and health system performance measurement.

Within IMPACT HTA work package 7 (WP7) research is taking place towards the development and testing of a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new medicines. This fits into the second task of WP7, whose aim is twofold: first, to structure a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, with these models reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers; and, second, to define alternative techniques and questioning protocols to build such a model. The starting point of Task 2 in terms of potential aspects of performance feeds from the results of Task 1 of the WP which has econometrically analysed the determinants of HTA recommendations by relying on secondary data. Following the completion of Task 2, the methodological framework will then be tested in practice through a number of case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies that will be carried out within Task 3 of WP7.

In order to build such a framework, two questions are currently being answered within Task 2: First, which aspects should be considered in a novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis? And second, which of those aspects are fundamental for that evaluation?

In order to address the first question, you kindly participated in a Web-Delphi process. The objective of this report is to provide you with an overview of the aggregated Web-Delphi results for all panels, and also more detailed results for your own stakeholder panel (Scientific Experts and Methodologists).

Regarding the general features of the already developed Web-Delphi process, the views of a mix of a large and diverse number of stakeholders were collected in separate panels (Panel 1: Payers and policy-makers; Panel 2: HTA bodies; Panel 3: Health care professionals; Panel 4: Patients and carers; Panel 5: Scientific experts and methodologists; and Panel 6: Industry) regarding which are the most relevant aspects that should be taken as value dimensions to evaluate new medicines on a common value basis. The complete list of aspects (24 in total) and their respective description are listed in Table

1. As described above, these aspects were derived from analysis that took place in the earlier task of this WP.

Participants were asked to specify their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5-level scale ('Strongly Disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', 'Agree', 'Strongly Agree'), about the relevance of each of the 24 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. For each aspect, participants could always select the option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' and leave additional comments. For each aspect there was a brief description of their substantive meaning.

This Web-Delphi panel included a total of two rounds that took place between February 5th – February 15th and February 19th – March 1st, 2019, respectively. The overall Web-Delphi process was divided across six panels that ran in parallel, with each panel gathering participants' views from a specific stakeholder group. The aim of the first round was to collect the initial views of each participant of the panel regarding what is the relevance of the 24 aspects when evaluating new medicines on a common value basis (e.g. on a multidimensional value score basis). The aim of the second round was for the participants of each panel to access an anonymous summary of their panel's overall responses from the first round and have the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in terms of the inclusion or exclusions of the 24 aspects.

Following the two Web-Delphi rounds, a survey to participants collected comments on both the final results of their panel and the Web-Delphi process itself. Additionally, the panels of 'HTA bodies' and 'Patients and carers' were questioned about one of the aspects separately ('Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of a medicine's clinical trials') because it was not included in the Web-Delphi rounds. The survey took place between March 21st and April 1st, 2019. Following the Web-Delphi, a facilitated workshop was organized in April, with 11 participants representing all stakeholder groups for the purpose of reviewing and validating (for instance, interpreting, discussing and adjusting) the results of the Web-Delphi process.

Information regarding the number of participants in each panel for each round is shown in Table 2, and the aggregated voting final results for all Web-Delphi participants are shown in Table 3.

Following further research conducted by the WP7 team, a new stage will start soon as part of Task 2: all Web-Delphi participants (which previously had been divided into 6 separate stakeholder panels) will be invited to participate together in an overall web-Delphi to provide their final views about how

fundamental is to include each selected aspect in the novel framework. All participants will view the aspects' results from the first Web-Delphi and of the Decision Conferencing processes, for several of which no consensus was reached regarding their inclusion or exclusion in the novel framework, and will be invited to state their views regarding how fundamental each aspect is for the evaluation of drugs on a common basis. This Web-Delphi will be launched in September.

The next section of this report presents the results of the Scientific Experts and Methodologists panel, summarising the results of the first and second rounds, together with the results of the survey including the comments received to the final results of the panel and to the Web-Delphi process.

Thank you again for your collaboration.

Table 1. List of aspects examined in the Web-Delphi and brief description.

Aspect	Description
Severity of the disease	The condition's/ indication's degree of seriousness in respect to mortality and morbidity-derived disability.
Unmet need of the disease	The availability of medical interventions for the indication of interest, which could relate to methods of diagnosis, prevention or treatment.
Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Number of cases of the disease at present or number of new cases that develop, e.g. prevalence of the disease (i.e. proportion of a population that have the disease at a point in time) or incidence of the disease (i.e. rate at which new disease cases occur in a population during a specified period).
Medicine's impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and complications.
Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.
Medicine's adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse outcomes occurring when a medicine is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.
Medicine's tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.
Medicine's contraindications of use	Any risk and safety factors that act as a reason for a medicine not to be used by a patient.
Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Potential risks associated with the use of the medicine in regards to specific patient sub-populations with particular characteristics.
Medicine's mechanism of action	The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).
Medicine's spill-over effects	R&D positive externalities (i.e. beneficial follow-on external effects) that can lead to the development of subsequent innovation or new indication in review or clinical development, e.g. new medicines or new indication approvals.
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.
Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Any risk reduction in transmitting and developing the disease under consideration or any other disease within the broader population.
Medicine's economic impact	Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.
Medicine's affordability	Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.
Medicine's efficiency	The medicine's value-for-money in terms of resource allocation, e.g. the additional cost needed to gain an extra unit of health outcome, i.e. Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants and personnel, detection bias due to ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.
Disease duration	The average length of time the disease is present, e.g. Chronic vs Incurable.
Disease age of onset	The average age at which an individual acquires, develops, or first experiences a condition or symptoms of a disease or disorder, e.g. children.
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity.
Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with cultural, political and stakeholder acceptability and participation, including any legal barriers.
Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Refers to whether the aim, i.e. targeted action of the medicine is preventive, symptomatic (relief) or curative.

Table 2. Number of participants per panel of stakeholder group, across each round of the Web-Delphi process and in the final survey.

Panel (Stakeholder group)	Invited	# participants (round 1)	# participants (round 2)	# participants (survey)
Healthcare professionals	30	25	21	10
Payers and policy-makers	20	18	18	11
HTA bodies	33	29	28	19
Scientific experts and methodologists	46	42	38	23
Patients and carers	26	22	19	13
Industry	40	31	29	14
Total	195	167	153	90

Table 3. Final voting results for all Web-Delphi participants (aggregated results from the 6 panels).

Aspect/ Level of agreement or disagreement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Total
1 - Severity of the disease	1%	3%	4%	24%	69%	0%	153
2 - Unmet need of the disease	1%	2%	3%	20%	72%	1%	153
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1%	11%	16%	42%	29%	0%	153
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	0%	0%	0%	18%	82%	0%	153
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	0%	0%	1%	22%	78%	0%	153
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	0%	0%	1%	22%	77%	0%	153
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	0%	1%	5%	39%	56%	0%	153
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0%	2%	7%	49%	42%	0%	153
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	1%	11%	20%	44%	24%	0%	153
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	0%	10%	27%	41%	22%	0%	153
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	4%	21%	39%	25%	11%	0%	153
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%	12%	29%	42%	12%	1%	153
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1%	5%	20%	52%	24%	0%	153
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0%	1%	7%	39%	54%	0%	153
15 - Medicine's economic impact	0%	5%	9%	35%	52%	0%	153
16 - Medicine's affordability	2%	6%	11%	39%	41%	1%	153
17 - Medicine's efficiency	1%	3%	3%	32%	61%	0%	153
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	0%	2%	10%	49%	39%	0%	106
19 - Disease duration	1%	10%	30%	45%	14%	1%	153

20 - Disease age of onset	1%	15%	30%	44%	10%	0%	153
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0%	5%	14%	54%	26%	1%	153
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1%	3%	19%	47%	30%	0%	153
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	8%	24%	36%	20%	7%	5%	153
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	2%	16%	24%	42%	16%	0%	153

2 Panel results: Scientific Experts and Methodologists

2.1 Web-Delphi – first round versus second round results

2.1.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 4. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) regarding the relevance of each of the 24 proposed aspects at the end of the first round (n=42 participants) versus the end of the second round (n=38 participants). Note: D = Disagree, A = Agree

Aspect/ Level of agreement per round	Round 1 - Strongly D	Round 2 - Strongly D	Round 1 - D	Round 2 - D	Round 1 - Neither A nor D	Round 2 - Neither A nor D	Round 1 - A	Round 2 - A	Round 1 - Strongly A	Round 2 - Strongly A	Round 1 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Round 2 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer
1 - Severity of the disease			7%	8%	7%	5%	24%	24%	62%	63%		
2 - Unmet need of the disease	2%	3%	10%	8%	2%	5%	31%	24%	50%	55%	5%	5%
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	2%	3%	12%	13%	19%	16%	40%	47%	26%	21%		
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality					2%		24%	18%	74%	82%		
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity					5%	3%	29%	13%	67%	84%		
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life							19%	11%	81%	89%		
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile			5%	3%	2%		43%	47%	50%	50%		
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients			7%	8%	10%	5%	45%	50%	38%	37%		
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	7%	5%	7%	13%	21%	18%	43%	47%	21%	16%		
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	2%		14%	18%	21%	18%	43%	53%	19%	11%		
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	5%	3%	26%	34%	48%	47%	17%	11%	5%	5%		
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%	5%	14%	18%	24%	16%	43%	47%	14%	13%		
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	2%	3%	7%	8%	10%	8%	55%	58%	26%	24%		

14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community					7%	8%	52%	55%	40%	37%		
15 - Medicine's economic impact			7%	8%	10%	5%	33%	32%	50%	55%		
16 - Medicine's affordability			7%	11%	12%	8%	33%	32%	48%	50%		
17 - Medicine's efficiency			2%	3%	5%	3%	31%	26%	62%	68%		
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials			2%	5%	14%	5%	36%	42%	48%	47%		
19 - Disease duration	5%	3%	12%	13%	33%	34%	38%	39%	12%	11%		
20 - Disease age of onset	2%		5%	5%	36%	34%	45%	53%	12%	8%		
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	5%		2%	3%	19%	18%	52%	58%	21%	21%		
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	5%	3%			21%	16%	48%	58%	26%	24%		
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	10%	5%	29%	34%	29%	32%	24%	24%	7%	3%	2%	3%
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	7%	5%	21%	24%	31%	34%	29%	29%	12%	8%		

2.1.2 Participants' comments first round

Aspect 1 - Severity of the disease

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, part of the overall assessment, but by affecting the cost-effectiveness threshold.
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Aspect 2 - Unmet need of the disease

Don't know/Don't want to answer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unmet need appears to be a buzz word that opens doors for licensing medicines, despite it being only vaguely defined. There is presumably general agreement that patients with "unmet need", i.e. no access to treatment that works for them, should rank highly on the list of priorities when evaluating medicines, but a discussion and proper definition of when this situation occurs is necessary.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In burden of disease study, not directly in CEA.

Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need to specify if this criterion would have a positive impact on overall value (e.g. we want to prioritize interventions for rare conditions given the possible market failure) or a negative impact (e.g. we want to prioritize interventions affecting as many people as possible). • Not rarity per se, but in combination with health-catastrophe. Changes the cost-effectiveness threshold.
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Aspect 4 - Medicine's impact on mortality

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on the context. Highly relevant for some diseases, less so for others (in particular if trumping other considerations, in particular quality of life).
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of key dimensions of the QALY, but should be captured by the QALY.

Aspect 5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Depends on context. Important to safeguard against purely focusing on outcomes that are easier to measure and easier to modify through treatments (e.g. short-term symptoms) when little or no effect on other, potentially more relevant outcomes (mortality, QoL) is expected.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Affects One key dimensions of the QALY by affecting health state utility. But don't double count: put in the QALY. • Potential double counting with HRQoL

Aspect 6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of key dimensions of the QALY. Better to enter the QALY.
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Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential double counting with HRQoL.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes, as it can enter part of incremental QALY estimate.

Aspect 8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • But double counts with adverse event profile and HR quality of life. • Don't double count. Better to use HR QoL. • Depends on capture, e.g., in relation to adverse events, pop size of available data on baseline MTD, etc.
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Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Should be considered in defining the scope of the analysis. • The evaluation should focus on the target patient group.
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Aspect 10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions

Strongly disagree	• More relevant uptake and use.
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Aspect 11 - Medicine's mechanism of action

Strongly disagree	• From a population perspective, only as it affects uptake and use.
Neither agree nor disagree	• MoA can easily not be known for a very effective drug, so far from ideal in terms of assessing 'innovativeness', particularly in terms of comparative assessments, etc. Also, I opened your definition out of interest, but this is not a definition I would easily endorse. Thinking of AIFA's new algorithm, i.e., unmet therapeutic need, added therapeutic value, quality of evidence, for innovativeness, I wonder what exactly it is proposed here in relation to MoA.

Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Strongly disagree	• I disagree because of the challenges in objectively assessing this criterion and the potential shift away from patient-relevant criteria for the evaluation of new medicines that the inclusion of such a criterion would bring (strong incentive for manufacturers to focus on knock-on effects and requesting longer-term exclusivity for markets based on their R&D portfolio, with no guarantees of beneficial effects for patients and health systems).
Disagree	• Theoretically, yes, it would be an important step -beyond the assessment or to complement it, however, on the basis of up-to-date pipeline data, recorded spill-over effects, etc., it is highly unlikely there would be sufficient information provided (transparently and accurately) for such a dimension to be meaningful.
Strongly agree	• As an add-on to applying cost-per-QALY metric.

Aspect 13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

Strongly disagree	• More at a population level, as if affects uptake and use.
Strongly agree	• Depends on capturing, e.g., double effect, QoL, whether safety/monitoring is affected and info on this, etc.

Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Strongly agree	• Sounds like incremental cost to me. okay to consider both health sector and societal perspective.
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Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Neither agree nor disagree	• It would depend on whether the evaluation is for licensing or for reimbursement.
Agree	• Should not be part of a CEA. Okay as BIA.

Aspect 17 - Medicine's efficiency

Strongly agree	• This is the main thing that should be considered. It is summary statistic that combines QALYs and incremental cost. It includes and therefore over-rides many o the others listed above--that I agreed with.
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Aspect 18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

Agree	• Should be considered qualitatively.
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Aspect 19 - Disease duration

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Used to define the target population, then you do the CEA or BIA. • Agree because of the relevance of disease duration for economic considerations (for individual patients and health systems).
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Aspect 20 - Disease age of onset

Agree	• Used to define the target population, then you do the CEA or BIA.
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Aspect 21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This depends mostly on the healthcare system setting and features. I believe that this aspect is not feasible to be considered on a common basis across systems. Each system is unique, with different flaws and unmet needs.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can consider qualitatively but no way to scale this. Could be considered in the broadest "societal" perspective.

Aspect 22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider qualitatively or quantitatively as an accompanying analysis to a cost-per-QALY analysis.
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Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Okay to consider qualitatively but not as part of the CEA or even MCDA.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to respond, as we have a very 'mixed bag' in the definition, i.e., both governance -and- political leadership, which are two very different things... • This can be important for gene therapy.

Aspect 24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Part of defining the problem to be analyzed. Implicit in the disease model underlying the incremental QALY calculation.
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2.1.3 Participants' comments second round

Aspect 2 - Unmet need of the disease

Strongly Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The reason why I disagreed with the inclusion of this is that, first, depending on the way severity is measured, it can capture this aspect (i.e. if there is not active treatment available, severity given the standard of care will be higher than in cases where there is an active treatment available). If severity does not include unmet need, the a relationship between the
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	two criteria needs to be established and taken into account (e.g. mild disease with an unmet need should NOT be prioritised).
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Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't see why rarity is per se a factor. I realize that it messes up threshold-based CEA but that is the problem of the method which is faulty.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Disease rarity seems more and more difficult to define given advance in "personalized" medicine.

Aspect 5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OK, I accept the opinion of the majority. The problem with regard my previous response is that morbidity is a broad term but I am sure this issue is very important and I can change my opinion.
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Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Revised answer to agree. Impact of adverse events is largely captured by QALY measurement. However, consideration of the overall adverse events profile can help to contextualize QALY calculations and this is important to understand what is driving the model. The other important dimension of safety is tolerability. • I do not really disagree with the majority. However, side effects are variable and not all are severe. In summary, I prefer to leave "agree" as response.
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Aspect 8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are tolerability and contra indications included in health related quality of life?
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Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contraindications are something to be aware of clinically but other than listing the, I don't see how they enter into the assessment.
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Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Very difficult to measure and therefore operationalize. One concern is that a product will be approved at a high price for a very small population, and then request the same price for additional indications (with potential much larger patient populations). I disagree that this should factor into an evaluation of a product. It is preferable to have separate evaluations for different indications and separate prices for different indications than to allow potential spill-over effects to modify an evaluation. The caveat here being that maintaining differential pricing can be problematic from a procurement and prescribing standpoint.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ok, revising the definition, I can accept the opinion of the majority.

Aspect 13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OK, I accept the opinion of the majority but my opinion was based on an expert opinion leaving the patient perspective aside. it was my mistake.
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Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct and indirect costs are important in decision but should not be included as criteria. how can people make tradeoff between costs (which are not incurring in the case of public NHS) and benefits?
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I would not like to change my opinion. I think that the economic impact by itself is not enough to impact in the final decision for marketing and reimburse the medicine.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic impact needs to be assessed at the system level, and considering opportunity costs incurred within and outside of health care, as well as equity in terms of who is paying opportunity costs.

Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> From my point of view affordability is related to available budgets. Budgets is something that must be flexible and could be expanded either by asking populations who sign in on a certain benefit plan or asking political decisionmakers to allocate more Resources.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affordability needs to be assessed at the household and the system level, and considering opportunity costs within and outside of health care, as well as equity in terms of who is paying opportunity costs.

Aspect 17 - Medicine's efficiency

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I would not consider cost effectiveness as a separate criterion. the purpose of a multi criteria framework it is still to reach efficient decisions but broaden the definition of value.
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Aspect 18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Uncertainty around effectiveness should be captured in sensitivity analyses not a separate criterion. Again, how do people can make trade off between this and with other criteria?
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This criterion seems of increasing importance given FDA and EMA approvals based on less and less stringent evidence.

Aspect 19 - Disease duration

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Under this point we should differentiate treatments for chronic diseases (e.g. leukemia) versus acute diseases (breast cancer) as the economic burden for those treatments (either for the patient or for the health care system) will be very different.
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Aspect 20 - Disease age of onset

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I believe this point is very important, especially in light of end-of-life care. We need to think more carefully about giving expensive treatments at the end of life.
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Aspect 24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning

Neither agree nor disagree	• I believe this point is more relevant in the US-context but maybe less important in the European systems.
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2.2 Survey – comments to the final results of the panel

- I noticed that the other panel members did not consider disease duration as relevant. In my opinion this variable should definitely be consider as more and more diseases develop into chronic life-long diseases such as chronic lymphocytic leukemia (CLL).
- The level of agreement was low in my opinion.
- Regarding Medicine's economic impact & affordability and actually the final HTA Board decision, should we take in consideration the (disclosed) list price or the (usually undisclosed) reimbursed price agreed after a negotiation process?
- For the most part, there seems to be a consensus which is encouraging in a field with so much uncertainty.
- I am surprised that there aren't more items getting majority negatives and also at the spread on some of these.
- Lakdawalla et al., in Defining Elements of Value in Health Care—A Health Economics Approach: An ISPOR Special Task Force Report. Value in Health, identify a number of value elements which can apply to medical technologies (ont only medicines). <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/29477390> I also wonder what how you defined your acceptable level of agreement and which value dimensions you have selected for the final framework. I guess I will have to wait for the report publication! I also wonder what how you defined your acceptable level of agreement and how the results will translate into a framwrok
- Nothing more to add. Given the broad range of criteria that reached a high level of agreement, I am interested in how this will be developed into actionable recommendations.
- Necessary research :)
- A general comment: for any consideration on a common basis agreement on definitions and clear understanding is key. For many key concepts, e.g. unmet medical need, legal frameworks of Member States in Europe diverge, with the EMA adopting an 'operational' definition for MAA, SA, etc. It is critical to have multistakeholder input on establishing definitions which are accepted and well understood by all before embarking on scoring concepts. It was not clear how the definitions in this process where generated. There were more than a couple ambiguous at best definitions with no detail on which frame they were anchored, etc.

2.3 Survey – comments about the Web-Delphi process

- Being able to see the results of the first round before answering the second round seemed as if it could bias my answers to the second round. That is, I could be swayed by the other answers. But perhaps that is what is intended?
- Congratulations to such a well organized process! Participation was very easy due to the superb preparation by the IMPACT team. It is a very valuable undertaking especially as so many diverse stakeholders are involved. Good luck with the next steps of the project.
- I think that one extra round with more explanations about include (or not) a criterium would be helpful.
- The online system was user-friendly and the questions were well-written and covered all of the main aspects that should be considered. Thank you for your work.
- Very easy and efficient.
- The process was very well organised and clearly explained. the interface is nice and user friendly.
- I think it might have helped to make the "comments" mandatory (i.e. asking for justification for the votes) to help understand better why others have voted differently.
- Passed successfully.
- The Web-Delphi process has been swift, precise and extremely user friendly. It has been a great experience participating in the panel and knowing that we have achieved a high level of agreement in the second round.
- There were no detailed instructions explaining to participants the clear need to see and 'assess' definitions prior to scoring. There were no instructions on, for example, whether it was necessary or not to provide comments upon strong agreement or disagreement, and on how this scoring will be used or interpreted. It was surprising not to see first round comments in the final output; in a Delphi procedure one expects to see consensus built along with all comments in the final output. This is clearly not the case here. Accessing the questionnaire was easy and the interface was user friendly, at least for people familiar with similar tools.

iMPACT HTA

The logo for iMPACT HTA features the word 'iMPACT' in a bold, black, sans-serif font, with a lowercase 'i'. The letter 'A' is replaced by a circular graphic consisting of several concentric rings in various colors (yellow, green, blue, purple, pink) and a central multi-colored dot. To the right of 'iMPACT' is the text 'HTA' in a large, bold, black, sans-serif font.

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2: Report with results from the Web-Delphi process of the Health Care Professionals panel to identify which value dimensions should be considered in the “New multicriteria framework to facilitate Health Technology Assessment (HTA) organisations in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”

Grant Agreement No.:779312

Work Package: WP7, Task 2

Prepared by: IST (Universidade de Lisboa) and London School of Economics

Date: 29 August 2019

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1 Background information

IMPACT HTA is a research project looking at new and improved methods across 10 thematic research areas aiming at understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, and integrating clinical and economic data from different sources to improve methods in economic evaluation in the context of HTA and health system performance measurement.

Within IMPACT HTA work package 7 (WP7) research is taking place towards the development and testing of a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new medicines. This fits into the second task of WP7, whose aim is twofold: first, to structure a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, with these models reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers; and, second, to define alternative techniques and questioning protocols to build such a model. The starting point of Task 2 in terms of potential aspects of performance feeds from the results of Task 1 of the WP which has econometrically analysed the determinants of HTA recommendations by relying on secondary data. Following the completion of Task 2, the methodological framework will then be tested in practice through a number of case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies that will be carried out within Task 3 of WP7.

In order to build such a framework, two questions are currently being answered within Task 2: First, which aspects should be considered in a novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis? And second, which of those aspects are fundamental for that evaluation?

In order to address the first question, you kindly participated in a Web-Delphi process. The objective of this report is to provide you with an overview of the aggregated Web-Delphi results for all panels, and also more detailed results for your own stakeholder panel (Health Care Professionals).

Regarding the general features of the already developed Web-Delphi process, the views of a mix of a large and diverse number of stakeholders were collected in separate panels (Panel 1: Payers and policy-makers; Panel 2: HTA bodies; Panel 3: Health care professionals; Panel 4: Patients and carers; Panel 5: Scientific experts and methodologists; and Panel 6: Industry) regarding which are the most relevant aspects that should be taken as value dimensions to evaluate new medicines on a common value basis. The complete list of aspects (24 in total) and their respective description are listed in Table

1. As described above, these aspects were derived from analysis that took place in the earlier task of this WP.

Participants were asked to specify their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5-level scale ('Strongly Disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', 'Agree', 'Strongly Agree'), about the relevance of each of the 24 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. For each aspect, participants could always select the option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' and leave additional comments. For each aspect there was a brief description of their substantive meaning.

This Web-Delphi panel included a total of two rounds that took place between February 5th – February 15th and February 19th – March 1st, 2019, respectively. The overall Web-Delphi process was divided across six panels that ran in parallel, with each panel gathering participants' views from a specific stakeholder group. The aim of the first round was to collect the initial views of each participant of the panel regarding what is the relevance of the 24 aspects when evaluating new medicines on a common value basis (e.g. on a multidimensional value score basis). The aim of the second round was for the participants of each panel to access an anonymous summary of their panel's overall responses from the first round and have the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in terms of the inclusion or exclusions of the 24 aspects.

Following the two Web-Delphi rounds, a survey to participants collected comments on both the final results of their panel and the Web-Delphi process itself. Additionally, the panels of 'HTA bodies' and 'Patients and carers' were questioned about one of the aspects separately ('Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of a medicine's clinical trials') because it was not included in the Web-Delphi rounds. The survey took place between March 21st and April 1st, 2019. Following the Web-Delphi, a facilitated workshop was organized in April, with 11 participants representing all stakeholder groups for the purpose of reviewing and validating (for instance, interpreting, discussing and adjusting) the results of the Web-Delphi process.

Information regarding the number of participants in each panel for each round is shown in

Table 2, and the aggregated voting final results for all Web-Delphi participants are shown in Table 3.

Following further research conducted by the WP7 team, a new stage will start soon as part of Task 2: all Web-Delphi participants (which previously had been divided into 6 separate stakeholder panels) will be invited to participate together in an overall web-Delphi to provide their final views about how

fundamental is to include each selected aspect in the novel framework. All participants will view the aspects' results from the first Web-Delphi and of the Decision Conferencing processes, for several of which no consensus was reached regarding their inclusion or exclusion in the novel framework, and will be invited to state their views regarding how fundamental each aspect is for the evaluation of drugs on a common basis. This Web-Delphi will be launched in September.

The next section of this report presents the results of the Health Care Professionals panel, summarising the results of the first and second rounds, together with the results of the survey including the comments received to the final results of the panel and to the Web-Delphi process.

Thank you again for your collaboration.

Table 1. List of aspects examined in the Web-Delphi and brief description.

Aspect	Description
Severity of the disease	The condition's/ indication's degree of seriousness in respect to mortality and morbidity-derived disability.
Unmet need of the disease	The availability of medical interventions for the indication of interest, which could relate to methods of diagnosis, prevention or treatment.
Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Number of cases of the disease at present or number of new cases that develop, e.g. prevalence of the disease (i.e. proportion of a population that have the disease at a point in time) or incidence of the disease (i.e. rate at which new disease cases occur in a population during a specified period).
Medicine's impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and complications.
Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.
Medicine's adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse outcomes occurring when a medicine is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.
Medicine's tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.
Medicine's contraindications of use	Any risk and safety factors that act as a reason for a medicine not to be used by a patient.
Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Potential risks associated with the use of the medicine in regards to specific patient sub-populations with particular characteristics.
Medicine's mechanism of action	The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).
Medicine's spill-over effects	R&D positive externalities (i.e. beneficial follow-on external effects) that can lead to the development of subsequent innovation or new indication in review or clinical development, e.g. new medicines or new indication approvals.
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.
Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Any risk reduction in transmitting and developing the disease under consideration or any other disease within the broader population.
Medicine's economic impact	Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.
Medicine's affordability	Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.
Medicine's efficiency	The medicine's value-for-money in terms of resource allocation, e.g. the additional cost needed to gain an extra unit of health outcome, i.e. Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants and personnel, detection bias due to ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.
Disease duration	The average length of time the disease is present, e.g. Chronic vs Incurable.
Disease age of onset	The average age at which an individual acquires, develops, or first experiences a condition or symptoms of a disease or disorder, e.g. children.
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity.
Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with cultural, political and stakeholder acceptability and participation, including any legal barriers.
Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Refers to whether the aim, i.e. targeted action of the medicine is preventive, symptomatic (relief) or curative.

Table 2. Number of participants per panel of stakeholder group, across each round of the Web-Delphi process and in the final survey.

Panel (Stakeholder group)	Invited	# participants (round 1)	# participants (round 2)	# participants (survey)
Healthcare professionals	30	25	21	10
Payers and policy-makers	20	18	18	11
HTA bodies	33	29	28	19
Scientific experts and methodologists	46	42	38	23
Patients and carers	26	22	19	13
Industry	40	31	29	14
Total	195	167	153	90

Table 3. Final voting results for all Web-Delphi participants (aggregated results from the 6 panels).

Aspect/ Level of agreement or disagreement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Total
1 - Severity of the disease	1%	3%	4%	24%	69%	0%	153
2 - Unmet need of the disease	1%	2%	3%	20%	72%	1%	153
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1%	11%	16%	42%	29%	0%	153
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	0%	0%	0%	18%	82%	0%	153
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	0%	0%	1%	22%	78%	0%	153
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	0%	0%	1%	22%	77%	0%	153
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	0%	1%	5%	39%	56%	0%	153
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0%	2%	7%	49%	42%	0%	153
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	1%	11%	20%	44%	24%	0%	153
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	0%	10%	27%	41%	22%	0%	153
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	4%	21%	39%	25%	11%	0%	153
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%	12%	29%	42%	12%	1%	153
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1%	5%	20%	52%	24%	0%	153
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0%	1%	7%	39%	54%	0%	153
15 - Medicine's economic impact	0%	5%	9%	35%	52%	0%	153
16 - Medicine's affordability	2%	6%	11%	39%	41%	1%	153
17 - Medicine's efficiency	1%	3%	3%	32%	61%	0%	153
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	0%	2%	10%	49%	39%	0%	106
19 - Disease duration	1%	10%	30%	45%	14%	1%	153

20 - Disease age of onset	1%	15%	30%	44%	10%	0%	153
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0%	5%	14%	54%	26%	1%	153
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1%	3%	19%	47%	30%	0%	153
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	8%	24%	36%	20%	7%	5%	153
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	2%	16%	24%	42%	16%	0%	153

2 Panel results: Health Care Professionals

2.1 Web-Delphi – first round versus second round results

2.1.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 4. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) regarding the relevance of each of the 24 proposed aspects at the end of the first round (n=25 participants) versus the end of the second round (n=21 participants). Note: D = Disagree, A = Agree

Aspect/ Level of agreement per round	Round 1 - Strongly D	Round 2 - Strongly D	Round 1 - D	Round 2 - D	Round 1 - Neither A nor D	Round 2 - Neither A nor D	Round 1 - A	Round 2 - A	Round 1 - Strongly A	Round 2 - Strongly A	Round 1 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Round 2 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer
1 - Severity of the disease			4%				24%	29%	72%	71%		
2 - Unmet need of the disease							20%	24%	80%	76%		
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)			8%	5%	16%	19%	40%	38%	36%	38%		
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality							24%	29%	76%	71%		
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity							28%	33%	72%	67%		
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life							32%	33%	68%	67%		
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile					4%		40%	48%	56%	52%		
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients					4%		64%	76%	32%	24%		
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use			8%	10%	12%	5%	64%	67%	16%	19%		
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions			4%	5%	36%	29%	44%	48%	16%	19%		
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	4%	5%	12%	14%	28%	24%	36%	33%	20%	24%		
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects			8%	5%	24%	24%	56%	57%	12%	14%		
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients			4%	5%	16%	10%	56%	67%	24%	19%		

14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health (disease risk reduction in the community)					16%	19%	24%	14%	60%	67%		
15 - Medicine's economic impact					24%	19%	48%	52%	28%	29%		
16 - Medicine's affordability			4%	5%	16%	10%	36%	38%	44%	48%		
17 - Medicine's efficiency					8%	10%	44%	38%	48%	52%		
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws (in design, conduct, analyses and reporting of clinical trials)					12%	5%	32%	33%	56%	62%		
19 - Disease duration			4%	5%	36%	33%	48%	57%	12%	5%		
20 - Disease age of onset			16%	19%	28%	19%	44%	52%	12%	10%		
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care					24%	24%	52%	52%	24%	24%		
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues					24%	19%	36%	33%	40%	48%		
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair (leadership goals and governance requirements)	4%	5%	16%	19%	48%	52%	24%	19%	8%	5%		
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning			4%	5%	40%	43%	40%	43%	16%	10%		

2.1.2 Participants' comments first round

Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

2.1.2.1 Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Why should any HTA assess a new technology on the possible basis of future benefit? It is important for manufacturers to provide evidence of this - not a hypothetical future requirement.
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Aspect 24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning

2.1.2.2 Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there is a positive ICER - then why does this matter?
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2.1.3 Participants' comments second round

Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

2.1.3.1 Neither agree or disagree	2.1.3.2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Importance of rarity of the disease depends on the perspective. Patients with rare diseases may have high unmet needs. This is important from their perspective and of their families, even if from a societal perspective it means paying much for a few people who need the treatment.
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Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

2.1.3.3 Strongly disagree	2.1.3.4 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Political priorities should have no impact on the objective assessment of new medicines
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2.2 Survey – comments to the final results of the panel

- I have a comment regarding the appraisal of rarity and contraindications as value dimensions. I saw the panel majority considered them as important / very important. The implications of this may not be clear. Unmet need may be clear for rare and common diseases. In this context, adverse events have a relative meaning.
- I don't miss any aspect.
- I would like to add an item related to patient feedback. This feedback (User experience UX) can condition compliance to treatment. Many factors can contribute to good or bad compliance such as: the psychological representation of this category of treatment, the name, the shape, the colour, the taste of the product, the experience of side effects etc. To study these aspects, it would be interesting to add during clinical studies, a qualitative study of patients included with interviews conducted by researchers in the human sciences, before the start of the tested treatments and after the study.
- We should also consider the impact of the medicine's adoption in the environment's sustainability.
- In my opinion the majority of most important aspects of the process were incorporated.
- Other dimensions for consideration should be: 1. Most of the new and innovative medicines (especially the costly ones) should be subject to specialist prescribing at least for the first years. After this initial period, their prescription should become less restricted once there is substantial clinical experience. 2. The type of the national health system is an essential factor that should be taken into consideration in an HTA. There is great difference in cost-containing health policies according to whether the health care system is mainly public or private or mixed.

2.3 Survey – comments about the Web-Delphi process

- Excellent process. Many thanks for inviting.
- I don't understand, why you highlighted results, which are not (in many cases) the most frequent. I tried to find some rules in highlighting, but I failed. But if I look to the answers according to their percentage, I can find that with almost all topics responders agree or strongly agree, only 1 (No 23) has disagreement. So these topics are important for responders.
- Very helpful.
- Very good. No comments on that.
- Appropriate.
- It was a good and new experience working within the panel through online assessment and comments. I would expect that this form of process might become more important in the future.
- A more interactive Web-Delphi process would be much appreciated. For example, the users could interact anonymously. Also, each HTA dimension could have a more detailed description.

iMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2: Report with results from the Web-Delphi process of the HTA Bodies panel to identify which value dimensions should be considered in the “New multicriteria framework to facilitate Health Technology Assessment (HTA) organisations in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”

Grant Agreement No.:779312

Work Package: WP7, Task 2

Prepared by: IST (Universidade de Lisboa) and London School of Economics

Date: 29 August 2019

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1 Background information

IMPACT HTA is a research project looking at new and improved methods across 10 thematic research areas aiming at understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, and integrating clinical and economic data from different sources to improve methods in economic evaluation in the context of HTA and health system performance measurement.

Within IMPACT HTA work package 7 (WP7) research is taking place towards the development and testing of a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new medicines. This fits into the second task of WP7, whose aim is twofold: first, to structure a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, with these models reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers; and, second, to define alternative techniques and questioning protocols to build such a model. The starting point of Task 2 in terms of potential aspects of performance feeds from the results of Task 1 of the WP which has econometrically analysed the determinants of HTA recommendations by relying on secondary data. Following the completion of Task 2, the methodological framework will then be tested in practice through a number of case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies that will be carried out within Task 3 of WP7.

In order to build such a framework, two questions are currently being answered within Task 2: First, which aspects should be considered in a novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis? And second, which of those aspects are fundamental for that evaluation?

In order to address the first question, you kindly participated in a Web-Delphi process. The objective of this report is to provide you with an overview of the aggregated Web-Delphi results for all panels, and also more detailed results for your own stakeholder panel (HTA Bodies).

Regarding the general features of the already developed Web-Delphi process, the views of a mix of a large and diverse number of stakeholders were collected in separate panels (Panel 1: Payers and policy-makers; Panel 2: HTA bodies; Panel 3: Health care professionals; Panel 4: Patients and carers; Panel 5: Scientific experts and methodologists; and Panel 6: Industry) regarding which are the most relevant aspects that should be taken as value dimensions to evaluate new medicines on a common value basis. The complete list of aspects (24 in total) and their respective description are listed in Table

1. As described above, these aspects were derived from analysis that took place in the earlier task of this WP.

Participants were asked to specify their level of agreement or disagreement, on a 5-level scale ('Strongly Disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neither Agree nor Disagree', 'Agree', 'Strongly Agree'), about the relevance of each of the 24 listed aspects, by reflecting on the following statement: 'This aspect should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis'. For each aspect, participants could always select the option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' and leave additional comments. For each aspect there was a brief description of their substantive meaning.

This Web-Delphi panel included a total of two rounds that took place between February 5th – February 15th and February 19th – March 1st, 2019, respectively. The overall Web-Delphi process was divided across six panels that ran in parallel, with each panel gathering participants' views from a specific stakeholder group. The aim of the first round was to collect the initial views of each participant of the panel regarding what is the relevance of the 24 aspects when evaluating new medicines on a common value basis (e.g. on a multidimensional value score basis). The aim of the second round was for the participants of each panel to access an anonymous summary of their panel's overall responses from the first round and have the opportunity to maintain or revise their previous individual responses in terms of the inclusion or exclusions of the 24 aspects.

Following the two Web-Delphi rounds, a survey to participants collected comments on both the final results of their panel and the Web-Delphi process itself. Additionally, the panels of 'HTA bodies' and 'Patients and carers' were questioned about one of the aspects separately ('Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of a medicine's clinical trials') because it was not included in the Web-Delphi rounds. The survey took place between March 21st and April 1st, 2019. Following the Web-Delphi, a facilitated workshop was organized in April, with 11 participants representing all stakeholder groups for the purpose of reviewing and validating (for instance, interpreting, discussing and adjusting) the results of the Web-Delphi process.

Information regarding the number of participants in each panel for each round is shown in Table 2, and the aggregated voting final results for all Web-Delphi participants are shown in Table 3.

Following further research conducted by the WP7 team, a new stage will start soon as part of Task 2: all Web-Delphi participants (which previously had been divided into 6 separate stakeholder panels) will be invited to participate together in an overall web-Delphi to provide their final views about how

fundamental is to include each selected aspect in the novel framework. All participants will view the aspects' results from the first Web-Delphi and of the Decision Conferencing processes, for several of which no consensus was reached regarding their inclusion or exclusion in the novel framework, and will be invited to state their views regarding how fundamental each aspect is for the evaluation of drugs on a common basis. This Web-Delphi will be launched in September.

The next section of this report presents the results of the HTA Bodies panel, summarising the results of the first and second rounds, together with the results of the survey including the comments received to the final results of the panel and to the Web-Delphi process.

Thank you again for your collaboration.

Table 1. List of aspects examined in the Web-Delphi and brief description.

Aspect	Description
Severity of the disease	The condition's/ indication's degree of seriousness in respect to mortality and morbidity-derived disability.
Unmet need of the disease	The availability of medical interventions for the indication of interest, which could relate to methods of diagnosis, prevention or treatment.
Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Number of cases of the disease at present or number of new cases that develop, e.g. prevalence of the disease (i.e. proportion of a population that have the disease at a point in time) or incidence of the disease (i.e. rate at which new disease cases occur in a population during a specified period).
Medicine's impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and complications.
Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.
Medicine's adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse outcomes occurring when a medicine is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.
Medicine's tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.
Medicine's contraindications of use	Any risk and safety factors that act as a reason for a medicine not to be used by a patient.
Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Potential risks associated with the use of the medicine in regards to specific patient sub-populations with particular characteristics.
Medicine's mechanism of action	The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).
Medicine's spill-over effects	R&D positive externalities (i.e. beneficial follow-on external effects) that can lead to the development of subsequent innovation or new indication in review or clinical development, e.g. new medicines or new indication approvals.
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.
Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Any risk reduction in transmitting and developing the disease under consideration or any other disease within the broader population.
Medicine's economic impact	Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.
Medicine's affordability	Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.
Medicine's efficiency	The medicine's value-for-money in terms of resource allocation, e.g. the additional cost needed to gain an extra unit of health outcome, i.e. Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants and personnel, detection bias due to ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.
Disease duration	The average length of time the disease is present, e.g. Chronic vs Incurable.
Disease age of onset	The average age at which an individual acquires, develops, or first experiences a condition or symptoms of a disease or disorder, e.g. children.
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity.
Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with cultural, political and stakeholder acceptability and participation, including any legal barriers.
Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Refers to whether the aim, i.e. targeted action of the medicine is preventive, symptomatic (relief) or curative.

Table 2. Number of participants per panel of stakeholder group, across each round of the Web-Delphi process and in the final survey.

Panel (Stakeholder group)	Invited	# participants (round 1)	# participants (round 2)	# participants (survey)
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HTA bodies	33	29	28	19
Scientific experts and methodologists	46	42	38	23
Patients and carers	26	22	19	13
Industry	40	31	29	14
Total	195	167	153	90

Table 3. Final voting results for all Web-Delphi participants (aggregated results from the 6 panels).

Aspect/ Level of agreement or disagreement	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neither Agree or Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree	Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Total
1 - Severity of the disease	1%	3%	4%	24%	69%	0%	153
2 - Unmet need of the disease	1%	2%	3%	20%	72%	1%	153
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1%	11%	16%	42%	29%	0%	153
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	0%	0%	0%	18%	82%	0%	153
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	0%	0%	1%	22%	78%	0%	153
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	0%	0%	1%	22%	77%	0%	153
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	0%	1%	5%	39%	56%	0%	153
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0%	2%	7%	49%	42%	0%	153
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	1%	11%	20%	44%	24%	0%	153
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	0%	10%	27%	41%	22%	0%	153
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	4%	21%	39%	25%	11%	0%	153
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	5%	12%	29%	42%	12%	1%	153
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1%	5%	20%	52%	24%	0%	153
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0%	1%	7%	39%	54%	0%	153
15 - Medicine's economic impact	0%	5%	9%	35%	52%	0%	153
16 - Medicine's affordability	2%	6%	11%	39%	41%	1%	153
17 - Medicine's efficiency	1%	3%	3%	32%	61%	0%	153
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	0%	2%	10%	49%	39%	0%	106
19 - Disease duration	1%	10%	30%	45%	14%	1%	153

20 - Disease age of onset	1%	15%	30%	44%	10%	0%	153
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0%	5%	14%	54%	26%	1%	153
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1%	3%	19%	47%	30%	0%	153
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	8%	24%	36%	20%	7%	5%	153
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	2%	16%	24%	42%	16%	0%	153

2 Panel results: HTA Bodies

2.1 Web-Delphi – first round versus second round results

2.1.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 4. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) about the relevance of each of the 23 proposed aspects at the end of the first round (n=29 participants) versus the end of the second round (28 participants). Note: D = Disagree, A = Agree

Aspect/ Level of agreement per round	Round 1 - Strongly D	Round 2 - Strongly D	Round 1 - D	Round 2 - D	Round 1 - Neither A nor D	Round 2 - Neither A nor D	Round 1 - A	Round 2 - A	Round 1 - Strongly A	Round 2 - Strongly A	Round 1 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer	Round 2 - Don't know/ Don't want to answer
1 - Severity of the disease	3%	4%	7%	4%	7%	4%	17%	21%	66%	68%		
2 - Unmet need of the disease	3%	4%			3%	4%	28%	29%	66%	64%		
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)			21%	25%	17%	11%	28%	32%	34%	32%		
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality					3%		17%	11%	79%	89%		
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity					3%		21%	21%	76%	79%		
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life					3%	4%	17%	18%	79%	79%		
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile					3%	7%	24%	18%	72%	75%		
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients					10%	11%	34%	25%	55%	64%		
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use			7%	11%	34%	32%	24%	21%	34%	36%		
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions			7%	7%	31%	32%	31%	29%	31%	32%		
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	7%	7%	24%	25%	24%	32%	28%	21%	17%	14%		
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	3%	7%	14%	18%	45%	39%	31%	32%	7%	4%		
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients			3%	4%	34%	39%	45%	43%	17%	14%		

14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community					3%		48%	50%	48%	50%		
15 - Medicine's economic impact					3%	7%	31%	21%	66%	71%		
16 - Medicine's affordability	3%	4%			3%	4%	41%	43%	52%	50%		
17 - Medicine's efficiency			3%	4%	3%	4%	21%	21%	72%	71%		
18 - Disease duration			3%	4%	31%	32%	41%	43%	24%	21%		
19 - Disease age of onset	3%	4%	10%	7%	31%	29%	38%	46%	17%	14%		
20 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care			10%	4%	7%	7%	45%	54%	34%	32%	3%	4%
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues			7%	7%	17%	14%	41%	46%	34%	32%		
22 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	14%	14%	28%	29%	28%	32%	21%	14%	7%	7%	3%	4%
23 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	3%	4%	7%	4%	28%	32%	38%	39%	24%	21%		

2.1.2 Participants' comments first round

Aspect 1 - Severity of the disease

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This is duplicative of the more precise measures in items 4,5 and 6 below.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All of the questions/answers below are actually context specific - ie grading may significantly differ case by case.

Aspect 2 - Unmet need of the disease

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The fact that no treatment works currently is no reason to waste resources if the new treatment doesn't work either.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need for a precise definition please. Not independent of the severity of the disease. For example, high unmet need in current arthritis, but one may consider that the present armentarium + physical exercise is enough. Only insofar as the medication is effective in improving survival/morbidity/HRQOL.

Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> This may affect the conduct of trials and the quality of the evidence base. Equity considerations may lead to modified decision-processes, but should not mean that a drug for a small population is given preference over an equally cost-effective drug for a large population. One needs to accept more uncertainty with truly rare conditions, but there are a lot of rare conditions, so over-emphasizing this can lead to a lot of opportunity cost.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rare diseases sometimes need other criteria when evaluating
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not independent of the severity of the disease and level of unmet need. Is last line metastatic cancer of whatever (with a small number of patients) the same as orphan diseases?

Aspect 5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Especially on severe morbidity.
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Aspect 6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This should be measured by a comprehensive indicator such as the QALY to avoid duplication with morbidity, mortality and 'economic' benefits.
----------------	---

Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only as a component of the measure of health benefit.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This should be captured by the effects on morbidity and HRQOL.

Aspect 8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only insofar as it affects the cost-effectiveness ratio through increasing the probability of patient benefit.
----------------------------	--

Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Again, only if it affects cost-effectiveness. • Contraindicated populations are not affected by a decision to reimburse a medicine (or not). They cannot have it either way.
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Aspect 10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As above. (Again, only if it affects cost-effectiveness*)
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Aspect 11 - Medicine's mechanism of action

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I don't really care if a medication has an "exciting" or "novel" or "groundbreaking" approach. I'm really only interested in whether it is effective in improving survival/HRQOL etc.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When there is no substantial benefit attached, lower value.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If new mechanism

Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there are future benefits, then the manufacturer will invest to achieve them. If the government wants to encourage this there are better ways than by paying high prices for ineffective medicines just to keep a company in funds.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • According to the definition provided, I would not consider it so important. New indications are assessed when submitted.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Too much bets on the future.

Aspect 13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Only as part of the measurement of effectiveness. • In my opinion is very difficult to quantify the convenience of a new administration form for patients but should be possible to do it.
----------------------------	---

Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no general answer on this one, as it is context -specific. Most western societies see no reason to give priority to people of working age in terms of access to health care. In countries with different economic and social priorities it might be more relevant. The QALY includes individual assessment of the impact of health on work activities, hence the familiar argument about the duplicative effect of adding 'productivity' benefits.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the difference with affordability? Needs to be clarified please although I think I know what the difference is. If economic impact is

	broad impact on productivity, then in some cases I would strongly agree (example of long term auto-immune diseases).
Strongly agree	• Economic impact is defined very broadly and is not in line with a health systems perspective.

Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Strongly disagree	• How can this be a measurable criterion? It is a subjective concept and setting arbitrary figures does not help.
Agree	• This has to be balanced against opportunity cost. If the ICER is e.g. £9k, then this is really an implementation problem for the service, and may require phasing approaches. If the ICER is £50k, then this helps to surface the scale of the opportunity cost.

Aspect 17 - Medicine's efficiency

Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Useful as a benchmark. • This should capture most of the other points listed! • Always important when having scarce resources, how should the health care sector allocate?
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Aspect 19 - Disease duration

Neither agree nor disagree	• Only insofar as it affects cost-effectiveness.
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Aspect 21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For me that is part of the economic impact. • All this should be a routine part of the cost-effectiveness assessment.
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Aspect 22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can be important but in my experience, it is rare for such aspects to be associated with individual medicines rather than health care programs.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • These are political rather than HTA decisions and any suggestions may be biased - example - IVF may be ethically rejected in conservative country, nevertheless should be positively evaluated based on scientific evidence. • If using an objective system, then it should intrinsically be equitable. If there are health disparities within a society (e.g. race) these should be addressed by other mechanisms, then distorting the HTA.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This issue is particularly difficult to address; yes ethical considerations may be very critical in some cases.

Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equity issues deserve serious consideration. Personal prejudices of politicians should be kept out of the process. • Too much political interference in HTA as it is. Politicians should set policy and process, and the outcomes should follow on from those processes. When politicians get involved in specific cases it generally leads to poor decision making, because they are too influenced by the media and need for re-election.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This would depend on each government requirements, that sometimes are not explicitly stated, so in my opinion this aspect isn't important.
Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not sure I understand what it means.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antibiotics.

Aspect 24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It should be about the cost-effectiveness/efficiency regardless of the type of intervention.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More concerned about the overall health impact than whether it's preventative or curative.

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mostly important is if medicines are curative, but this could also be reflected in other aspects such as the effect on mortality.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is a bit secondary or unclear: do you refer to target population, thus size, thus affordability? Or other issues?

2.1.3 Participants' comments second round

Aspect 1 - Severity of the disease

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considered that what matters here at this point is the condition itself, and not the impact of the medicine on morbidity and mortality, which will be assessed according to other criteria. • I still don't strongly agree with this because some conditions may not be particularly serious but still have a large impact on quality of life for a large number of people.
Strongly Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ceteris paribus, this should still be a factor to be considered. We would target resource to a severe condition over a less severe one, but not if we gained fewer QALYs.

Aspect 2 - Unmet need of the disease

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Still need a clear definition of unmet need, with some sort of scoring. • Considered that what matters here at this point is the condition itself, and not the impact of the medicine on the condition, which will be assessed according to other criteria.
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Aspect 3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not the rarity of the disease as such should be a criterion, but the severity of the rare disease. • Another concern here, is that pharma will use the tactic of market segmentation to create more "rare" diseases, if it is over-incentivised.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Same comment on rarity as for unmet need. Rarity is looked at but then may not be the main dimension for decision making. • Considered that it's an important factor, but more important should be the effect of the medicine on the condition.

Aspect 5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity

Strongly agree	• I would expect this to be captured under impact on health-related quality of life so I don't regard it as a separate criterion.
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Aspect 7 - Medicine's adverse events profile

Strongly Agree	• I would expect this to be captured under impact on health-related quality of life (as disutility) so I don't regard it as a separate criterion.
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Aspect 9 - Medicine's contraindications of use

Neither agree nor disagree	• Contraindicated populations should be considered in the evaluation because it defines the population that should not receive the new medicine. For the contraindicated population, the medicine cannot be reimbursed. Therefore, medicine's contraindications will not affected a decision to reimbursement.
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Aspect 10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions

Agree	• Most of the time, the information about precautions and warning helps to define the specific population which the new treatment has benefit. For this reason, this information should be considered in the evaluation.
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Aspect 11 - Medicine's mechanism of action

Neither agree nor disagree	• What it matters is the impact of medicine on effectiveness and safety, not its mechanism of action.
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Aspect 12 - Medicine's spill-over effects

Strongly disagree	• At the previous round i filled incorrectly. In my opinion medicine's spill-over effects should not be considered.
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Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I don't feel HTA is the correct tool for this purpose. Government industrial strategy and investment in research and development funds would be more appropriate? And probably better targeted.
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Aspect 13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It's a very critical aspect. Convenience for patients should be taken into account but it shouldn't have the same importance as other aspects like mortality and safety.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Depends on situation but could be a key factor affecting usage and thus ultimately effectiveness in practice.

Aspect 15 - Medicine's economic impact

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I have changed to neither agree or disagree. If the only consequence of including this is to direct resources to the working population then it would only apply where this was considered a legitimate goal.
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Aspect 16 - Medicine's affordability

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affordability has some bearing on what is considered to be acceptable value for money in a healthcare system but budget impact for a specific medicine is not so relevant for decision making. Important but I have not put to strongly agree as I think this should not be the key focus in the HTA decision but come in later decision making.
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Aspect 19 - Disease duration

Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> It is unclear whether this is intended to prioritise diseases that are long-term, regardless of severity, over acute diseases that may or may not be severe/life threatening.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considered that what matters here at this point is the duration of the condition, and not the impact of the medicine on the condition.

Aspect 20 - Disease age of onset

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Considered that what matters here at this point is disease age of onset of the condition, and not the impact of the medicine on the condition.
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Aspect 21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consider that this relates to the impact of medicine on organization, that should be taken into consideration.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • I think this is a key facet of HTA.

Aspect 22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It might be difficult to address.
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Aspect 23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support

Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In a publicly funded healthcare system without unlimited resources, it is legitimate to consider the political priorities overtly set by elected politicians.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification of what this value dimension means is vague/confusing.

2.2 Survey – comments to the final results of the panel

- With the paradigm shift in understanding what constitutes health and how it is protected, maintained and delivered, assessing value of a single medicine might not be relevant at all in the near future. Methods to assess the value of disease/health management "service" (in which a drug is just one of several components in this service delivery) would need to be quickly prioritised for development and further improved. But maybe with the current HTA approaches we are assessing BENEFITS, and not value, of medicines? :) Context within which a drug is delivered (and marketed) will become more and more important.
- Some criteria overlap. For instance "medicines economic impact" and "medicine's efficiency". For this reason I responded disagree on medicine's efficiency, because I believe that the economic impact, combined with evidence on effectiveness and relative importance to patients, level of unmet need, impact of disease on mortality, morbidity and QoL tells all about the efficiency. I am not in favour of reducing the efficiency to cost-per-QALY and call this the proxy for "value for money" (as in the definition provided). For an MCDA it would not work to put all these criteria in one framework because of the overlap.
- Uncertainty in evidence due to lower-quality regulatory submissions for medicines approved on an accelerated basis.

- Seems comprehensive. Can't think of anything else to add. Perhaps need to think however about personalised medicines and ATMPs at some point too and see if the criteria will work equally well for them.
- From the methodological point within SR it will be important to use GRADE criteria to assess quality (certainty) of evidence.
- Well results are not that surprising! Now the items are identified, the following question is that some items, like unmet needs, require some specification because they are disease and treatment dependent.
- Many of the aspects listed were components of health-related quality of life and would be incorporated into a conventional cost utility analysis. Cost utility analysis has a single maximand, health, usually measured in QALYs. Moving away from this model only becomes necessary if there are non-monetisable maximands that need to be traded off against health. Of the aspects listed, only patient convenience truly fell into this category (unless that could be monetised). Arguably it might be appropriate to sacrifice health in order to correct real or perceived inequalities (which is where severity/unmet need/rarity might be relevant). Perhaps it might be appropriate to include the environmental impact of health care interventions. It might be appropriate to forgo health in order to limit damage to the environment. Other than that I struggle to think of anything else that might be relevant.
- We did not identify additional aspects not mentioned in this webinar. However, a common ground was that the risk of double counting was identified when evaluating the different aspects. Another interesting aspect of discussion was how the decision makers judge which weight that should be applied.
- I think that, regarding the quality of evidence, there are other aspects that should be considered in the evaluation and not only the risk of bias. For example, if the comparison of the effect of the intervention of interest and the comparator is not made directly (head-to-head) but indirectly, the quality of evidence should be rated considering the magnitude of the differences between populations of patients, co-interventions, and measures of outcomes. Another example is the use of surrogate outcomes. It should exist a strong and consistent association between surrogate outcomes and relevant outcomes so that can be considered.

2.3 Survey – comments about the Web-Delphi process

- The process appears to have captured the primary elements.
- I would be interested to see the results according to the different stakeholders, if you performed Delphi panels for other stakeholders as well (patients, industry, decision makers). The definitions of the different criteria were not always 100% clear; also the implications of "agreeing" are not clear. You can agree that a criterion should be considered, but not that it should get a high weight. Some respondents highlighted this in their comments when they "agreed", but you don't know whether other respondents maybe answered 'disagree' when making the same reflection.
- Worked quite well.
- Very straightforward to participate.
- Very understandable procedure, easy to apply, consensus quickly reached.
- I have no specific comments, this is has been an interesting process. Good luck with your project.
- Congratulation; excellent concept, view, clarity and quality.
- Simple to use.

- It is annoying that have had to complete the box above 3 times, due to the log in timing out before the text was saved.
- The Web-Delphi process was great! I am very grateful for the invitation and I hope that I have been able to help.

2.4 Survey – aspect ‘Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine’s clinical trials’

2.4.1 Synthesis of level of agreement or disagreement

Table 5. Level of agreement or disagreement (%) about the relevance of the aspect ‘Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials’ (19 participants).

Proposed aspect	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree	Don't know/Don't want to answer
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	5%	5%	5%	16%	68%	

2.4.2 Participants’ comments

Aspect 18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

Strongly disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This is an important consideration in assessing the clinical effectiveness and patient benefit from a medicine but it is not a separate value dimension. The quality and reliability of trial design should be taken into account in selecting the most likely level of effectiveness, and the range of any sensitivity analysis around that, used in an HTA. The same assessment of quality should be applied to all data used in HTA. Taking clinical trial results at face value and then applying a further decision criterion to reduce their weighting in a decision might sometimes come up with the same result, but would be less transparent and less easy to justify. Trials for regulatory purposes, even if designed to FDA and EMA standards, do not always provide the best data for HTA, but usually provide an adequate basis for decision-modelling. If trials are obviously flawed then the medicine should not receive marketing approval let alone be considered for reimbursement.
Disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is risk of bias that one is always vigilant to avoid, how much bias would necessary for it to be considered?

Neither agree nor disagree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To the extent that such flaws can be accounted for in the analysis they should be. The influence of any potential bias should be explored in sensitivity analyses. It is not a factor that should be considered independently of the analysis, it only casts doubt on the reliability of it.
Agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Risk of bias is important. However, from my point of view it is not taken into consideration to a large extent in health economic evaluations if the number of Clinical trials are scarce and the evaluator have the make an assessment on limited information.
Strongly agree	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This should be a linchpin of any strong HTA process, as this is a cornerstone of systematic review methods. • I've put strongly agree, as this is undoubtedly important. However, I had thought that this would be picked up during the assessment of the other aspects already listed. I think I would prefer it to be so, because it is an aspect of the studies, rather than the medicine itself, and as such differs from the other aspects listed. • We have to consider not only the size of the effect but also the level of evidence based upon acceptable and validated methodology to minimise bias • Important for assessment of the validity of clinical studies and results. • This is the starting point of the clinical assessment. My statement doesn't mean that this would lead systematically to a yes or no answer, but may lead to restrictions in coverage recommending, request for post-launch RWE and conservative-conditional coverage. • I consider that risk of bias it's a very important aspect that definitively has to be analysed in the evaluation of new medicines. Nowadays, there are some methodologies to assess the quality of evidence that gives us a rating of confidence in effect estimates of a new medicine. The quality of evidence should be taken into account in the decision-making process.

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2: Report with results from the second Web-Delphi process to identify which value dimensions should be considered in the “New multicriteria framework to facilitate Health Technology Assessment (HTA) organisations in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis”

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Prepared by: IST (Universidade de Lisboa) and London School of Economics

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1 Background information

IMPACT HTA is a research project looking at new and improved methods across 10 thematic research areas aiming at understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, and integrating clinical and economic data from different sources to improve methods in economic evaluation in the context of HTA and health system performance measurement.

Within IMPACT HTA work package 7 (WP7) research is taking place towards the development and testing of a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new medicines. This fits into the second task of WP7, whose aim is twofold: first, to structure a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines in the context of HTA, reflecting what is relevant for HTA agency decision-makers; and, second, to define alternative techniques and questioning protocols to build such a model. The starting point of Task 2 in terms of potential aspects of performance feeds from the results of WP7 Task 1 which has econometrically analysed the determinants of HTA recommendations by relying on secondary data. Following the completion of Task 2, the methodological framework will then be tested in practice through case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies that will be carried out in Task 3 of WP7.

In order to build such a framework, the following question is currently being answered in Task 2: First, which aspects should be considered in a novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis?

In order to address this first question, you kindly participated in two Web-Delphi processes. During the initial Web-Delphi process, a lot of useful information from six stakeholder groups was generated about which aspects should be included in a novel framework. In this process, you had the opportunity to provide and revise your views in light of the responses of the rest participants of your panel (i.e., payers and policymakers, HTA bodies, healthcare professionals, scientific experts and methodologists, patients and carers, or industry). Subsequently, a decision conference involving 11 stakeholder participants was held in April 2019. In this decision conference, participants reviewed and discussed the results of the initial Web-Delphi process for assisting their interpretation and validation regarding the consideration of aspects within the novel framework. However, for some aspects there was no group consensus about their inclusion or exclusion, while suggestions for the consideration of additional new aspects also emerged during this decision conference.

Accordingly, the second Web-Delphi process was focused only on a few aspects for which doubts still subsisted in the light of the combined results of the initial Web-Delphi and the decision conference. Specifically, you were presented with a list of 16 aspects and asked whether they should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis, by specifying a choice between ‘Yes’ or ‘No’. For each aspect, you could always select the option 'Don't Know/Don't want to answer' and leave additional comments.

The first nine aspects had already been studied in the initial Web-Delphi questionnaire. The remaining seven aspects were new (having emerged during the initial Web-Delphi and/or the decision conference). An overview of the results of the previous stages of this collaborative process (i.e. initial Web-Delphi, decision conference, and combined results) was available for your consultation during the second Web-Delphi, presented in Table 1. Finally, for each aspect there was a brief description of their substantive meaning, as well as the results of the initial Web-Delphi (if applicable) and decision conference, and the combination of the two. This information is presented in Table 2.

In the summary results from the initial Web-Delphi and from the decision conference (Table 1), the classification “include”, “exclude”, or “doubt” were used in accordance to the rules described in Appendix 1.

Table 1. Results overview of the previous Delphi-Decision Conferencing processes regarding aspects' consideration in the novel value framework: initial Web-Delphi result, decision conference result, and combined result.

	Initial Web-Delphi result	Decision conference result	Combined result
Aspect			
1 - Severity of the disease	Include	Include	Include
2 - Unmet need of the disease	Include	Include	Include
3 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
4 - Medicine's impact on mortality	Include	Include	Include
5 - Medicine's impact on morbidity	Include	Include	Include
6 - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Include	Include	Include
7 - Medicine's adverse events profile	Include	Doubt	Doubt
8 - Medicine's tolerability to patients	Include	Exclude	Doubt
9 - Medicine's contraindications of use	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
10 - Medicine's special warnings and precautions	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
11 - Medicine's mechanism of action	Exclude	Doubt	Doubt
12 - Medicine's spill-over effects	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
13 - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt

	Initial Web-Delphi result	Decision conference result	Combined result
14 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Include	Include	Include
15 - Medicine's economic impact	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
16 - Medicine's affordability	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
17 - Medicine's efficiency	Include	Include	Include
18 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Include	Doubt	Doubt
19 - Disease duration	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
20 - Disease age of onset	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
21 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
22 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
23 - Alignment of the medicine-indication pair with leadership goals and governance requirements, including political support	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
24 - Medicine's therapeutic positioning	Exclude	Exclude	Exclude
New aspects suggested in the initial Web-Delphi			
Quality of evidence	–	Exclude	Exclude
Surrogate outcomes	–	Exclude	Exclude
Patient feedback/User experience	–	Exclude	Exclude

	Initial Web-Delphi result	Decision conference result	Combined result
Specialist prescribing for the first years	–	Exclude	Exclude
Type of National Health System	–	Exclude	Exclude
Adherence to treatment	–	Exclude	Exclude
Medicine's environmental impact	–	Doubt	Doubt
Medicine's "value of hope"	–	Doubt	Doubt
Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	–	Doubt	Doubt
New aspects suggested in the decision conference			
Medicines' impact on patient functionality	–	Include	Doubt
Medicine's time for treatment effect	–	Include	Doubt
Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	–	Include	Doubt
Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	–	Include	Doubt

Note: Blue highlighted rows correspond to the aspects whose inclusion in the framework was classified to be in “doubt”, forming the set of aspects to be studied in the second Web-Delphi questionnaire.

Table 2. List of aspects examined in the second Web-Delphi: brief description and process information made available to participants.

Aspects for which no conclusion had been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference
<p>Medicine's adverse events profile (aspect 7 in the initial Web-Delphi)</p> <p>Description</p> <p>The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards (adjusted according to initial Web-Delphi comments).</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial Web-Delphi result: 95% of agreement and 1% of disagreement. - Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus). - Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).
<p>Medicine's tolerability to patients (aspect 8 in the initial Web-Delphi)</p> <p>Description</p> <p>The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial Web-Delphi result: 92% of agreement and 2% of disagreement. - Decision conference result: consensual exclusion. - Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).
<p>Medicine's mechanism of action (aspect 11 in the initial Web-Delphi)</p> <p>Description</p> <p>The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initial Web-Delphi result: 36% of agreement and 25% of disagreement. - Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus). - Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).

Medicine's ease and convenience for patients (aspect 13 in the initial Web-Delphi)**Description**

Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.

Process information

Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.

- Initial Web-Delphi result: 75% of agreement and 5% of disagreement.
- Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus).
- Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).

Medicine's economic impact (aspect 15 in the initial Web-Delphi)**Description**

Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.

Process information

Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.

- Initial Web-Delphi result: 86% of agreement and 5% of disagreement.
- Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus).
- Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).

Medicine's affordability (aspect 16 in the initial Web-Delphi)**Description**

Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.

Process information

Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.

- Initial Web-Delphi result: 80% of agreement and 8% of disagreement.
- Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus).
- Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).

Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (aspect 18 in the initial Web-Delphi)**Description**

Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants

and personnel, detection bias due to ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.

Process information

Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.

- Initial Web-Delphi result: 88% of agreement and 2% of disagreement.
- Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus).
- Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).

Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (aspect 21 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Description

The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).

Process information

Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.

- Initial Web-Delphi result: 80% of agreement and 5% of disagreement.
- Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus).
- Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).

Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (aspect 22 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Description

The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity (adjusted according to initial Web-Delphi comments).

Process information

Aspect for which no conclusion has been reached following the initial Web-Delphi and subsequent decision conference, with regard to whether it should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines on a common basis.

- Initial Web-Delphi result: 77% of agreement and 4% of disagreement.
- Decision conference result: doubt (no consensus).
- Combined result: doubt (to be addressed in this second Web-Delphi).

New aspects suggested either at the end of the initial Web-Delphi or during the subsequent decision conference.

Medicine's environmental impact

Description

The environmental impact of the medicine (e.g. because of manufacturing, distribution, etc.).

<p>Process information</p> <p>New aspect suggested at the end of the initial Web-Delphi and considered during the subsequent decision conference.</p>
<p>Medicine's "value of hope"</p> <p>Description</p> <p>The potential of the medicine to offer hope to patient due a potential large benefit that is not sufficiently represented by the median or mean benefit, e.g. the likelihood of a long survival tail, even though the average life expectancy might be equal to or lower than that provided by standard therapy.</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>New aspect suggested at the end of the initial Web-Delphi and considered during the subsequent decision conference.</p>
<p>Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>Description</p> <p>The potential of the medicine to act as a "bridge therapy" by keeping the patient alive so that they can benefit from better treatment options, e.g. until bone marrow transplant or development of future technologies.</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>New aspect suggested at the end of the initial Web-Delphi and considered during the subsequent decision conference.</p>
<p>Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Impact of the medicine on the ability of patient to function socially in a variety of activities (as implied by improvements in functionality).</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>New aspect suggested during the decision conference.</p>
<p>Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Time for the medicine's treatment effect to take place (e.g. fast drug action vs slow drug action).</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>New aspect suggested during the decision conference.</p>
<p>Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p> <p>Description</p> <p>Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration).</p> <p>Process information</p> <p>New aspect suggested during the decision conference.</p>

Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

Description

The degree of reversibility (or irreversibility) of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (e.g. reversible adverse effects vs irreversible adverse effects).

Process information

New aspect suggested during the decision conference.

2 Second Web-Delphi results

The main objective of this report is to provide you with an overview of the aggregated results of the second Web-Delphi process.

The second Web-Delphi process included a total of two rounds that took place between September 25th – October 6th and October 9th – October 20th, 2019, respectively. The aim of the first round was to collect your initial views (as well as the views of all participants) regarding whether each of the 16 aspects should be considered when evaluating new medicines on a common value basis (e.g. using a multidimensional value score). The aim of the second round was to provide you with an anonymous summary of the overall responses (and comments) of all participants from the first round, giving you the opportunity to maintain or revise your initial responses in the light of the overall group's opinion. Note that in this Web-Delphi you took part in a single panel with all the 153 participants from all stakeholder groups that completed the initial Web-Delphi (including payers and policymakers, HTA bodies, healthcare professionals, scientific experts and methodologists, patients and carers, and industry). At the end of the second round, you were also invited to leave any further comments regarding this second Web-Delphi process.

Information regarding the number of participants in each round is shown in Table 3. The voting results per aspect (for round 1 and round 2) of the second Web-Delphi are shown in Table 4, and the voting results per aspect of round 2 are additionally illustrated in Figure 1.

Finally, the full set of participants' comments (round 1 and round 2), as well as the responses from the open ended-question regarding the Web-Delphi process are available in Appendix 2.

Thank you again for your time and valuable input!

Table 3. Number of participants in each round of the second Web-Delphi process

No. invited participants	No. participants Round 1	No. participants Round 2
153	118	102

Table 4. Voting results per aspect (for round 1 and round 2) of the second Web-Delphi.

Aspect	Round 1			Round 2			Round 2 - Round 1 difference		
	Yes	No	DN/DWA	Yes	No	DN/DWA	Yes	No	DN/DWA
Medicine's adverse events profile (aspect 7 in the initial Web-Delphi)	92%	7%	1%	92%	8%	0%	0%	1%	-1%
Medicine's tolerability to patients (aspect 8 in the initial Web-Delphi)	83%	15%	2%	89%	10%	1%	6%	-5%	-1%
Medicine's mechanism of action (aspect 11 in the initial Web-Delphi)	34%	61%	5%	30%	67%	3%	-4%	6%	-2%
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients (aspect 13 in the initial Web-Delphi)	76%	20%	3%	78%	18%	4%	2%	-2%	1%
Medicine's economic impact (aspect 15 in the initial Web-Delphi)	89%	10%	1%	90%	9%	1%	1%	-1%	0%
Medicine's affordability (aspect 16 in the initial Web-Delphi)	71%	25%	3%	78%	20%	2%	7%	-5%	-1%
Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (aspect 18 in the initial Web-Delphi)	86%	12%	2%	91%	8%	1%	5%	-4%	-1%
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (aspect 21 in the initial Web-Delphi)	70%	28%	2%	75%	24%	2%	5%	-4%	0%
Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (aspect 22 in the initial Web-Delphi)	78%	19%	3%	81%	16%	3%	3%	-3%	0%
Medicine's environmental impact	41%	54%	5%	40%	55%	5%	-1%	1%	0%

Aspect	Round 1			Round 2			Round 2 - Round 1 difference		
	Yes	No	DN/DWA	Yes	No	DN/DWA	Yes	No	DN/DWA
Medicine's "value of hope"	34%	61%	5%	29%	67%	4%	-5%	6%	-1%
Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	58%	36%	7%	57%	37%	6%	-1%	1%	-1%
Medicines' impact on patient functionality	81%	15%	4%	86%	11%	3%	5%	-4%	-1%
Medicine's time for treatment effect	50%	44%	6%	50%	46%	4%	0%	2%	-2%
Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	73%	25%	3%	78%	21%	1%	5%	-4%	-2%
Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	73%	25%	3%	76%	22%	2%	3%	-3%	-1%

DN/DWA: Don't know/ Don't want to answer

Figure 1. Aggregated voting results per aspect (round 2) of the second Web-Delphi.

DN/DWA: Don't know/ Don't want to answer

Appendix 1 - Rules adopted to summarise the combined Web-Delphi and decision conferencing results

Regarding the results from the initial Web-Delphi, a Delphi Net Agreement score (DNA) was calculated for each aspect using the following formula:

$$DNA = \%(SA+A) - f * \%(SD+D)$$

In which %(SA+A) is the Delphi concordance measured by summing the percentages of “strong agreement” and “agreement”, %(SD+D) is the Delphi discordance measured by summing the percentages of “strong disagreement” and “disagreement”, and f is the Discordance factor (≥ 1).

The DNA score was used to summarise the initial Web-Delphi panel results, with a f Discordance factor of 2 being adopted (giving to disagreement double the importance of agreement), leading the results classification by applying the following rules:

Table 5. Initial Web-Delphi process result classification

DNA ($f=2$)	Initial Web-Delphi panel results classification
>80%	Include
[50-80]	Doubt
<50%	Exclude

Regarding the results from the decision conferencing process, the following results classification was used based on the voting of each aspect:

Table 6. Decision conference result classification

Decision conferencing voting	Decision conference results classification
Consensual inclusion	Include
No consensus	Doubt
Consensual exclusion	Exclude

The new aspects proposed in the initial Web-Delphi were also subject to voting in the decision conference, and those that were not consensually excluded received the classification of “doubt”.

Additionally, any new aspects proposed in the decision conference received the classification of “doubt”. The procedure used to combine together the results from the initial Web-Delphi and the decision conference into an overall outcome was the following:

Table 7. Procedure used to combine the results from the initial Web-Delphi and from the decision conference

Initial Web-Delphi result	Decision conference result	Combined overall result outcome
Include	Include	Include
Include	Doubt	Doubt
Include	Exclude	Doubt
Doubt	Include	Include
Doubt	Doubt	Doubt
Doubt	Exclude	Exclude
Exclude	Include	Doubt
Exclude	Doubt	Doubt
Exclude	Exclude	Exclude

Appendix 2: Participants' comments

Participants' comments first round

Medicine's adverse events profile (aspect 7 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Should be to the extent that this has patient or economic impact. Do not have to repeat a full assessment of adverse events, this would duplicate what regulators have already done.</p> <p>I clicked yes, but only on a comparative basis, considering that the overall cost/benefit balance is positive.</p> <p>Medicine's adverse events profile - this tool is important to be evaluated especially for biosimilars (e.g. in country was decided to introduce one insulin analogue biosimilar and to switch all the patients that have to use original analogue insulin to that one, in 6 months, around 150 patients have reported different adverse events, which were not presented initially by manufacturer).</p> <p>This is an aspect of effectiveness and should be picked up by a proper measure of effectiveness. However, risk of catastrophic adverse events may be a separate consideration.</p> <p>Adverse events profile is part of safety evidence of new medicines. If there are mandatory aspects that should be considered in the assessment of new medicines, adverse events profile should be one of them.</p> <p>In order for adverse events to be considered routinely, the reporting system has to be improved. Lack of data on adverse events may appear in the decision model as negative adverse events which would be misleading. The safety analysis should present relevant findings regarding adverse events, but acknowledge that they may be incomplete.</p> <p>With care on double-counting, reporting accuracy, creating additional issues in terms of missing values/info, and in consideration to time frames required.</p> <p>Quality of life is certainly important for patients, even more so if they have a short prognosis.</p>
No	<p>This is a regulatory issue, however may be relevant if the HTA comparator is different to the regulatory comparator.</p> <p>This doesn't need to be separately identified. It will be captured by mortality/HRQOL etc. as a benefit. This doesn't add anything by being a separate category.</p> <p>AEs--should be captured but aggregated into negative QALYS.</p> <p>This should be part of aggregated health gain.</p>

	Isn't this more a question of whether the medicine is fit for purpose rather than a reimbursement issue? Is there an adherence component to this question? I would be more inclined to include if there was an impact from this that was included.
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's tolerability to patients (aspect 8 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Patient relevant - instruments like PRO CTCAE could be relevant.</p> <p>Yes, but only when applying it on a comparative basis. To rank two medicines, but would not use it as a criterion for a pure reimbursement decision.</p> <p>Tolerability should be considered since it gives us information about the safety of a new medicine. It is not desirable a new medicine with good efficacy results that cannot be used by patients because of its poor tolerability. On the other hand, it will be important to know if there is discontinuation of treatment due to adverse events. The treatment of these adverse events should be considered in the indirect costs of the new medicine. In conclusion, it is an important aspect, but not so much as adverse events profile (perhaps tolerability may be included in safety analysis).</p> <p>There might be variation between patients in tolerability. In my view, it should be considered as it can also help to estimate the possible impact on the use of alternative treatments for patients who do not tolerate the medicine and the budget impact. It is relevant information in a holistic approach, which is required in the evaluation of medicines.</p> <p>Compliance with treatment is fundamental to hope for a favorable effect of it. The reasons for poor compliance are to be anticipated by taking into account the patient's opinions regarding the appearance of the treatment, how it is taken, the useful and expected information about it, and the expected effect.</p> <p>Need to be careful not to end up double counting some aspects, in particular adverse events and tolerability are closely linked.</p> <p>A patient is far more likely to continue their treatment on a regular basis if it is tolerable.</p>
No	<p>Overlap with adverse event objective no clear distinction between tolerability and adverse event.</p> <p>This point has to be evaluated in more detailed analysis at the marketing authorization process.</p> <p>Again this will be captured by the usual measures. If a medicine is discontinued its benefits will reduce with time, its costs will reduce. If the reason for discontinuing is an adverse event that will already be captured. This doesn't add anything as a separate category.</p> <p>This will affect adherence and ultimately effectiveness. It should be considered as part of effectiveness.</p>

	<p>Tolerability--should be captured but as negative QALYs in disease model.</p> <p>This should be part of aggregated health gain (i.e. QALY gain).</p> <p>I would expect that tolerability to patients is an aspect that would vary among patients based on comorbidities and age.</p> <p>Again, is this a question of adherence? The tolerability is subjective so more a clinical question than cost question.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>Not sure whether this is not cover by the adverse events attribute.</p> <p>It is not clear what is meant by tolerability.</p>

Medicine's mechanism of action (aspect 11 in the initial Web-Delphi)

3	Comment
Yes	<p>Including scientific skills and innovation benefit to the whole society.</p> <p>Typically, we only care about the impact, not on how this is achieved. There are, however, several examples (e.g. antimicrobial resistance) where new modes of action have to be developed, so we should consider this item.</p> <p>Important as it can explain relevance of potential endpoints (e.g. cure for viruses), and long-term outcomes (e.g. tail for IO therapies in survival extrapolation). It also shows innovation and therefore important for scientific advances.</p>
No	<p>MOA per se not relevant, but the additional clinical benefit as consequence of the new MOA. This related clinical benefit is already captured under clinical effects.</p> <p>To the patient the mechanism is irrelevant. They only care if it works. The only reason to consider this, is the potential for future therapy development, and medication pricing is not the best way to stimulate R&D.</p> <p>Innovative mechanisms of action do have research value, but this is not the kind of value that should be remunerated by the healthcare budget. There are/should be other routes to reward innovation with potential future impact (R&D budgets for instance).</p> <p>Difficult to relate the monetary value to the mechanism of action of a new drug. An additional medicine with a new mechanism of action should instead be related to a less severe adverse event profile, facilitating administration or increase compliance.</p> <p>If this element is meant to capture level of innovativeness, I am not sure that the mechanism of action is the right way to define and measure it. It is unclear why payers should value innovative technologies per se if they don't have specific benefits to patients or others.</p> <p>MOA--not directly, but in disease model and potentially in QALY as a "process utility".</p> <p>This is process - we should be concentrating on the outcomes, which have value for the patients.</p>

	<p>I would not include "Mechanism of Action" per se in the evaluation, but somehow we could take into account whether the new MoA has "spillover effects", for instance.</p> <p>Not to the mechanism of action in itself, but to its effects. I think that the value of a health care treatment should relate to what it does to patients' health and welfare, not to how it does it.</p> <p>Considering the definition, this has to be a 'no' for the purpose of the evaluation; there are many effective drugs for which we have not many clues as to the actual MoA. This is very tricky and ought to be discussed with all stakeholders, particularly for areas like oncology or immuno-oncology, but not only; e.g., consider KCE or AIFA. For AIFA's algorithm, there are actually three key aspects in the algorithm, 1. the unmet --therapeutic-- need, the --added-- therapeutic value and the quality of evidence. The first two criteria are, indeed assessed with a five-score scale, from "maximum" to "absent", while the quality of evidence is assessed with GRADE, from "high" to "very low". Also, for rare diseases' drugs, AIFA takes into account the difficulty to conduct gold standard studies, etc. However, key element to achieving innovative designation has not been linked to the highest total score, e.g., adalimumab obtained a total score higher than cenegermin and daratumumab (I think the report was IQVIA, but could be wrong), but it was evaluated as conditionally innovative. It is unclear why AIFA scored the way it did, but perhaps because the molecule/drug addresses --multiple needs-- at the same time, in psoriasis and in arthritis, is effective, and is the cheapest of the biological medicines; besides, it is going generic in a few years. The aspect of 'multiple' needs is not touched upon here, and neither was 'cumulative effect'. So for AIFA not a real algorithm or even a guideline, more like arbitrary judgement, although there may well be sound grounds to measure such things...</p>
DK/DWA	<p>If MoA translates into a patient related benefit (efficacy, safety, tolerability etc.), this would already be captured in relevant aspects. Hence, MoA innovation would be a redundant aspect if objective is to value patient impact. On the other hand, it may be an objective to award and encourage innovation - perhaps with the expectation of future benefits in areas with limited innovation - and in such cases it would be meaningful to include MoA aspect in assessment.</p> <p>The criterion would need to be better defined - e.g.: a new MOA may benefit some patients who may not respond to existing therapies. -eventually this could fall under "unmet need"?</p>

Medicine's ease and convenience for patients (aspect 13 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Moving from invasive to an oral has important considerations for not just the patient, but also the health care system and infrastructure. It can also be part of the recognition of innovation.</p> <p>Similarly, only on a comparative basis, when trying to rank two therapeutics. But not for a sole reimbursement decision.</p>

	<p>In a study performed by KCE in the general public, it was found that two value criteria are considered very important to patients: impact on quality of life and impact on convenience of treatment.</p> <p>Yes, if they have an impact of compliance with the treatment.</p> <p>I would include as a dimension, but in order to "reward" it, there would be a need to have evidence on how "ease and convenience" leads to better outcomes.</p> <p>Provided this is captured by patients and not by doctors or assumed by the pharma company. Again, I think the impact of this is important.</p>
No	<p>Ease and convenience only matters when it translates into better outcomes or better efficiency of care delivery. But that is already considered in other variables.</p> <p>These will matter to patients (mostly to a lesser degree than outcomes), but will be already captured in HRQOL measures. Adding another category adds complexity but limited value.</p> <p>This will affect compliance and ultimately effectiveness and should be considered as part of effectiveness.</p> <p>Not itself. It should be translated in efficacy and or safety.</p> <p>Convenience--should be captured as part of model and QALY impact.</p> <p>People with serious diseases are probably more OK with difficult and inconvenient pharmaceuticals than others. They mainly want something that works.</p> <p>I think the benefit of this dimension is largely captured through quality of life measures, tolerability and adherence.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>It depends if it makes the life of the patient substantially better. An at-home injection will have higher-quality of life than spending one day at an infusion center. However, this would not be captured with EQ-5D.</p> <p>From one way - if we have to compare the real benefit of medicine 1 vs medicine 2 in relation to the patient - for sure this information should be presented. But, manufacturers often speculate with such information and with public opinion and relate to treatment adherence, in such way that by the end the main specialist come to MoH, NHIC and require to include this medicine list in reimbursement system, but sometimes the cost of "ease and convention" is higher than health system threshold, and other patient have to "suffer" from this introduction (due to shrinking budget for disease).</p> <p>Depends. The ease of convenience has to translate in efficacy and /or safety.</p> <p>Should be included but preferably related to data indicating better compliance and less treatment discontinuation with regards to a medicine with a better ease and convenience.</p>

Medicine's economic impact (aspect 15 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Economic impact not as cost-effectiveness or ICER giving its methodological limitations (e.g. combination therapies not cost-effective at zero price etc.), suggestion below: - Direct cost comparison of the intervention - Indirect costs and savings to system - Wider system efficiencies and other benefits - Economic implications for patients - Economic implications for caregivers - Jobs and growth.</p> <p>If separate from the health/patient benefit assessment. It should also look at a wider economic perspective.</p> <p>This aspect has to be take into appoint, but for it is mandatory to elaborate a core set of variables and indicators that should be taken in calculation and to have possibility to reproduce independently (from manufacture or person who submit the dossier) presented data by experts/council members/ decision maker persons.</p> <p>Provided that there is no overlap between this criterion and others. Economic impact should not be assessed by means of incremental cost-effectiveness ratios. If the idea is to do it via ICERs, my answer changes into "no".</p> <p>If economic impact means incremental cost-effectiveness ratio.</p> <p>It would be great if we could see how it is possible that this aspect was not included in the first phase - it is amazing. I would be really interested - I also don't want this aspect to be important, but I think in reality it still is...maybe not for long though in the face of the social changes...</p>
No	<p>This should not be included as it will lead to discriminatory allocation of resources. e.g. favours those in work over out of work, favours higher paid over lower paid, favours men over women.</p> <p>Economic impact is too vague. Value should be compared with net cost.</p> <p>Counterproductive to the patient.</p> <p>The patient and their health should be the centre of focus.</p>
DK/DWA	This topic depends on the policy of the countries.

Medicine's affordability (aspect 16 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Budget impact important for decision makers, however HTA process should happen 1st with the clinical assessment and then proceed to add economic and budget considerations, which can be addressed in reimbursement, negotiation phase. Also, if budget allocation to health low, budget impact can be relative higher due to insufficient prioritization and resources to health. If budget impact as a criterion, the considerations above have to be addresses to guarantee good quality of HTA assessment and health decision making.</p>

	<p>First of all, the term medicine affordability is confusingly used, because a lot of expert will understand first of all like affordability used by WHO and HAI. The budget impact analysis, is very useful tool for middle income and low income countries (I suppose that not all countries have the capacity to read and analyse more in-depth methods of HTA). I suggest to change the name of affordability, and maybe after that it will be accepted by experts.</p> <p>This is important, but I would prefer to frame it as the scale of opportunity cost. If you have a low ICER med (12k) it may affect implementation speed rather than the decision. However, if it is a high ICER med (45k) then the decision may be different if it affects only a small number of patients with high unmet need, compared to a high number of patients, where the negative impact via opportunity cost will be more substantial.</p> <p>Important to consider budgetary impact of drugs where it is relevant.</p> <p>Budget impact.</p> <p>Economic impact and affordability appear to be overlapping.</p> <p>Just like before, I am completely amazed that this issue made it to the second phase...</p> <p>I would argue "budget impact" (BI) is not related to "value", but ultimately "affordability" needs to be taken into account when determining price and reimbursement status of new medicines. Also, if budget impact is included, do we need to define a "threshold" after which price is reduced (or company pays back, etc.)?</p> <p>I was uncertain because rare diseases and even common cancers are being streamlined into rare categories, should be an exception here.</p>
<p>No</p>	<p>Affordability and value considerations should be distinct.</p> <p>This is a political assessment and should not be confused with the clinical and economic assessment.</p> <p>Affordability is a political decision / issue, not HTA. HTA may help with estimating potential budget and service impact but not affordability.</p> <p>How do individual stakeholders define affordability? No generally accepted definition available.</p> <p>Affordability is a buzz term with more political charge than an objective definition. HTA should consider budget impact.</p> <p>This is an important aspect of decision making but I am not sure that having it as a criterion is the right way to incorporate it.</p> <p>Affordability: incorporate in threshold to compare to value.</p> <p>See previous comments in round one too.</p> <p>My concern with this is that it is a subjective measure as demonstrated well by the different decisions made in England by commissioning teams and will depend on who makes it.</p>

	The costs should not concern the patient.
DK/DWA	<p>As affordability is not standardized it could also include lack of willingness to pay rather than lack of funds. Affordability first needs to be standardized with respect to what does it mean in different countries and only then it could be included into the HTA assessment.</p> <p>Again, it's depending on health priorities of the countries.</p> <p>Not sure about the difference between this and previous attribute.</p> <p>This is not a clear question.</p>

Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (aspect 18 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Bias can work both ways e.g. crossover in oncology can underestimate true survival benefit. Wording this question as flaws in the design may be misleading. Sometimes there are good ethical reasons for the trial design (these should always be outlined along with regulatory body requirements) e.g. treatment switching, open-label. When undertaking HTA, the assessment of bias must also consider the ethics as well as magnitude of effect. Some HTA bodies are RCT purists and ignore PROs in highly ethical open label designs (e.g. oral, well tolerated vs IV with significant tolerability issues).</p> <p>Yes, because it can help to qualify some findings.</p> <p>Increasingly important aspect of HTA due to the decreasing quality of trials. It would be nice to have a more structured approach to incorporating this into decision making.</p> <p>Should this be defined as "quality of evidence" rather than in negative terms.</p> <p>Is risk of bias also assessed under "uncertainty"? If yes, then we should not include it (to avoid double counting).</p>
No	<p>HTA bodies should be very careful not to cause confusion around regulatory recommendations and decisions.</p> <p>Evaluation responsibility of regulatory agency, e.g. FDA.</p> <p>These are essential aspects to consider regarding a medicine's efficacy and effectiveness. However, this should be carried out by other regulatory agencies such as European Medical Agency, before reaching a HTA authority with focus on value based pricing. With experience from the Swedish setting, this is because a HTA body have to prioritize the health economic evidence where less time is given to consider the validity of clinical trials for an already approved drug.</p> <p>Bias--No but can be considered in deliberative process.</p>

	There are various mechanisms like MEA where we can insure against that. But I don't understand how we could take this into account if we still don't know about it? When we do, we will just adapt, but to take account of the risk is strange.
DK/DWA	To me if this happens, it should be send back to further research. Poorly formulated "aspect".

Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (aspect 21 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>If assessing the economic impact, then yes. If not, then is it relevant?</p> <p>This point should be take into account for some specific diseases like HIV/AIDS, TB, Malaria, Hepatitis, Diabetes etc.</p> <p>It only makes sense to reimburse a new medicine if there are the right health care structures in place for it. These health care structures must be identified in advance in order to be developed, if necessary.</p> <p>To be included as long as there is no double counting with the economic impact dimension.</p>
No	<p>It's an element that may mean different things to each stakeholder.</p> <p>Clearly the service has to consider these implementation issues (e.g. CAR-T), but that should not affect the HTA decision.</p> <p>This should be factored into the analysis of costs and timing of benefits. For example, if service reorganisation is needed benefits will be delayed.</p> <p>Organization--try to incorporate in system QALY and cost models.</p> <p>Would prefer to see these captured as part of the economic analysis rather than a standalone dimension.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>Overlap with consideration of the budgetary impact - apport of the medicine's affordability (aspect 16).</p> <p>Poorly formulated "aspect".</p>

Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (aspect 22 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>These can be important considerations and can align with context of the disease and medicines.</p> <p>Only if equity and ethical aspects can be objectively evaluated.</p>
No	Not a generally accepted definition feasible for all regulators.

	Equity--possibly, using Cookson-Asaria-Griffin inequality aversion. But maybe better as separate input to deliberative process.
DK/DWA	<p>This should be based on the values and priorities of the country assessing the medicine.</p> <p>Struggle with this one. The processes in HTA (assuming a universal healthcare system) are intrinsically fair, in that people with the same condition get the same treatment. It may not be fair that there are more medicines for one subgroup than another, but doesn't feel like HTA is the right mechanism to address that.</p> <p>It is not a pertinent criterion for the evaluation of the clinical benefit.</p> <p>Is this asking about equity for all patients with a certain disease or for all patients in a country regardless of what disease they have? Is the ethics issue about access or about treatment (for example, there was 'ethics' concern that introducing the HPV vaccine would be unethical because it could encourage promiscuity)?</p>

Medicine's environmental impact

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Consider this criterion as a bonus point rather than a core criterion - but very important to start integrating environmental considerations and goals in HC systems.</p> <p>Important - but no guidance today exists.</p> <p>Safer alternatives must be considered if available. If not, the appropriate handling and disposal measures must be clearly stated as part of the CTD and RCM documents.</p> <p>This should in principle be considered but not necessarily a priority.</p>
No	<p>Again, no generally accepted definition of environment from the perspective of pharmaceutical treatment.</p> <p>Ideally yes, but impossible in practice. Maybe in the medium term. In any case, environmental hazards are mainly related to the mass production of generics in Asia and China, where environment protection standards are less stringent. Expensive medicines are mostly produced in industrialized countries where standards are enforced. As a result, I do not think it is relevant right now.</p> <p>The impact on environment may be important, but should not be dealt with in an HTA context.</p> <p>While this is important, it should be addressed through tax and regulation, not via HTA. Trying to cost environmental impacts would open up a whole other field of economic assessment, and we are probably not best placed to do that.</p> <p>Not sure how this could be measured at the level of an individual medicine.</p> <p>Environment--vague--only as it affects QALYs and Costs.</p> <p>This is a regulatory issue in my view.</p>

	<p>Don't know.</p> <p>This should be a regulatory issue - whether it is fit for purpose.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>Maybe, could consider as part of an overall framework, but this would not be the highest priority factor.</p> <p>Usually very little information available.</p> <p>This is tricky. What should be preferred? Patients life or environment life?</p> <p>This is a very important question but I feel that should a new treatment actually jump through the hoop of the preceding value questions (1 to 9 above) then the environmental question should be posed, but not as a first objective. There are so few real innovations, we should be working on things that satisfy the first 9 points and then, taking into consideration the overly positive results that pharma publish, we might be really talking about important new treatments (quite rare nowadays) and ascertain their impact on the environment. So maybe some sort of secondary level of evaluation and the primary concerns.</p> <p>This needs to be clarified. Are we talking about the environmental impact of the manufacturing process or the waste produced at the point of consumption/use? The former would be very hard for HTA researchers to determine, but the later may be considered.</p>

Medicine's "value of hope"

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>This also aligns with potential unmet need - hope is a benefit (as we see with people playing the national lottery or praying). What is required is clear communication with patients on likelihood of achieving the hoped benefit.</p> <p>I believe that although the risk-benefit ratio cannot be proven in these cases it may prove useful through the palliative phase and thus unethical not to provide it to the patients with end of the line indication.</p> <p>Value of hope--uncertainty factor--see Lakdawalla and Phelps NBER working paper.</p> <p>I think this could be included, although it will be difficult to measure. But then, if we do not include it, we will never try to measure, and I think is an important dimension.</p> <p>This is very important to the patient.</p> <p>Definitely, hope is medicine in itself!</p>
No	<p>Depends on efficacy - if there is a small chance of being effective, the patient understands this, and this gives hope than 'yes' but if there is no realistic, demonstrated chance of effect I would say 'no'.</p> <p>A subjective component.</p> <p>This would introduce the idea of "moral luck" in the decision process, which would take us away from a purely rational and sound decision-making process. Just for</p>

	<p>your information: "Moral luck describes circumstances whereby a moral agent is assigned moral blame or praise for an action or its consequences even if it is clear that said agent did not have full control over either the action or its consequences."</p> <p>Big Pharma is very keen on selling hope rather than outcomes. I wonder why. As much as hope is worth paying for, it should be captured in QOL.</p> <p>If hope is a relevant domain, it should translate into improved quality of life (or at least aspects of it). We can measure quality of life and related domains in robust studies, if required. A loosely defined "value of hope" appears a weak justification to reimburse medicines that fail to demonstrate effectiveness on meaningful endpoints.</p> <p>Potentially of interest to discuss/test. Not at the moment. It would require a lot of work to substantiate; would be interesting to see examples of molecules people had in mind, how and where they were tested, what QoL/HRQoL data was collected and whether there are patient/carers narratives or views on overall experience.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>This factor may be considered in the future, but more research is needed.</p> <p>Need to research this issue more.</p> <p>Hope is very important but should be addressed in a different setting than the evaluation of a new drug. It would be so open to abuse. Our doctors and society should be giving hope. Evaluating hope would hardly be good science - important but not in this context.</p> <p>It is unclear exactly what value of hope is and how it is to be measured.</p> <p>Is delicate, if the hope will not become reality? Is important not to play with patients emotions, they already have emotional issues.</p>

Medicine's value as a bridge therapy

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Only in the sense that bridging in itself can bring patient benefit e.g. HIV drugs can prolong survival. One shouldn't include the assessment of some future imaginary new treatment bringing cure unless likely to occur.</p> <p>Yes, in certain circumstances e.g. while waiting for a transplant donor.</p> <p>Option value.</p> <p>Yes, in case of a clear perspective on future treatments (e.g. bone marrow therapy).</p> <p>Would include bridging to a definitive treatment (such as transplant), but not to unspecified future therapies, which may or may not be developed.</p> <p>Yes, it should be taken into account.</p> <p>Is this similar to the "option value" concept mentioned in the ISPOR task force on value frameworks (among others)?</p>

	Bridge therapy--yes but in QALY model. Maybe as "real option value".
No	<p>If current and future therapies are VB priced, I don't think it makes a difference.</p> <p>May be an important element for some severe diseases, but should be considered under clinical benefits.</p> <p>Can be dealt with using standard evaluation methods.</p> <p>The definition includes two options: bridge to existing treatment (e.g. because patient is not ready or some functions need to be 'prepared') or bridge to novel, in-development treatments. For me, there is a huge difference between these two. The first case is clear, but this should already be part of the effectiveness evaluation, as the medicine will in that case have an impact on the final outcomes of patients. For the second case, there is huge uncertainty. It is less valuable to include this aspect already in the value assessment.</p> <p>I am in two minds with this one, as I feel it could be important, but why should we "reward" this dimension? It will be very difficult to measure this element, and what happens if that new treatment is never launched? So ultimately, I have voted for "no".</p> <p>This is embedded in clinical utility, but ok, understand point. It would open a lot of arbitrary interpretations, particularly considering guideline variation, but certainly worth exploring.</p> <p>There are many clinical trial designs that allow for patients to go on and receive additional therapies. If the therapy is indeed intended to be a bridge therapy, this would likely already be captured in the other clinical dimensions.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>Maybe, this could be considered as a contextual factor.</p> <p>The "value" of this kind of therapies might lead to perpetual transitory status of being on the bridge and never crossing to the other side. Are we interested to play with a value of purgatory?</p> <p>Not clear of what means with bridge therapy.</p> <p>This one feels a bit dodgy too. Can we really justify this given that in some countries even the universal basket of care is being cut? Sounds really open to abuse by pharma and a luxury apart from maybe in the very very young.</p> <p>Is like hope, you promise a therapy and you don't know if the therapy will be authorized or not. Is important to offer a realistic perspective to the patients and not to offer promises with no support.</p>

Medicines' impact on patient functionality

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Yes, but this should be included in the evaluation of 'efficacy' in terms of quality of life.</p> <p>Functionality--reflected in QALY prediction.</p>

	<p>Sure, but this -to a substantial extent- can be captured through some tools/instruments; with care on double counting, etc.</p>
No	<p>Should be part of quality of life or PRO.</p> <p>This could be captured in the economic evaluation.</p> <p>This can be captured at medicine's impact on health related quality of life domain.</p> <p>This is absolutely important, but should already be captured in HRQOL. I'm not sure what value is added by having a separate category.</p> <p>This is covered by a proper effectiveness measure.</p> <p>Not itself. It should be translated in efficacy and or safety.</p> <p>Should be part of effectiveness assessment (impact on quality of life as outcome parameter). Adding an additional criterion for functionality would imply double counting in most instances.</p> <p>This point may have impact if systems of social and health care have one budget but this is not the case for all EU countries (incl. Czech Republic).</p> <p>I understand this to mean (instrumental) activities of daily living which should already be reflected in quality of life.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>Patient functionality is an aspect covered by many instruments regarding quality of life, hence would be redundant for many cases. While functionality may be more relevant than other aspects the case for separating one aspect of quality of life from others should be discussed.</p> <p>It has to translate in efficacy and safety.</p> <p>Should already be reflected in a patient's health-related quality of life.</p> <p>I don't understand this - functionality is just one aspect of HRQoL. Now, I don't understand why it should be specifically listed like a special item? Or maybe I misunderstood...</p> <p>Is "functionality" already included in HRQoL? if yes, then it should not be included.</p>

Medicine's time for treatment effect

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Should be considered as part of CUA if relevant to that market.</p> <p>This would be relative to how fast and underlying condition. A quick acting antibiotic for someone in ICU is highly relevant, aggressive cancers need fast acting therapies. But getting a response to therapy a few days or hours earlier when a doctor will make an assessment of treatment effect in four weeks' time is not relevant.</p> <p>Time to treatment effect--vague. Build into QALY and cost models.</p>

<p>No</p>	<p>Depends on how important speed is to a patient e.g. if symptoms are acute like pain then 'yes' - but if speed is not important to overall clinical outcome (e.g. speed of lowering cholesterol), then 'no'.</p> <p>It is already captured when you do cost-effectiveness models.</p> <p>To be considered under clinical impact.</p> <p>This would be captured in conventional health economics. Don't think it helps to have it as a separate category.</p> <p>Faster or slower effect is usually part of health economic evaluation (gain of QALY). If this is true, separate aspect is not necessary.</p> <p>This should be part of aggregated health gain.</p> <p>I am saying "no" to time for treatment effect, duration of treatment effect, and duration of adverse effects not because I don't think these aspects are important, but rather because I think they are too heterogeneous to be measured in a valid and reliable way. If measured in a clinical trial setting, I am hesitant to assume results would translate into the real-world setting of different, usually more complex patients.</p> <p>I guess this issue will be picked up in other dimensions measuring "outcomes"?</p> <p>Only dependent on drug options.</p> <p>This would depend on toxicity or whether the patient can tolerate the fast treatment. There should be choice.</p> <p>Interesting, but logistically challenging to measure in a lot of settings. This is more of a practicality issue around clinical trial design. In an ideal world we have continuous data for patients over the course of therapy rather than efficacy reported at discrete time intervals. But this is unfeasible in many settings.</p>
<p>DK/DWA</p>	<p>Do not know what "time for treatment effect" means.</p> <p>Should be reflected in a health economic model if there is any additional benefit to its comparator.</p> <p>This looks interesting. It probably depends upon the setting and the patient population being considered and whether the outcome was really worth waiting for. Sometimes, the extra health benefit is extremely marginal. Obviously, we all know that we want our health now and pay later, so perhaps this could be included as a secondary objective?</p> <p>Unclear question.</p> <p>More like a proxy measure with -potentially- tremendous variation. Without a concrete example or an established definition in a given jurisdiction, it is impossible to tell.</p>

Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Should be reflected in the efficacy measure.</p> <p>Duration--build into QALY and cost models.</p>
No	<p>Duration of treatment in itself is not a measure of value.</p> <p>Under clinical evaluation.</p> <p>This would be captured in the effectiveness evaluation. Taking a pill every day vs. "free of drug - free of disease" seems difficult to quantify separately.</p> <p>Again this is already captured by conventional health economics. Also, it is a substantial area of uncertainty particularly with newer high cost meds. It's probably unhelpful to emphasize a factor around which there is so much uncertainty, and no way to improve that uncertainty.</p> <p>Just part of effectiveness.</p> <p>Should already be included, be it indirectly, in effectiveness assessment. Not a value criterion in itself, only because of its impact on the treatment path of the patient.</p> <p>Effect of duration is also part of complex health economic model, as individual aspect is not necessary.</p> <p>This should be part of aggregated health gain.</p> <p>This looks like an alternative way of describing time to progression and similar endpoints. These are surrogate measures and strong preference should be given to meaningful endpoints that matter to patients, i.e. quality of life and survival.</p> <p>I answered NO as I thought the dosage reflects the strength and then this is already taken into account.</p> <p>Same comment as "time for treatment effect" - already picked up elsewhere?</p> <p>Interesting, but logistically challenging to measure in a lot of settings. This is more of a practicality issue around clinical trial design. In an ideal world we have continuous data for patients over the course of therapy rather than efficacy reported at discrete time intervals. But this is unfeasible in many settings.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>This is automatically considered in the clinical effectiveness.</p> <p>More than duration, what is important to take into account is the gradation of the curative nature to only symptomatic of short duration brought by the treatment.</p> <p>Same as for the previous comment. These are interesting aspects, and there are many different ways to capture them. It would be best to have examples and details on established definitions. Could be interesting to see patient views vs. clinician views on this and previous item.</p>

Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>If assessed mainly from a patient perspective; however this could also be a regulatory question instead.</p> <p>Could also be included under AE profile.</p> <p>I wonder if having only one criterion around adverse events which could capture all relevant aspects with one appropriate indicator would be better.</p> <p>AE duration--build into QALY and cost models.</p> <p>In conduction to adverse effects and SAEs too; see also item 1. There are specific definitions captured on grading the effects. These encompass duration. So, again, not quite sure what is being proposed here...</p>
No	<p>Already captured. We have the disutility of AEs and cost of treating those.</p> <p>Idem, sub-element of clinical impact.</p> <p>This can be captured at medicine's adverse events profile domain.</p> <p>Again this would be captured in outcomes/HRQOL, so little point in separating it out.</p> <p>Is part of the adverse effects assessment. Avoid double counting.</p> <p>The comment is the same like for the previous points.</p> <p>This should be part of aggregated health gain.</p> <p>I assume this will (could?) also be implicit in "adverse events"?</p> <p>This should be a clinician-patient decision.</p>
DK/DWA	<p>This is already considered in the clinical benefit.</p> <p>Should be reflected in a patient's gains in health related quality of life.</p> <p>Well, I basically imagined this was included in the existence of adverse effects - I don't see why it would not be, you don't really want to estimate yes/no, but what kind of effect it is: and this involved magnitude and duration. Just like QALY.</p>

Participants' comments second round

Medicine's adverse events profile (aspect 7 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	-
No	<p>I think most people are saying the same thing, though some have said yes and some no! It is essential to capture the impact of adverse events as they can be severe. The question is what value is added by having a separate category from mortality / HRQOL to capture it? Personally, I still feel an aggregate measure is better.</p> <p>Agree with comments that would be captured in AEs and QoL, so changed.</p> <p>AEs should be captured but aggregated into negative QALYS.</p>
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's tolerability to patients (aspect 8 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	Accept this may also be captured in AEs but feel this is really different and may not be captured that way so would still include it.
No	<p>Again this is captured within QALYs and time to treatment discontinuation in conventional models. I don't see the value of adding this as a separate category.</p> <p>Again a lot of the comments are similar in both the Yes votes and the No votes!</p> <p>Tolerability should be captured as part of aggregated health gain (i.e. QALY gain).</p>
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's mechanism of action (aspect 11 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	The drug's mechanism of action can influence the interaction with other drugs and potential side effects.
No	<p>I only see the relevance if mode of action has some clinical benefit.</p> <p>Main argument for this seems to be to stimulate innovation, and the side benefits for society. I don't think individual medication pricing is the best method for this (tax</p>

	incentives, prizes, direct funding are all better methods of driving innovation). It's a distraction from individual patient benefit. Patients do not usually care about it.
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's ease and convenience for patients (aspect 13 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	Issues on usability and compliance of treatments are two important factors. Current research for new treatments are focused on this and this must be encouraged.
No	Convenience should be captured as part of model and QALY impact. Not in itself, greater ease would need to translate into improved efficacy and safety compared to other products.
DK/DWA	It depends on the benefit it apport.

Medicine's economic impact (aspect 15 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	-
No	I'm finding this one difficult. Clearly economic impact as captured by ICER is important. But when broadens out to loss of income etc. becomes a real risk to equality. I've therefore voted no. I assume ICER is incorporated elsewhere. "Economic impact" is vague and unclear. Do you mean costs?
DK/DWA	You should clarify what do you mean for 'economic impact'.

Medicine's affordability (aspect 16 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	Affordability should be considered within economic impact, specifically within budget impact. Aspect needs to be defined clearly, and external effects on budgets (fiscal / political events) should be taken into consideration while assessing "affordability" of a medicine.

	<p>Affordability is a very subjective criterion.</p> <p>The same health product may or may not fit into the therapeutic arsenal according to the priorities and the basket of care adopted in a region or a country. It seems to me necessary to see the determinants of such a choice and the criteria favoring (e.g. replacement of a product, practice or organization) its implementation.</p> <p>Affordability needs to include affordability to health systems (including societal opportunity costs) and affordability to households and patients.</p> <p>Does it enter into 'patient's costs'?</p>
No	<p>Affordability only a consideration in as much as it informs cost effectiveness thresholds.</p> <p>I recognise this is important from a decision-making perspective but unsure how this element of value can be traded off with other benefits (e.g. adverse events). If the issue is mainly financial, should not this be tackled at a subsequent phase where payments methods can be defined?</p> <p>There is no well-defined metric for 'affordability'. It is not a value element - better to incorporate in threshold.</p> <p>I think most comments I see from colleagues are valid throughout, but adding an extra one for this one; you do need an established definition; considering you used the word affordability, I stick with my answer.</p>
DK/DWA	-

Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (aspect 18 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	I think this would be valuable to incorporate, but not sure how that would be done? Scoring trials for reliability?
No	<p>The bias or design risk should be assessed by the ethical committees monitoring the trials at the stage in which the trial is being conducted.</p> <p>Bias - poorly formulated concept, but can be considered in deliberative process.</p>
DK/DWA	-

Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (aspect 21 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	-
No	<p>This is an implementation issue not an assessment issue.</p> <p>Would prefer to see these captured as part of the economic analysis rather than a standalone dimension.</p> <p>This is an interesting aspect but too difficult to measure in common economic evaluation studies.</p>
DK/DWA	Too complex in my option, existing organizational structures might favour a particular disease or it will be difficult to judge this aspect similar across different medicines.

Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (aspect 22 in the initial Web-Delphi)

Answer	Comment
Yes	This is also very relevant but standard methods to measure the equity aspects should be developed.
No	<p>If HTA is carried out with rigour and good process, it should be inherently equitable.</p> <p>Equity - possibly, using Cookson-Asaria-Griffin inequality aversion. But maybe better as separate input to deliberative process.</p>
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's environmental impact

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>While this is probably not much of a problem, Western societies are more and more concerned about this topic. Drug evaluations should reflect societal preferences.</p> <p>Great to see such a support for this criteria! But we need to do better in round #3!</p> <p>An important implication, however, I'm not aware of any such guidance exists today or in the near future on how to systematically evaluate the environmental impact of a new medicine.</p> <p>Given that climate change is one of the two major threats to humanity as we know it, attention to environmental impact needs to be included in all aspects of</p>

	innovation. HTA will need to operationalize environmental impact of new technologies.
No	-
DK/DWA	It is an important criterion, but hard to measure and the question also is whether this should be managed through the healthcare budget. A more global strategy for dealing with environmental impact of medicines is required. Very relevant and 'hot' topic nowadays but difficult to include in standard HTA.

Medicine's "value of hope"

Answer	Comment
Yes	Value of hope, while it may not be fully measurable at this time, would address an important aspect of uncertainty, that would be relevant to patients and decision makers. Inclusion of the aspect would initiate development of methods/approaches to measuring it, which in turn would allow HTA to capture a broader impact of a medicine, hence increasing the quality and relevance of the assessment. This might be very important in rare diseases.
No	All treatments offer hope - in what way is this discriminant other than via the effectiveness which is already measured separately? Payer don't to pay for hope. Hope is/can be driven in part by advertising and should not be rewarded.
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's value as a bridge therapy

Answer	Comment
Yes	-
No	If all therapies are priced on VBP, I don't think it will bring additional value. I've switched my vote. For actual existing therapies, they will be incorporated in the economic model already. For bridging to future possible treatments, I think that is just hope in another guise. Accept comments again but this is a very difficult concept to measure I feel-bridge to what for example so stick with original view. When relevant, the value of a bridge therapy should be part of the product's efficacy assessment.

	Important only in rare clinical situations.
DK/DWA	-

Medicines' impact on patient functionality

Answer	Comment
Yes	<p>Patient functionality should be considered as an aspect. But this aspect should be captured within quality of life, not as a separate dimension.</p> <p>Only if it can be proven with relative certainty that this has not be capture or valued in any other factors.</p> <p>Changing if we consider it as an element of the effectiveness evaluation. Not to be considered separately.</p> <p>Surely important but already captured by PROMs such as EQ-5D.</p>
No	<p>Already captured in other dimensions, e.g. health related quality of life</p> <p>Functionality should be part of a comprehensive efficacy assessment (e.g., impact on HrQOL).</p>
DK/DWA	Should be covered by the impact on patients health-related quality of life.

Medicine's time for treatment effect

Answer	Comment
Yes	-
No	<p>Should be part of efficacy assessment.</p> <p>In general it is not important.</p>
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

Answer	Comment
Yes	Changing from no to yes if we consider the fact that it is the lasting of the effect, and the possibility to be a "free of drug free of disease" therapy. But it may be really tricky to appraise though.

	Important, but should not play a vital role in those evaluations where the difference in time to treatment effect is very small between two drugs. Yes, but already captured by survival and quality-adjusted survival.
No	Should be part of efficacy assessment.
DK/DWA	-

Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

Answer	Comment
Yes	-
No	I think this could be already captured at the medicine's adverse events profile dimension. Should be part of safety assessment.
DK/DWA	This aspect should be integrated with the one called "Medicine's adverse event profile".

Survey – comments regarding the second Web-Delphi process

Based on the comments, I think some of the aspects may need to be redefined. For instance, affordability, bridge therapy, ... When reading the comments, I got the impression that the same remark sometimes led to a 'yes' (e.g. yes, but under certain conditions), sometimes to a 'no' (e.g. no, because only under certain conditions) and sometimes to an 'I don't know' (in some cases yes, in some cases no). I found the comments also very interesting, as you can clearly see that there are different viewpoints and opinions, different 'schools' almost. This is very intriguing.

Fascinating process and comments, looking forward to the final report and publication of results.

I'm finding this round particularly frustrating. A lot of comments are similar regardless of whether people voted Yes, No or Don't Know. It suggests that there is either misunderstanding of the individual questions, or of the overall purpose of the Delphi. It's the same issue we see with miscommunication by email. It may have been more efficient to get us in a room for a weekend!

Many of the disagreements appeared to be due to overlap in suggested aspects. In these cases, my preferences were to avoid double counting and I cast "no" votes on aspects such as patient functionality, which would already form part of the effectiveness assessment.

Many thanks for let me take part of this Project!!!

Several items have potential overlap with each other, which may result in double counting.

Thanks a lot.

Thanks again for the opportunity to participate.

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

WP7 Task 2/3: Web-Delphi results for INAMI on the relevance of value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in five disease contexts

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1 Background information

This report forms part of IMPACT-HTA, a European-funded project (Grant Agreement No. 779312) focusing on the development of new and improved methods for the conduct of Health Technology Assessment (HTA). More information on IMPACT-HTA can be found online at <https://www.impact-hta.eu/>.

This is a study carried out within the context of Work Package 7 (WP7), dedicated to the development of actionable methodological tools using multi-criteria value methods for improved decision-making in HTA. The main objective of WP7 is to structure a generic multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) framework to assist HTA agencies in the evaluation of new drugs on a common basis, and subsequently to adapt and test the framework through empirical applications and case studies in collaboration with HTA agencies. Ultimately, the new value framework could act towards a common approach for value assessment and appraisal across HTA agencies.

In Task 1 of WP7, an econometric analysis of the determinants of HTA recommendations was conducted by relying on secondary data across eight settings. In Task 2 of WP7, a large number of HTA stakeholders was invited to reflect upon “which aspects should be considered in this novel framework to assist HTA agencies to evaluate new medicines on a common basis”. Specifically, six stakeholder panels independently provided their views about the relevance of aspects collected from Task 1 within a Web-Delphi process, with an option to comment and suggest new aspects. Results from the six panels were analysed and discussed with a group of 11 participants representing all stakeholder groups in a decision conferencing format. The combined results from the first Web-Delphi process and the decision conference were then validated in a second Web-Delphi with a single panel consisting of participants from all six stakeholder groups, proposing a preliminary list of 20 generic value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in HTA.

In Task 3, the information generated in Task 2 will be used to validate, finalise and test the new value framework with INAMI-RIZIV in Belgium. Specifically, a three-round Web-Delphi process was conducted with several stakeholders to provide information on the relevance of a list of value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in five disease contexts. Further, a short semi-structured interview with INAMI-RIZIV representatives will be held, and lastly two case studies will be conducted in the form of virtual decision conferences.

The objective of this report is to provide an overview of the synthesized results of the Web-Delphi process conducted with INAMI-RIZIV in Belgium.

2 Web-Delphi process and participation

The Web-Delphi process included a total of three rounds that took place between May 6th and September 14th, 2020. The aim of the first round was to validate the preliminary list of 20 generic value aspects from Task 2 (already validated by INAMI-RIZIV representatives), by giving the option of adding any additional value aspect(s) that might have been missed, that should be considered in the evaluation of new medicines from the perspective of INAMI-RIZIV in Belgium.

The aim of the second and third rounds was to identify the relevance of the finalised list of 24 value aspects (that resulted from round 1) across five disease contexts, by choosing the following classification and definitions:

- **Essential:** this aspect must be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it is not possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); it is not possible to reach an evaluation recommendation without explicitly considering performance on this aspect.
- **Influential:** this aspect is highly desirable to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it could still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); the lack of favourable performance on this aspect could influence the decision in a detrimental way, as a desirable benefit may not be captured.
- **Complementary:** this aspect is advantageous to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it would still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); favourable performance on this aspect could act supportively to complement the designated purpose of the medicine, i.e. "nice-to-have".
- **Irrelevant:** this aspect does not necessarily need to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (evidence of the medicine's performance on it, does not influence if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose).

The following five disease contexts were considered by participants:

1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.

2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.
3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.
4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for non alcoholic steatohepatitis.
5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

Information regarding the number of participants, and the distribution of participants by stakeholder group in each round is shown in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively.

Table 1. Number of participants in each round of the Web-Delphi process

HTA agency	No. Invited	Completed Round 1	Completed Round 2		Completed Round 3	
INAMI	36	17	14	Drop-out 17.6%	13	Drop-out 7.1%

Table 2. Number of participants in each round of the Web-Delphi process by stakeholder group (as self-reported by participants).

Stakeholder group	INAMI		
	R1	R2	R3
Health care professionals, e.g. clinicians, pharmacists, etc.	5	3	3
HTA bodies, e.g. HTA committees, evidence assessors, etc.	5	5	5
Industry, e.g. pharmaceutical companies, industry associations, etc.	3	2	1
Payers and policymakers, e.g. ministry of health, local/central government, etc.	2	2	2
General population, e.g. taxpayers, citizen representatives, etc.	1	1	1
None of the above	1	1	1
Total	17	14	13

3 Web-Delphi results

In this section, the main results of the Web-Delphi process conducted with INAMI-RIZIV in Belgium are presented, specifically:

1. The validated list of value aspects that resulted from round 1.
2. The final voting results for the relevance of each value aspect, per disease context from round 3

The participants' comments from rounds 2 and 3 are presented in Appendix 1.

3.1 Final list of value aspects

Three value aspects – Disease frequency (e.g. rarity); Medicine's spill-over effects; and Medicine's mechanism of action – were added to the preliminary list of 20 value aspects, based on the feedback from round 1. The final validated list of value aspects is shown in Table 3 (the added value aspects are highlighted in blue).

Table 3. Final validated list of value aspects for INAMI-RIZIV (i.e. 20 value aspects from Task 2 plus 3 value aspects from round 1, in blue)

Value Aspects
A - Severity of the disease
B - Unmet need of the disease
C - Medicine's impact on mortality
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life
F - Medicine's adverse events profile
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community
J - Medicine's economic impact
K - Medicine's affordability
L - Medicine's efficiency
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)
V - Medicine's spill-over effects
W - Medicine's mechanism of action

3.2 Voting results per value aspect, per disease context

The voting results per value aspect and per disease context for round 3 of the Web-Delphi are presented in Tables 4, 5, 6 and 7.

Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.

Table 4. Voting results per value aspect from round 3 for disease context 1.

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	6	4	1	1	1
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	9	4	0	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	8	4	1	0	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	9	4	0	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	7	6	0	0	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	8	4	1	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	2	3	6	2	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	7	4	1	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	7	5	0	1	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	7	5	1	0	0

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	2	3	7	1	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	0	4	7	1	1
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	5	4	0	4
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	4	8	1	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	2	1	6	3	1
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	4	3	0	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	5	5	3	0	0
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1	2	8	2	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	4	6	3	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	0	0	10	3	0

Note: DN/DWA: Don't know/ Don't want to answer

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.

Table 5. Voting results per value aspect from round 3 for disease context 2.

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	8	2	2	1	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	8	5	0	0	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	7	6	0	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	6	7	0	0	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	5	8	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	7	5	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	6	5	1	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	6	6	1	0	0

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	1	6	5	1	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	2	5	2	2
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	3	6	3	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	5	3	5	0	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	9	4	0	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	7	4	2	0	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	4	6	3	0	0
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	5	3	4	1	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	3	8	2	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	2	6	4	0

Note: DN/DWA: Don't know/ Don't want to answer

Disease Context 3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.

Table 6. Voting results per value aspect from round 3 for disease context 3.

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
A - Severity of the disease	7	4	1	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	6	5	1	1	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	13	0	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	9	4	0	0	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	7	6	0	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	6	7	0	0	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	3	6	4	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	3	7	3	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	8	3	1	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	10	2	0	1	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	7	4	1	1	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	6	5	2	0	0

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	3	6	3	1	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	2	7	1	1
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	1	2	8	0	2
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	4	4	5	0	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	2	4	6	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	6	1	0	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	5	6	2	0	0
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	3	4	3	2	1
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	4	8	1	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	0	1	8	3	1

Note: DN/DWA: Don't know/ Don't want to answer

Disease Context 4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for non alcoholic steatohepatitis.

Table 7. Voting results per value aspect from round 3 for disease context 4.

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
A - Severity of the disease	9	3	0	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	9	2	1	1	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	13	0	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	7	5	1	0	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	8	5	0	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	8	5	0	0	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1	7	5	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	3	3	6	1	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	11	1	0	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	8	3	0	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	8	5	0	0	0

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	3	4	5	1	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1	3	5	3	1
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	5	5	1	2
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	1	4	8	0	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	5	2	6	0	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	7	4	2	0	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	4	6	3	0	0
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	5	4	1	3	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	1	4	6	1	1
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	2	7	3	0

Note: DN/DWA: Don't know/ Don't want to answer

Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

Table 8. Voting results per value aspect from round 3 for disease context 5.

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
A - Severity of the disease	5	4	3	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	3	2	2	6	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	8	1	2	2	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	10	2	0	1	0
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	9	3	0	1	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	9	3	0	1	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	9	3	0	1	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	3	9	1	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	4	5	1	3	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	11	0	1	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	9	2	0	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	10	2	1	0	0

Value Aspect	Round 3 (n=13)				
	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant	DN/DWA
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	2	5	5	1	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	1	7	2	1
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	3	1	6	3
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	3	6	3	1	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	3	5	4	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	4	2	1	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	6	4	2	1	0
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	0	4	3	6	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	3	8	2	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	4	5	3	0

Note: DN/DWA: Don't know/ Don't want to answer

Appendix 1 - Participants' comments

The participants' comments from rounds 2 and 3 regarding the relevance of the value aspects across the different disease contexts are available in Tables 9 and 10, respectively.

Table 9. Participants' comments from round 2.

ROUND 2	
Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.	
Value aspect	Comment
A - Severity of the disease	All fields are completed from the point of view of the FAHMP (regulatory agency).
	The disease already having been characterized as "severe".
B - Unmet need of the disease	Automatically provided as compared to the current alternative.
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	In case of transmissible disease.
L - Medicine's efficiency	Highly recommended if uncertainty and/or high budget impact.
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Not competent to judge.

O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	Inapplicable in Belgium.
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Will also be influenced by the type of next therapy.
	Already captured in other aspects, e.g. efficiency, impact on morbidity/mortality, organisation of care...
	Question unclear.
	We have a situation of several treatment possibilities. The fact that the new medicine is a bridge to an existing treatment, is very difficult to comment on, in terms of essential, complementary...
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	Partly included in QoL already.
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	What is important is the impact on morbidity/mortality.
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Is it really different from mortality impact?
	Already captured in morbidity/mortality etc... Duplication?
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Already captured in morbidity/mortality/tolerability profile etc... Duplication?
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	Not relevant in Context 1 (earlier indication).
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	In previous submission.
Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.	
Value aspect	Comment

I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Transmissible rare disease? Probably not relevant in context 2.
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	Irrelevant in Belgium.
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Cf comment in context 1.
	Question unclear.
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	Cf comment in context 1.
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
Disease Context 3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.	
Value aspect	Comment
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Transmissible in this context 3?
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	Particularly in a chronic orphan disease, often in pediatric and disabled children. E.g. if we can avoid visits at hospitals and have home care.
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	Irrelevant in Belgium
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Cf comment in context 1
	Question unclear.
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	Cf comment in context 1.

S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Rarity is by definition the case for orphan disease.
Disease Context 4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for non alcoholic steatohepatitis.	
Value aspect	Comment
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Crucial if transmissible.
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	High prevalence medicine, so risk of inequity in this context?
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Cf comment in context 1.
	Question unclear.
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Cf comment in context 1.
Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.	
Value aspect	Comment
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	Irrelevant in Belgium.
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Cf comment in context 1.

	Question unclear. For a disease with a high prevalence and with several treatment options, the factor "bridge to another treatment" is difficult to place. Either irrelevant either unknown.
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	Cf comment in context 1.
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Cf comment in context 1.
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	High frequency is by default in this context 5.

Table 10. Participants' comments from round 3.

ROUND 3	
Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.	
Value aspect	Comment
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Very dependent of situation: other therapies available, impact of next therapy, disease
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	If not considered as integrated to effect on morbidity/mortality/efficiency, and considered as a separated element, then of course, it is of major relevance.

T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	If not considered as integrated to effect on morbidity/mortality/efficiency, and considered as a separated element, then of course, it is of major relevance.
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	Most important is clinical improvement as compared to available therapies
Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.	
Value aspect	Comment
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	If not considered as integrated to effect on morbidity/mortality/efficiency, and considered as a separated element, then of course, it is important.
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	If not considered as integrated to effect on morbidity/mortality/efficiency, and considered as a separated element, then of course, it is of major relevance.
Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.	
Value aspect	Comment
B - Unmet need of the disease	There are other therapeutic classes available in this context.
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	Especially in comparison to other available treatments.
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Important in comparison to other available treatments.
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Especially in comparison to other available treatments.
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Context = high prevalence chronic disease.